

FJÖLRIT

NÁTTÚRUFRAEÐISTOFNUNAR

ANNOTATED CHECKLIST OF VASCULAR PLANTS OF ICELAND

Paweł Wąsowicz

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Fjölrit Náttúrufræðistofnunar er ritröð sem hóf göngu sína árið 1985. Birtar eru greinar og skýrslur eftir starfsmenn og fræðimenn sem vinna í samvinnu við þá. Í hverju hefti er ein sjálfstæð grein um náttúrufræði. Útgáfan er óregluleg. Greinar eru ritaðar á íslensku með enskum útdrætti. Þær mega einnig vera á ensku en þá skal ávallt fylgja ítarlegur útdráttur á íslensku.

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ABSTRACT

The present edition of the annotated checklist is a comprehensive catalogue of all vascular plant taxa: native and alien that occur in Iceland. The checklist features nearly 2500 taxa names, including ca. 1000 accepted names and more than 1400 synonyms and encompasses, apart from the updated list of native taxa, a complete and revised list of non-native plants (both naturalized and casual) as well as a number of more important cultivated species. According to the checklist, there are 426 native taxa in the Icelandic flora. Ten taxa have been classified as doubtfully native, ten taxa have been classified as

non-native of unknown age and 19 taxa qualified as archaeophytes. There are at least 65 non-native taxa naturalized in the Icelandic flora. In total, there are 530 taxa able to form self-sustaining populations in Iceland. Apart from the main core, 282 taxa have been registered as casual aliens (not able to form self-sustaining populations). One species – *Primula egaliksensis*, has been classified as extinct. The list encompasses also 150 taxa excluded from the Icelandic flora, with brief explanations of the reasons that lead to the exclusion.

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NÁTTÚRUFRAEDISTOFNUN ÍSLANDS, mars 2020

INTRODUCTION

Annotated Checklist of Vascular Plants of Iceland is a comprehensive catalogue of plant species that occur in Iceland, and it is primarily based on extensive herbarium collections of the Icelandic Institute of Natural History stored in two herbaria: AMNH (Akureyri) and ICEL (Garðabær). The first modern checklist of the Icelandic flora was published more than a decade ago by Kristinsson (2008) and served as an excellent basis for further research on the diversity and taxonomy of vascular plants. However, the present edition of the checklist goes beyond the first by adding a significant amount of information, including many more species names and synonyms. Overall, the new edition of the checklist features nearly 2500 taxa names, including ca. 1000 accepted names and more than 1400 synonyms. This new edition of the Icelandic checklist encompasses, apart from the updated list of native taxa, a complete and revised list of non-native plants (both naturalized and casual). A number of more important cultivated species (especially those used widely in forestry) are also listed owing to their potential to become naturalized in the near future.

Non-native taxa

There is no doubt that a number of species regarded as native by Kristinsson (2008) are, in fact, old anthropochorous taxa (archaeophytes) that came to Iceland with the man and became naturalized a long time ago – during landnám (settlement of Iceland), medieval times and even later. The origin of those species still remains largely unresolved, but in the present checklist, a new category – an archaeophyte – was introduced in order to differentiate putative „old aliens”, i.e. alien species arriving before 1770, from native taxa following Wasowicz (2018). Sometimes, there are doubts about whether a taxon in question can be treated as archaeophyte. In this case, two new taxa categories were introduced to classify these taxa correctly: (1) doubtfully native taxa, (2) non-native taxa of unknown age - see Wasowicz (2018).

The status of new aliens (neophytes) in Iceland is usually clear, but when one subspecific taxon is native and the other is non-native, or when two subspecific taxa differ in terms of the stage of the naturalisation process, this information was also indicated with appropriate symbols.

Doubtful and discounted taxa records

We cannot avoid the fact that over the past centuries, much data on the Icelandic flora has been accumulated in many different published and unpublished accounts and lists. One of the main aims of the present edition of the checklist is to review and critically assess these sources. This review showed that doubtful species records are present both in old floristic lists (from the 18th and 19th centuries) as well as in more modern floras published in the 20th century. In order to clarify this question, a group of taxa excluded from Icelandic flora (151 in total) was also added to the present edition of the checklist. Each species excluded from Icelandic flora is listed and the reasons for its exclusion are briefly specified in the footnotes.

Taxonomy and Latin nomenclature

In order to highlight the diversity of the Icelandic flora and to register the maximal number of taxa that can be unambiguously distinguished narrow definitions of taxa were preferred in the present edition of the checklist. In most cases, where discrepancies with respect to the species or subspecies rank of a taxon existed, the higher taxonomic rank was applied. When the presence of transitional forms and the lack of clear habitat preferences was unambiguously confirmed the lower taxonomic ranks were applied. The present edition of the Checklist does not list most of the hybrid taxa, an exception was made for several well established and fairly common hybrids of native taxa and several cultivated plants.

Families in the checklist were organised according to the systematic order, while species within families were organised alphabetically. Linear sequences of families follow the most recent classifications: Christenhusz et al. (2011b) for lycophytes and ferns, Christenhusz et al. (2011a) for gymnosperms, and the Angiosperm Phylogeny Group – APG IV (2016) for angiosperms.

Only taxon names that fully comply with the terms of the International Code of Botanical Nomenclature were listed here as valid, accepted names.

Each record of the checklist consists of:

1. accepted Latin name of a taxon in question followed by author citation (accepted names of native taxa were given in boldface) e.g. ***Lycopodium clavatum*** L.;
2. name citation;
3. a common name in Icelandic; and
4. a list of synonyms (including, when relevant, a basionym) and misapplied names.

Apart from very few exceptions where several synonyms were introduced in order to enhance clarity, records of excluded taxa do not contain any synonyms. Instead, a list of records by different authors was compiled on the basis of the available literature. The list frequently features names used by these authors to refer to the species in question (these are not necessarily synonyms in a strict sense).

In a variety of cases, the introduction of subspecific taxa was necessary. They are listed below each record and may contain a list of synonyms for each accepted subspecific name as well as distinct common names (where applicable).

The present checklist is by no means a final and perfect work. In many cases, modern taxonomic revisions of plant material from Iceland have not been carried out yet. Therefore, the list of species from several genera (including *Taraxacum*, *Hieracium* and *Euphrasia*) should be treated with extreme caution and regarded as very preliminary. In fact, these most problematic taxa contain merely a list of species known from previous investigations. Clearly, further investigation is needed to obtain a better understanding of the biological diversity within these genera in Iceland.

In order to differentiate taxa on the list and classify them in different categories (e.g. according to their origin and/or naturalization status) a set of symbols was used:

- a doubtfully native taxon
- a naturalized non-native taxon
- ▶ a non-native taxon of unknown age
- ◆ an archaeophyte
- a casual alien
- > a microspecies known from Iceland, being a part of species aggregate or section
- ◇ a cultivated taxon
- * a taxon entered provisionally
- ▼ a taxon excluded from the Icelandic flora
- † an extinct taxon

Basic statistics

According to the present treatment, there are 426 native taxa in the Icelandic flora (including eight provisionally accepted native taxa, 14 species aggregates in *Hieracium* and the genus *Taraxacum* counted as one taxon). In addition, ten taxa have been classified as doubtfully native, ten taxa have been classified as non-native of unknown age and 19 taxa qualified as archaeophytes (c.f. Wasowicz 2018). The present data suggest that at least 65 non-native taxa that came to Iceland only recently became naturalized in the Icelandic flora. All in all, the main core of the flora of Iceland is formed by 530 taxa (both native and alien) that are able to form self-sustaining populations (Fig. 1). One species has been classified as extinct (Wasowicz and Heiðmarsson 2019).

Apart from this main core, there are 282 taxa that have been registered at least once outside cultivation in Iceland but are not able to form self-sustaining populations (causal aliens).

There are four families that are most species-rich and account for 35% of the total number of native taxa: Cyperaceae, Poaceae, Asteraceae, and Caryophyllaceae. The remaining families (84 in total) account for 65 % of the total number of taxa, but the share of each family is less than 5% (Fig. 2.)

Fig. 1. The share of selected taxa categories in the total flora of Iceland.

Fig. 2. Main families in the native flora of Iceland.

DEFINITIONS OF TERMS AND ABBREVIATIONS USED

archaeophyte – a plant species which is non-native to a geographical region, but which was introduced in "ancient" times, rather than being a modern introduction. In Iceland, archaeophytes are considered to be those species first introduced prior to 1770. Time limits for the introduction of archaeophytes may be different in different areas (Preston et al. 2004, Wasowicz 2018).

auct. (auctorum) – a name used in the sense of a number of subsequent authors and not in its (different) sense as established by the original author. It is often used in conjunction with „nec“ or „non“ to indicate a misapplied name (Turland et al. 2018)

basionym – the first valid and legitimate name ("base name") used for a taxon (Turland et al. 2018)

casual aliens – alien plants that may flourish and even reproduce occasionally outside cultivation in an area, but that eventually die out because they do not form self-replacing populations, and rely on repeated introductions for their persistence (Richardson et al. 2000, Pyšek et al. 2004)

comb. ined. (combinatio inedita) – a combination that appears not to have been validly published or whose publication is uncertain under one or more articles of International Code of Nomenclature for algae, fungi, and plants (ICN) (Turland et al. 2018)

comb. illeg. (combinatio illegitima) – a validly published name that is not in accordance with one or more rules in ICN (Turland et al. 2018)

doubtfully native plants – plant taxa that cannot be classified neither as native nor as non-native on the basis of available evidence.

introduction – introduction means that the plant (or its propagule) has overcome, through human agency, a major geographical barrier (Richardson et al. 2000)

native plants – taxa that have originated in a given area without human involvement or that have arrived there without intentional or unintentional intervention of humans from an area in which they are native (Pyšek et al. 2004)

naturalized plants (established plants) – non-native plants that sustain self-replacing populations for at least 10 years without direct intervention by people (or in spite of human intervention) by recruitment from seed or ramets (tillers, tubers, bulbs, fragments, etc.) capable of independent growth (Richardson et al. 2000, Pyšek et al. 2004)

neophyte – a plant species which is not native to a geographical region, and was introduced in recent history (Preston et al. 2004).

nom. cons. (nomen conservandum) – a name of a family, genus, or species, or in certain cases a name of a subdivision of a genus or of an infraspecific taxon, declared legitimate, even though it may have been illegitimate when published, and taking precedence over other specified names even if it lacks priority (Turland et al. 2018)

nom. illeg. (nomen illegitimum) – a validly published name that is not in accordance with one or more rules of ICN (Turland et al. 2018)

nom. illeg. hom. (nomen illegitimum homonymum) – a validly published name that is not in accordance with the one or more of the rules on homonymy, a later or junior homonym (Turland et al. 2018)

nom. rej. (nomen rejiciendum) – a name rejected in favour of a name conserved or a name ruled as rejected (Turland et al. 2018)

nom. superfl. (nomen superfluum) – superfluous name; usually used for illegitimate names where the correct name or basionym is mentioned at the time of publication (Turland et al. 2018)

non-native plants – plant taxa in a given area whose presence there is due to intentional or accidental introduction as a result of human activity (synonyms: exotic plants, non-native plants; non-indigenous plants) (Richardson et al. 2000, Pyšek et al. 2004)

non-native plants of unknown age – non-natives that cannot be classified neither as archaeophytes nor as neophytes on the basis of available evidence

orth. var. – orthographic variant

synonym – one of two or more names that apply to the same taxon (Turland et al. 2018)

taxon – a taxonomic group at any rank (Turland et al. 2018).

CHECKLIST OF VASCULAR PLANTS – PLÖNTUTAL**LYCOPODIACEAE** P. Beauv. ex Mirb.

Hist. Nat. Vég. 4: 293 (1802)

Jafnaætt

Huperzia appressa (Bach.Pyl. ex Desv.) Á. Löve & D. Löve¹

Bot. Not. 114: 34 (1961)

Paufafingur

- *Lycopodium selago* f. *appressum* Bach.Pyl. ex Desv., Mém. Soc. Linn. Paris 6: 180 (1827)
- *Huperzia selago* subsp. *appressa* (Bach.Pyl. ex Desv.) D. Löve, Nucleus (Calcutta) 1(1): 8 (1958) comb. illeg.
- *Lycopodium selago* subsp. *appressum* (Bach.Pyl. ex Desv.) Hultén, Ark. Bot., n.s., 7(1): 7 (1968)

Huperzia arctica (Grossh. ex Tolm.) Sipliv.²

Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 10: 347 (1973)

Skufsafingur

- *Lycopodium selago* subsp. *arcticum* Grossh. ex Tolm., Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk SSSR 20: 39 (1960)
- *Huperzia selago* subsp. *arctica* (Grossh. ex Tolm.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 35 (1961)

Huperzia selago (L.) Bernh. ex Schrank & Mart.

Hort. Reg. Monac.: 3 (1829)

Skollafingur

- *Lycopodium selago* L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1102 (1753)

Lycopodium alpinum L.³

Sp. Pl.: 1104 (1753)

Litunarjafni

- *Diphassium alpinum* (L.) Rothm., Feddes Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 54: 65 (1944)
- *Lycopodium complanatum* L., auct. non L. (1753)
- *Diphasiastrum alpinum* (L.) Holub, Preslia 47: 107 (1975)

1 *Huperzia* is a very complicated genus that requires urgent taxonomic revision with the use of combined morphological, cytological and molecular data. As for now there are two opinions on the taxonomy of the genus in Northern Europe: (1) treating the three morphological groups as subspecies within *Huperzia selago* (Kukkonen 2000), or (2) assuming the presence of three separate species (Wagner and Beitel 1993). There are different arguments to support both points of view (see e.g. Alsos et al. 2019), but it seems that in the present state of knowledge both views are equally justified. Here, the latter view is adopted in order to highlight the clear diversity present in the Icelandic populations of *Huperzia*.

2 Plants clearly belonging to the morphotype *arctica* are present in Iceland in the highest parts of the mountains of the Tröllaskagi peninsula (N Iceland). Whether the species is also present in other regions is still unknown.

3 Cf. Christenhusz et al. (2011b)

***Lycopodium annotinum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1103 (1753)

Lyngjafni

- *Lycopodium annotinum* L. subsp. *annotinum*
- *Lycopodium annotinum* subsp. *alpestre* (Hartm.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, *Nucleus* (Calcutta) 1(1): 7 (1958)
- *Lycopodium annotinum* var. *alpestre* Hartm., *Handb. Skand. Fl.*, ed. 2: 294 (1832)
- *Lycopodium annotinum* var. *pungens* Desv. ex Spring, *Nouv. Mém. Acad. Roy. Sci. Bruxelles* 15: 78 (1842)
- *Lycopodium annotinum* subsp. *pungens* (Desv. ex Spring) Hultén, *Ark. Bot.*, n.s., 7(1): 7 (1968)
- *Lycopodium dubium* Zoëga, *Fl. Isl.*: 11 (1772)

***Lycopodium clavatum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1101 (1753)

Burstajafni

ISOËTACEAE Dumort.

Anal. Fam. Pl. 67 (1829)

Álftalauksætt

***Isoëtes echinospora* Durieu⁴**

Bull. Soc. Bot. France 8: 164 (1861)

Álftalaukur

***Isoëtes lacustris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1100 (1753)

Vatnalaukur

▼ ***Isoëtes muricata* Durieu⁵**

Bull. Soc. Bot. France 11: 100 (1864)

- by Löve (1970)

SELAGINELLACEAE Willk.

Anleit. Stud. Bot. 2: 163 (1854)

Mosajafnaætt

***Selaginella selaginoides* (L.) P. Beauv. ex Schrank.**

Prodr. Aethéogam.: 101 (1805)

Mosajafni

- *Lycopodium selaginoides* L., Sp. Pl.: 1101 (1753)
- *Selaginella selaginoides* (L.) Schrank & Mart., *Hort. Reg. Monac.*: 3 (1829)
- *Selaginella spinulosa* A. Braun, *Rhein. Fl.* 38 (1843)

4 There are two views on the taxonomy of the *Isoëtes echinospora* aggregate. Taylor et al. (1993) included both European and N American plants in one taxon under the name of *I. echinospora*, referring only to presence or absence of stomata as a diagnostic character. Elven et al. (2011) accepted two species: N American *I. muricata* and European *I. echinospora*, referring to additional differential characters. Here, the latter point of view is adapted.

5 Icelandic plants were classified as *I. muricata* [= *Isoëtes echinospora* subsp. *muricata* (Durieu) Á. Löve & D. Löve] by Löve (1970). This classification was later questioned by different authors including Snogerup and Snogerup (2000) as well as Elven et al. (2011). Elven et al. (2011) suggests that Löve wanted to strengthen the impression of a significant American element in the Icelandic flora. There is no support for the presence of *I. muricata* in Iceland.

EQUISETACEAE Michx. ex DC.

Essai Propr. Méd. Pl.: 49 (1804)

Elftingarætt

Equisetum arvense L.

Sp. Pl.: 1061 (1753)

Klóelfting

Equisetum arvense L. subsp. ***arvense***
Equisetum arvense subsp. ***alpestre*** (Wahlenb.) Schönswetter & Elven⁶

J. Bot. Res. Inst. Texas 2: 433 (2008)

- *Equisetum arvense* var. *alpestre* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 296 (1812)
- *Equisetum boreale* auct. non Bong. (1833)
- *Equisetum arvense* var. *boreale* auct. non Rupr. (1845)
- *Equisetum arvense* subsp. *boreale* auct. non Á. Löve (1948)

Equisetum fluviatile L.

Sp. Pl.: 1062 (1753)

Fergin

- *Equisetum limosum* L., Sp. Pl.: 1062 (1753)

Equisetum hyemale L.

Sp. Pl.: 1062 (1753)

Eski

- *Hippochaete hyemalis* (L.) Bruhin, Verh. K.K. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 18: 760 (1868)

Equisetum* × *mackaii (Newman) Brichan

 [*Equisetum hyemale* × *variegatum*]

Phytologist 1: 369 (1843)

Eskibróðir

- *Equisetum* × *trachyodon* (A. Braun) Koch, Flora 22: 305 (1839)
- *Hippochaete* × *trachyodon* (A. Braun) Börner
- ? *Equisetum hyemale* var. *moorei* sensu Stefánsson (1901)

Equisetum palustre L.

Sp. Pl.: 1061 (1753)

Mýrelfting

Equisetum pratense Ehrh.

Hannover. Mag. 22: 138 (1784)

Vallelfting

- *Equisetum umbrosum* J.G.F. Meyer ex Willd., Enum. Pl. (Willdenow) 2: 1065 (1809)

 ▼ *Equisetum scirpoides* Michx.⁷

Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2: 281

- by Rostrup (1887)
- by Bennett (1890)

6 Kristinsson (2008) recognised two subspecies within *E. arvense*: nominal and subsp. *boreale* (Bong.) Á. Löve. Both Schönswetter et al. (2001) and Elven et al. (2011) argue that the latter name has been misapplied. The name *E. boreale* Bong., Mém. Acad. Imp. Sci. St.-Pétersbourg, sér. 6, Sci. Math. 2: 174 (1833) [syn. *E. arvense* var. *boreale* (Bong.) Rupr., Hist. Stirp. Fl. Petrop.: 91 (1845); *E. arvense* subsp. *boreale* (Bong.) Á. Löve, Náttúrufræðingurinn 18: 101 (1948)] is based on a plant belonging to subsp. *arvense* and therefore should not be applied to arctic and high alpine plants.

7 The species is listed by Rostrup (1887) and Bennett (1890) from Eyjafjörður. No specimens are available to confirm these records and the species has never been recorded from Iceland by other authors. Misidentification of *E. variegatum* is the most probable explanation of these doubtful records.

***Equisetum sylvaticum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1061 (1753)

Skógelfting

***Equisetum variegatum* Schleich. ex Weber & Mohr**

Deut. Crypt. Gewächse 60: 447 (1807)

Beitieski

- *Hippochaete variegata* (Schleich. ex Weber & Mohr) Bruhin, Verh. K.K. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 18: 760 (1868)

▼ *Equisetum arvense* × *fluviatile*⁸*Equisetum litorale* Kuehlew. ex Rupr., Beitr. Pflanzenk. Russ. Reich. 4: 91 (1845)

- by Grøntved (1942)

OPHIOGLOSSACEAE Martinov

Tekhno-Bot. Slovar.: 438 (1820)

Naðurtunguætt

***Botrychium boreale* Milde**

Bot. Zeitung (Berlin) 15: 880 (1857)

Mánajurt

***Botrychium lanceolatum* (S.G. Gmel.) Ångström**

Bot. Not. 1854: 68 (1854)

Lensutungljurt

- *Osmunda lanceolata* S.G. Gmel., Novi Comment. Acad. Sci. Imp. Petrop. 12: 516 (1768)

***Botrychium lunaria* (L.) Sw.**

J. Bot. (Schrader) 1800, 2: 110 (1801)

Tungljurt

- *Osmunda lunaria* L., Sp. Pl.: 1064 (1753)

Botrychium lunaria* (L.) Sw. var. *lunaria***Botrychium lunaria* var. *melzeri* Stensvold & Farrar⁹**

Brittonia 69: 165 (2017)

***Botrychium minganense* Vict.**

Proc. & Trans. Roy. Soc. Canada, ser. 3, 21: 331 (1927)

Keilutungljurt

- *Botrychium lunaria* var. *minganense* (Vict.) Calder & R.L. Taylor, Canad. J. Bot. 43: 1388 (1965)

***Botrychium nordicum* Stensvold & Farrar¹⁰**

Brittonia 69: 173 (2017)

Skorutungljurt

8 Grøntved (1942) lists this hybrid on the basis of a single, sterile and poorly preserved specimen from Vallanes (E Iceland). It seems safe to exclude this hybrid from the Icelandic flora as no other records are known.

9 A newly described taxon endemic to Greenland, Iceland and Norway.

10 A newly described species from the *B. lunaria* complex, known from Iceland and Norway

Botrychium simplex E. Hitchc.

Amer. J. Sci. Arts 6: 103, t. 8 (1823)

Dvergtungljurt

*** *Botrychium tenebrosum*** A.A. Eaton¹¹

Fern Bull. 7: 8 (1899)

Renglutungljurt

- *Botrychium simplex* var. *tenebrosum* (A.A. Eaton) R.T. Clausen, Bull. Torrey Bot. Cl. 64(5): 275 (1937)

Ophioglossum azoricum C. Presl¹²

Suppl. Tent. Pterid.: 49 (1845)

Naðurtunga

- *Ophioglossum vulgatum* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Ophioglossum vulgatum* var. *minus* auct. non Moore (1856)
- *Ophioglossum vulgatum* var. *polyphyllum* sensu Grønlund (1881); Stefánsson (1901)
- *Ophioglossum vulgatum* var. *islandicum* Á. Löve & D. Löve, nom.nud.

HYMENOPHYLLACEAE Mart.

Consp. Regn. Veg.: 3 (1835)

Mosaburknaætt

Hymenophyllum wilsonii Hook.

Brit. Fl. 1: 446 (1830)

Mosaburkni

PTERIDACEAE E.D.M. Kirchn.

Schul-Bot.: 109 (1831)

Vængburknaætt

Cryptogramma crispa (L.) R. Br. ex Hook.

Gen. Filic.: t. 115B (1842)

Hlíðaburkni

- *Osmunda crispa* L., Sp. Pl.: 1067 (1753)
- *Pteris crispa* (L.) All., Fl. Pedem. 2: 284 (1785)
- *Allosorus crispus* (L.) Bernh., Neu. J. Bot. 12: 36 (1806), ex Spreng., Syst. 4: 65 (1827)

11 Entered provisionally. This species was treated previously as a variety of *B. simplex*. Recent results (allozyme and chloroplast DNA data) suggest however, that the taxon should be recognised on species level (Donald Farrar, pers. comm.). Genetic data from Icelandic populations clearly show that Icelandic specimens can not be included in *B. simplex* (Wasowicz, unpubl.). It is still not clear, however, whether they belong to *B. tenebrosum* or to unrecognised or yet unidentified taxon. Ongoing molecular analyses are expected to solve this problem.

12 Numerous early authors listed the species under the name *O. vulgatum* (Grønlund 1881, Stefánsson 1901, Grøntved 1942).

CYSTOPTERIDACEAE Schmakov

Turczaninowia 4: 60 (2001)

Tófugrasætt

Cystopteris fragilis (L.) Bernh.¹³

Neues J. Bot. 1, 2: 27 (1805)

Tófugras (Refagras)

- *Polypodium fragile* L., Sp. Pl.: 1091 (1753) "filix-fragile"
- *Cystopteris filix-fragilis* (L.) Borbás, Balaton Fl.: 314 (1900)
- *Cystopteris dentata* (Sw.) Desv., Mém. Soc. Linn. Paris 6: 263 (1827)
- *Cystopteris dickieana* R. Sim, Gard. Farmer's J. 2(20): 308 (1848)
- *Cystopteris fragilis* var. *dickieana* (R. Sim) T. Moore, Handb. Brit. Ferns: 81 (1848)
- *Cystopteris fragilis* subsp. *dickieana* (R. Sim) Hook. f., Student Fl. Brit. Isl.: 464 (1870)

Gymnocarpium dryopteris (L.) Newman

Phytologist 4: 371 (1851)

brílaufungur

- *Polypodium dryopteris* L., Sp. Pl.: 1093 (1753)
- *Aspidium dryopteris* (L.) Baumg., Enum. stirp. Transs. 4: 29 (1846)
- *Dryopteris linnaeana* C. Chr., Index Filic.: 275 (1905)
- *Dryopteris pulchella* (Salisb.) Hayek, Fl. Steiermark 39 (1908)
- *Carpogymnia dryopteris* (L.) A. Löve & D. Löve, Univ. Color. Stud. Biol. 24: 8 (1966)
- *Lastrea dryopteris* (L.) Bory, Dict. Class d'Hist. Nat. 9: 233 (1826)

ASPLENIACEAE Newman

Hist. Brit. Ferns: 6 (1840)

Klettaturknaætt

▼ ***Asplenium fontanum*** (L.) Bernh.¹⁴

J. Bot. 1799(1): 314 (1799)

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Polypodium fontanum*
- by Baring-Gould (1863)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Asplenium septentrionale (L.) Hoffm.

Deutschl. Fl. Crypt. 12 (1795)

Skeggburkni

- *Acrostichum septentrionale* L., Sp. Pl.: 1068 (1753)

13 Löve (1970) on the basis of spore morphology recognised two distinct species in Iceland: *C. fragilis* and *C. dickieana*. Until recently, plants with echinate spores (*fragilis* type) and rugose spores (*dickieana* type) have been recognised as two species, subspecies or varieties. Macromorphologically both types cannot be separated (Elven et al. 2011). Recent studies (Dyer et al. 2000, Parks et al. 2000) rejected *C. dickieana* as a separate taxon.

14 No specimens are available to confirm the occurrence of this species in Iceland. Mentioned for the first time by König and Müller (1770), then by Baring-Gould (1863) and Babington (1871) from Þingvellir. The occurrence of this species in Iceland has never been confirmed later and seems to be very unlikely.

***Asplenium trichomanes* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1080 (1753)

Svartburkni

– *Asplenium melanocaulon* Willd., Enum. Fil. 1072 (1809) ***Asplenium trichomanes* L. subsp. *trichomanes*** ▼ *Asplenium trichomanes* subsp. *quadrivalens* D.E. Meyer¹⁵

Ber. Deutsch. Bot. Ges. 74: 456 (1962)

***Asplenium viride* Huds.**

Fl. Angl.: 385 (1762)

Klettaburkni

THELYPTERIDACEAE Pic.Serm.

Webbia 24: 709 (1970)

Þríhyrnuburknaætt

***Phegopteris connectilis* (Michx.) Watt**

Canad. Naturalist & Quart. J. Sci., n.s., 3: 159 (1867)

Þríhyrnuburkni

– *Polypodium connectile* Michx., Fl. Bor. Amer. 2: 271 (1803)– *Polypodium phegopteris* L., Sp. Pl.: 1089 (1753)– *Lastrea phegopteris* (L.) Bory, Dict. Class d'Hist. Nat. 9: 233 (1826)– *Aspidium phegopteris* (L.) Baumg., Enum. stirp. Transs. 4: 28 (1846)– *Dryopteris phegopteris* (L.) C. Chr., Index Filic.: 284 (1905)– *Thelypteris phegopteris* (L.) Sloss. in Rydb., Fl. Rocky Mts: 1043 (1917)▼ ***Thelypteris palustris* Schott¹⁶**

Gen. Fil. ad t. 10 (1834)

Mýraburkni

– by König and Müller (1770) as *Acrostichum thelypteris* L.– by Babington (1850) as *Lastrea thelypteris* (L.) Bory

– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

WOODSIACEAE Herter

Rev. Sudamer. Bot. 9: 14 (1949)

Liðfætluætt

***Woodsia alpina* (Bolton) Gray¹⁷**

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 17 (1821)

Fjallaliðfætla

– *Acrostichum alpinum* Bolton, Filic. Brit. 2: 76 (1790)– ? *Woodsia ilvensis* var. *alpina* (Bolton) Watt– *Woodsia glabella* auct. non R. Br. ex Richardson (1823)

15 Kristinsson (2008) mentioned two subspecies present in Iceland: nominal and subsp. *quadrivalens* D.E. Mey. Subsequent revision of herbarium material in AMNH and ICEL showed that only subsp. *trichomanes* is present in Iceland.

16 There are no specimens available to confirm the presence of *T. palustris* in Iceland. Misidentification is the most probable cause of the records mentioned above.

17 Initially misdiagnosed as *Woodsia glabella*, e.g. Grøntved (1942)

Woodsia ilvensis (L.) R. Br.

Trans. Linn. Soc. London 11: 173 (1815)

Liðfætla

- *Acrostichum ilvense* L., Sp. Pl.: 1071 (1753)

BLECHNACEAE Newman

Hist. Brit. Ferns, ed. 2: 8 (1844)

Skollakamsætt

Struthiopteris fallax (Lange) S. Molino, Gabriel y Galán & Wasowicz¹⁸

Pl. Syst. Evol. 305: 266 (2019)

Tunguskollakambur

- *Struthiopteris spicant* var. *fallax* (Lange) Wasowicz & Gabriel y Galan, Phytotaxa 302: 198 (2017)
- *Blechnum spicant* var. *fallax* Lange., Fl. Dan., Fasc. 50, no. 2983, figs. 2 & 3 (1880)

Struthiopteris spicant (L.) Weiss¹⁹

Pl. Crypt. Fl. Gott. 287 (1770)

Skollakambur

- *Osmunda spicant* L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1066 (1753)
- *Blechnum spicant* Mém. Acad. Turin 5: 411 (1793)
- *Blechnum spicant* (L.) Roth, Usteri Ann. 10: 56 (1794)
- *Blechnum spicant* (L.) With., Bot. Arrang. ed. III, 3: 765 (1796) comb. superfl.
- *Blechnum boreale* (Salisb.) Sw., Schrad., J. Bot. 1800(2): 75 (1801)

ATHYRIACEAE Alston

Taxon 5: 25 (1956)

Fjöllaufungsætt

Athyrium distentifolium Tausch ex Opiz

Tent. Fl. Crypt. Boem. 2, 1: 14 (1820)

Þúsundblaðarós

- *Polypodium rhaeticum* L., Sp. Pl. 2: 1091 (1753)
- *Aspidium alpestre* Hoppe, Neues Bot. Taschenb. 1805: 216 (1805)
- *Polypodium alpestre* Hoppe, Taschenb. 137 (1799) (nomen), ex Spenn., Fl. Frib. 1: 12 (1825)
- *Athyrium alpestre* (Hoppe) Rylands, Ferns Gr. Br. nat. Print, t. 7 (1857)

Athyrium filix-femina (L.) Roth

Tent. Fl. Germ. 3, 1: 65 (1799)

- *Polypodium filix-femina* L., Sp. Pl.: 1090 (1753)
- *Asplenium filix-femina* (L.) Bernh. in Schrad., Neu. J. Bot. 12: 26, 48, t. 2, f. 7 (1806)

Athyrium filix-femina L. subsp. **filix-femina**

Fjöllaufungur

18 This taxon has been newly elevated to species rank (Molino et al. 2019) and currently is known just from one location in Iceland where it grows on a warm geothermal soil.

19 According to a new classification of *Blechnaceae* (de Gasper et al. 2016) the species is now classified within genus *Struthiopteris* Scop., Meth. Pl. 25. (1754).

DRYOPTERIDACEAE Herter

Rev. Sudamer. Bot. 9: 15 (1949), nom. cons.

Skjaldburknaætt

Dryopteris expansa (C. Presl) Fraser-Jenk. & Jermy²⁰

Brit. Fern Gaz. 11: 338 (1977)

Dílaburkni

- *Nephrodium expansum* C. Presl, Reliq. Haenk. 1: 38 (1825)
- *Lastrea dilatata* var. *alpina* Moore, Handb. Brit. Ferns, ed. 3: 126 (1857)
- *Dryopteris assimilis* S. Walker, Amer. J. Bot. 48: 607 (1961)
- *Dryopteris dilatata* auct. non (Hoffm.) Gray (1848)
- *Dryopteris austriaca* auct. non (Jacq.) Woyнар, Schinz & Thellung (1915)
- *Aspidium spinulosum* var. *dilatatum* auct. non (G.F. Hoffmann) Hampe (1836)

Dryopteris filix-mas (L.) Schott

Gen. Fil. 1: t. 9 (1834)

Stóriburkni

- *Polypodium filix-mas* L., Sp. Pl.: 1090 (1753)
- *Aspidium filix-mas* (L.) Sw., Schrad., J. Bot. 1800(2) 38 (1802)
- *Lastrea filix-mas* (L.) C. Presl, Tent. Pterid. 76 (1836)
- *Dryopteris abbreviata* auct. non Newm. (1891)

Polystichum lonchitis (L.) Roth

Tent. Fl. Germ. 3(1): 71 (1799)

Skjaldburkni

- *Polypodium lonchitis* L., Sp. Pl.: 1088 (1753)
- *Aspidium lonchitis* (L.) Sw., Schrad., J. Bot. 1800(2): 30 (1802)
- *Dryopteris lonchitis* (L.) O. Kuntze, Rev. Gen. Pl. 1: 813 (1891)

POLYPODIACEAE J. Presl & C. Presl

Delic. Prag.: 159 (1822)

Köldugrasætt

Polypodium vulgare L.

Sp. Pl.: 1085 (1753)

Köldugras

PINACEAE Spreng. ex F. Rudolphi

Syst. Orb. Veg.: 35 (1830) nom. cons.

Þallarætt

◇ *Abies balsamea* (L.) Mill.

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: Abies No. 3 (1768)

Balsamþinur

◇ *Abies concolor* (Gordon) Lindl. ex Hildebr.

Verh. Naturhist. Vereines Preuss. Rheinl. Westphalens 18: 261 (1861)

Hvítþinur

²⁰ *Dryopteris expansa* has many times been misidentified in Iceland and determined as *Dryopteris austriaca* (Jacq.) Woyнар, Schinz & Thellung by Stefánsson (1948); *Dryopteris dilatata* (Hoffm.) A. Gray, by Löve (1970) or *Aspidium spinulosum* var. *dilatatum* (G.F. Hoffmann) Hampe by Stefánsson (1901). All material annotated as *D. austriaca*, *D. dilatata*, *D. expansa* or *D. assimilis* and preserved in AMNH and ICEL herbaria belong to *D. expansa*.

- ◇ *Abies lasiocarpa* (Hook.) Nutt.
N. Amer. Sylva 3: 138 (1849)
Fjallapínur
- ◇ *Abies nordmanniana* (Steven) Spach
Hist. Nat. Vég. Phan. 11: 418 (1841)
Norðmannspínur
- ◇ *Abies sibirica* Ledeb.
Fl. Altaica 4: 202 (1833)
Síberíupínur
- ◇ *Larix decidua* Mill.
Gard. Dict., ed. 8: Larix No. 1 (1768)
Evrópulerki
- ◇ *Larix gmelinii* (Rupr.) Kuzen.
Trudy Bot. Muz. Rissijsk. Akad. Nauk 18: 41 (1920)
Dáríulerki
– *Larix cajanderi* Mayr, Fremdl. Wald-Parkbäume: 297 (1906)
- ◇ *Larix kaempferi* (Lamb.) Carrière
Fl. Serres Jard. Eur. (Ghent) 11: 97 (1856)
Japanslerki
- ◇ *Larix laricina* (Du Roi) K. Koch
Dendrol. 2 (2): 263 (1873)
Mýralerki
- ◇ *Larix lyallii* Parl.
Conif. Nov.: 3. Jan. (1863)
Fjallalerki
- ◇ *Larix occidentalis* Nutt.
N. Amer. Sylva 3: 143, t. 120 (1849)
Risalerki
- ◇ *Larix sibirica* Ledeb.
Fl. Altaica 4: 204 (1833)
Síberíulerki
– *Larix sukaczewii* Dylis, Khvoin. Por. 50: 489 (1945)
- ◇ *Larix* × *marschlinsii* Coaz (*L. decidua* × *L. kaempferi*)
Sifjalerki
– *Larix* × *eurolepis* Henry nom. illeg.
- ◇ *L. decidua* × *L. sukaczewii*
Hrymur
- ◇ *Picea abies* (L.) H. Karst
Deutsche Fl.: 324 (1881)
Rauðgreni

- ◇ *Picea engelmannii* Parry ex Engelm.
Trans. Acad. Sci. St. Louis 2: 212 (1863)
Blágréni
- ◇ *Picea glauca* (Moench) Voss
Mitt. Deutsch. Dendrol. Ges. 1907 (16): 93 (1907)
Hvítgréni
- ◇ *Picea mariana* (Mill.) Britton, Sterns & Poggenb.
Prelim. Cat. 71 (1888)
Svartgréni
- ◇ *Picea pungens* Engelm.
Gard. Chron., ser. 2, 11: 334 (1879)
Broddgréni
- ◇ *Picea sitchensis* (Bong.) Carrière
Traité Gén. Conif.: 260 (1855)
Sitkagréni
– *Pinus sitchensis* Bong., Mém. Acad. Imp. Sci. Saint-Petersbourg, sér. 6, Sci. Math. 2: 164 (1832)
- ◇ *Picea* × *lutzii* Little
J. Forest. (Washington) 51: 745 (1953)
- ◇ *Pinus albicaulis* Engelm.
Trans. Acad. Sci. St. Louis 2: 209 (1863)
Klettafura
- ◇ *Pinus aristata* Engelm.
Amer. J. Sci. Arts, ser. 2, 34: 331 (1862)
Broddfura
- ◇ *Pinus cembra* L.
Sp. Pl. 2: 1000 (1753)
Lindifura (Sembráfura)
- ◇ *Pinus contorta* Douglas ex Loudon
Trudy Bot. Muz. Rissijsk. Akad. Nauk 18: 41 (1920)
Stafafura
- ◇ *Pinus flexilis* E. James
Account Exped. Pittsburgh 2: 27, 35 (1823)
Sveigfura
- ◇ *Pinus mugo* Turra
Giorn. Italia Sci. Nat. 1: 152 (1764)
Fjallafura
- ◇ *Pinus sibirica* Du Tour
Déterville, Nouv. Dict. Hist. Nat. 18: 18 (1803)
Silfurfura (Siberíufura)

◇ *Pinus sylvestris* L.

Sp. Pl. 2: 1001 (1753)

Skógarfura

◇ *Pinus uncinata* Ramond ex DC.

Lamarck & Candolle, Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 3: 726 (1805)

Bergfura

◇ *Pseudotsuga menziesii* (Mirb.) Franco

Conif. Duarum Nominibus 4 (1950)

Döglingsviður

◇ *Tsuga heterophylla* (Raf.) Sarg.

Silva N. Amer. 12: 73, t. 605 (1899)

Marþöll

◇ *Tsuga mertensiana* (Bong.) Carrière

Traité Gén. Conif., ed. 2, 1: 250 (1867)

Fjallapöll

CUPRESSACEAE Gray

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 222, 225 (1822), nom. cons.

Sýprisætt (Einisætt)

◇ *Cupressus nootkatensis* D. Don

Lambert, Descr. Pinus 2: 18 (1824)

Alaskasýprus

Juniperus communis L.

Sp. Pl.: 1040 (1753)

Einir

Juniperus communis L. subsp. ***communis***

Juniperus communis subsp. ***nana*** (Willd.) Syme²¹

Engl. Bot., ed. 3B, 8: 275 (1868)

– *Juniperus nana* Willd., Sp. Pl. 4, 2: 854 (1806), nom. illeg.

– *Juniperus communis* var. *nana* (Willd.) Čelak., Prodr. Fl. Böhmen 1: 17 (1867)

– *Juniperus communis* var. *alpina* Sm., Fl. Brit. 3: 1086 (1804) nom. illeg.

– *Juniperus communis* subsp. *alpina* (Sm.) Čelak., Prodr. Fl. Böhmen 1: 17 (1867)
nom. illeg.

– *Juniperus communis* var. *montana* Aiton, Hort. Kew. 3: 414 (1789)

◇ *Thuja koraiensis* Nakai

Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 33: 196 (1919)

Kóreulífviður

◇ *Thuja occidentalis* L.

Sp. Pl. 2: 1002 (1753)

Kanadalífviður

21 In Grønlund (1881) as *Juniperus alpina* Clus.

NYMPHAEACEAE Salisb.

Ann. Bot. (König & Sims). 2: 70 (1822), nom. cons.

Nykurrósætt

○ *Nuphar pumila* (Timm) DC.

Syst. Nat. 2: 61 (1821)

Dvergnykurrós (Dvergvatnalilja)

TOFIELDIACEAE (Kunth.) Takht.

Bot. Zhurn. (Moscow & Leningrad) 79(12): 65 (1995)

Sýkigrasætt

▼ *Tofieldia calyculata* (L.) Wahlenb.²²

Fl. Lapp.: 90 (1812)

Spóafótur

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Anthericum calyculatum* L.

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Tofieldia pusilla (Michx.) Pers.

Syn. Pl. 1: 399 (1805)

Sýkigras (Bjarnarbroddur)

- *Narthecium pusillum* Michx., Fl. Bor.-Amer. 1: 209 (1803)- *Tofieldia borealis* (Wahlenb.) Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 89 (1812)- *Anthericum calyculatum* auct. non L. (1753)- *Tofieldia palustris* auct. non Huds. (1778)**HYDROCHARITACEAE** Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 67 (1789), nom. cons.

Froskablaðsætt

● *Egeria densa* Planch.

Ann. Sci. Nat., Bot., sér. 3, 11: 80 (1849)

Kransarfi

● *Vallisneria spiralis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 1015 (1753)

Skrúfugras

JUNCAGINACEAE Rich.

Démonstrations Botaniques: 9 (1808), nom. cons.

Sauðlauksætt

Triglochin maritima L.

Sp. Pl.: 339 (1753)

Strandsauðlaukur

²² *T. calyculata* was mentioned by some early authors. There are no specimens to confirm these records and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

***Triglochin palustris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 338 (1753)

Mýrasauðlaukur

ZOSTERACEAE Dumort.

Anal. Fam. Pl. 65–66 (1829)

Marhálmsætt

***Zostera angustifolia* (Hornem.) Rchb.**

Icon. Fl. Germ. Helv. 7: 3 (1845)

Marhálmur

- *Zostera marina* var. *angustifolia* Fl. Dan. 9, 26: 3, t. 1501 (1816)
- *Zostera hornemanniana* Tutin, J. Bot. 74: 227 (1936)
- *Zostera marina* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Zostera stenophylla* sensu Löve (1983) non Raf. (1818)

POTAMOGETONACEAE Bercht. & J. Presl

Prir. Rostlin Aneb. Rostl. 1(Sig. 7*-13): 1,3 (1823), nom. cons.

Nykrætt

***Potamogeton alpinus* Balb.**

Mém. Acad. Sci. Turin, Sci. Phys. 10–11, 1: 329 (1804)

Fjallnykra

- *Potamogeton rufescens* Schrad., Fl. Berol. 5 (1815)
- *Potamogeton nigrescens* Fr., Novit. Fl. Suec. Mant. 3: 17 (1842)
- *Potamogeton lanceolatus* auct. non Sm. (1809)

***Potamogeton berchtoldii* Fieber**

Oekon.-Techn. Fl. Böhm. 2(1): 277 (1838)

Smánykra

- *Potamogeton pusillus* var. *tenuissimus* Mert. & W.D.J. Koch in Röhl., Deutschl. Fl., ed. 3, 1: 857 (1823)
- *Potamogeton pusillus* subsp. *tenuissimus* (Mert. & W.D.J. Koch) R.R. Haynes & Hellq., Novon 6: 370 (1996)
- *Potamogeton pusillus* auct. non L. (1753)

***Potamogeton compressus* L.²³**

Sp. Pl.: 127 (1753)

Sverðnykra

▼ ***Potamogeton crispus* L.²⁴**

Sp. Pl.: 126 (1753)

Hrukkunykra

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Vahl (1840)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

23 *P. compressus* was found growing in Iceland in 2012. Currently, known just from one lake.

24 *P. crispus* is present in some of the older lists. There are no specimens available and the species has never been found later.

***Potamogeton gramineus* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 127 (1753)

Grasnykra

- *Potamogeton heterophyllus* Schreb., Spic. Fl. Lips.: 21 (1771)

▼ ***Potamogeton lucens* L.²⁵**

Sp. Pl.: 126 (1753)

Gljánykra

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Potamogeton "lucidum"*
- by Vahl (1840)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Potamogeton natans* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 126 (1753)

Blöðkunykra

▼ ***Potamogeton obtusifolius* Mert. & W.D.J. Koch²⁶**

Deutschl. Fl. (Mertens & W.D.J. Koch), ed. 3, 1: 855 (1823)

Pollanykra

- by Bjarnason (1977)
- by Löve (1983)

***Potamogeton perfoliatus* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 126 (1753)

Hjartanykra

▼ ***Potamogeton polygonifolius* Pourr.²⁷**

Mém. Acad. Sci. Toulouse 3: 325 (1788)

Rauðnykra

- by Rostrup (1887)
- by Bennett (1890)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Potamogeton praelongus* Wulfen**

Arch. Bot. (Leipzig) 3: 331 (1805)

Langnykra

***Stuckenia filiformis* (Pers.) Börner**

Fl. Deut. Volk: 713 (1912)

Þráðnykra

- *Potamogeton filiformis* Pers., Syn. Pl. 1: 152 (1805)
- *Coleogeton filiformis* (Pers.) Les & R.R. Haynes, Novon 6: 390 (1996)
- ? *Potamogeton "maritimum"* sensu König and Müller (1770)
- *Potamogeton marinus* sensu Grønlund (1881), non L. (1753)

25 *P. lucens* was mentioned by König and Müller (1770) and then copied by other authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been observed later.

26 *P. obtusifolius* has been recorded fairly recently from Meðalfellsvatn (SW Iceland) but the evidence supporting its presence are too weak to include it into Icelandic flora with certainty.

27 *P. polygonifolius* was recorded in Iceland by A. Feddersen, but later on this finding was found to be a misidentification.

▼ *Stuckenia pectinata* (L.) Börner²⁸

Fl. Deut. Volk: 713 (1912)

Burstanykra

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Potamogeton pectinatus*
- by Babington (1871)
- by Rostrup (1887)
- by Bennett (1890)

***Zannichellia palustris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 969 (1753)

Hnotsörvi

- *Zannichellia palustris* subsp. *repens* (Boenn.) Schübl. & G. Martens, Fl. Württemberg: 579 (1834)
- *Zannichellia polycarpa* Nolte ex Rchb., Handb. Gewächsk. ed. 2, 3: 1590 (1850)

RUPPIACEAE Horan.

Prim. Lin. Syst. Nat.: 46. (1834), nom. cons.

Lónajurtarætt

Ruppia cirrhosa (Petagna) Grande

Bull. Orto Bot. Regia Univ. Napoli 5: 58 (1918)

Flóðjurt

***Ruppia maritima* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 127 (1753)

Lónajurt

- *Ruppia cirrhosa* subsp. *longipes* (Hagstr.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 49 (1961)

MELANTHIACEAE Batsch ex Borkh.

Bot. Wörterb. 2: 8 (1797), nom. cons.

Ferlaufungsætt

***Paris quadrifolia* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 367 (1753)

Ferlaufungur

LILIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 48 (1789), nom. cons.

Liljuætt

○ *Lilium bulbiferum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 302 (1753)

Eldlilja

28 *S. pectinata* has been recorded from Iceland most probably as a results of a misidentification of *S. filiformis*.

ORCHIDACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 64 (1789), nom. cons.

Brönugrasætt

▼ *Anacamptis morio* (L.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase²⁹

Lindleyana 12: 120 (1997)

Vormunagras

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Orchis morio*
- by Hooker (1811)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Coeloglossum viride (L.) Hartm.

Handb. Skand. Fl.: 329 (1820)

- *Satyrium viride* L., Sp. Pl.: 944 (1753)
- *Dactylorhiza viridis* (L.) R.M. Bateman, Pridgeon & M.W. Chase, Lindleyana 12: 129 (1997)
- *Habenaria viridis* sensu Stefánsson (1901), non R. Br. (1813)
- *Peristylus viridis* (L.) Lindl., Syn. Brit. Fl., ed. 2: 261 (1835)

Coeloglossum viride subsp. ***islandicum*** (Lindl.) Kreutz

Barnarót

- *Peristylus islandicus* Lindl., Gen. Sp. Orchid. Pl.: 297 (1835)
- *Coeloglossum viride* var. *islandicum* (Lindl.) M. Schulze, Oesterr. Bot. Z. 48: 113 (1898)

Corallorhiza trifida Châtel.

Specim. Inaug. Corallorhiza: 8 (1760)

Krækjurót

- *Ophrys corallorhiza* L., Sp. Pl.: 945 (1753)
- *Corallorhiza innata* W.T. Aiton, Hortus Kew. 5: 209 (1813)
- *Ophrys camtschatea* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Epipactis nidus-avis* auct. non Crantz (1769)

▼ *Dactylorhiza fuchsii* (Druce) Soó³⁰

Nom. Nov. Gen. Dactylorhiza: 8 (1962)

Töfragrös

- by Kristinsson (2008)

29 The occurrence of *A. morio* is very unlikely in Iceland. No specimens are available to confirm early records.

30 The presence of *D. fuchsii* in Iceland has been suggested by Kristinsson (2008) on the basis of some oral communications, but there is still not enough proof to accept this species from Iceland.

▼ *Dactylorhiza incarnata* (L.) Soó³¹Nom. Nov. Gen. *Dactylorhiza*: 3 (1962)

Munaðargras

- by Gliemann (1824) and Babington (1871) as *Orchis cruenta*
- by König and Müller (1770) as *Orchis latifolia*
- by Babington (1850, 1871)
- by Stefánsson (1901, 1948)
- by Ostenfeld and Grøntved (1934)
- by Davíðsson (1937)

Dactylorhiza maculata (L.) SoóNom. Nov. Gen. *Dactylorhiza*: 7 (1962)

Brönugrös

- *Orchis maculata* L., Sp. Pl.: 942 (1753)³²
- *Dactylorchis maculata* (L.) Verm., Stud. Dactyl.: 130 (1947)
- *Dactylorchis maculata* subsp. *islandica* Á. Löve & D. Löve, Rep. Dept. Agric. Univ. Inst. Appl. Sci. (Reykjavik), ser. B, 3: 106 (1948)
- *Dactylorhiza maculata* subsp. *islandica* (Á. Löve & D. Löve) Soó, Nom. Nov. Gen. *Dactylorhiza*: 7 (1962)
- *Dactylorhiza islandica* (Á. Löve & D. Löve) Aver., Bot. Zhurn. 69: 875 (1984)
- *Orchis ericetorum* E.F. Linton, Fl. Bournemouth: 208 (1900)
- *Dactylorhiza maculata* subsp. *ericetorum* (E.F. Linton) P.F. Hunt & Summerh., Watsonia 6: 132 (1965)
- *Orchis mascula* auct. non L. (1755)
- *Orchis "maculatus"* sensu Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Gymnadenia nigra* (L.) Rchb.f.³³

Bonplandia (Hannover) 4: 321

Mókolla

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Satyrium nigrum*
- by Baring-Gould (1863) as *Nigritella angustifolia*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Orchis mascula* (L.) L.³⁴

Fl. Suec., ed. 2: 310 (1755)

Gaukmunagras

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Hooker (1811)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

31 At least two different names that can be considered as synonyms of *D. incarnata* are mentioned in old lists: *Orchis cruenta* and *Orchis latifolia*.

O. latifolia was included in Icelandic flora also by Stefánsson (1901, 1948) and Grøntved (1942) and described as "exceedingly rare" by the latter. Grøntved (1942) cites two specimens collected by Babington ("Prope Geysers") and Stefán Stefánsson (Kaldalón, NW). Stefánsson (1948) cites numerous locations, but it seems that all the material available from these sites has been redetermined to *D. maculata* as well as collection from Kaldalón made by Stefánsson in 1893 and mentioned by Grøntved (1942). Currently, there is no evidence available to accept this species from Iceland.

32 As *Orchis "maculatus"* L. in Stefánsson (1901)

33 *G. nigra* was mentioned by early authors as present in Iceland. However, there are no specimens available to confirm these records.

34 *O. mascula* was recorded by some early authors but there are no specimens available. These records are most probably misidentified *D. maculata*.

Neottia cordata (L.) Rich.³⁵

De Orchid. Eur.: 37 (1817)

Hjartatvíblaðka

- *Ophrys cordata* L., Sp. Pl.: 946 (1753)
- *Listera cordata* (L.) R. Br., Hortus Kew. 5: 201 (1813)

Neottia ovata (L.) Bluff & Fingerh.

Comp. Fl. German., ed. 2, 2: 435 (1838)

Eggtvíblaðka

- *Ophrys ovata* L., Sp. Pl.: 946 (1753)
- *Epipactis ovata* (L.) Crantz, Stirp. Austr. Fasc., ed. 2, 2: 473 (1769)
- *Listera ovata* (L.) R. Br., Hort. Kew., ed. 2, 5: 201 (1813)

 ▼ ***Neottia nidus-avis*** (L.) Rich.³⁶

De Orchid. Eur.: 37 (1817)

Hreiðurrót

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Ophrys camtschatea*
- by Gliemann (1824) as *Ophrys nidus-avis*
- by Baring-Gould (1863) as *Listera nidus-avis*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Platanthera hyperborea (L.) Lindl.

Gen. Sp. Orchid. Pl.: 287 (1835)

Friggjargras

- *Orchis hyperborea* L., Mant. Pl.: 121 (1767)
- *Habenaria hyperborea* (L.) R. Br. in W.T. Aiton, Hort. Kew., ed. 2, 5: 193 (1813)
- *Limnorchis hyperborea* (L.) Rydb., Cat. Fl. Montana: 104 (1900)
- *Platanthera koenigii* (Gunnerus) Lindl., Gen. Sp. Orchid. Pl.: 286 (1835)

Pseudorchis straminea (Fernald) Soó³⁷

Monogr. Icon. Orch. Europ. 2, Nachtr.: XII (1972)

Hjónagras

- *Pseudorchis albida* subsp. *straminea* (Fernald) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Taxon 18: 312 (1969)
- *Leucorchis albida* subsp. *straminea* (Fernald) Á. Löve, Bot. Not. 103: 36 (1950)

IRIDACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 57 (1789), nom. cons.

Sverðliljuætt

 ○ ◇ *Iris pseudacorus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 38 (1753)

Tjarnaíris (Tjarnasverðlilja)

35 The genus *Listera* as traditionally circumscribed is undoubtedly paraphyletic and has been merged with *Neottia* (Szlachetko 1995, Bateman 2009)

36 *N. nidus-avis* has been mentioned many times by early authors under different names. It seems that all these records could be considered as misidentifications of *C. trifida*.

37 Kristinsson (2008) accepted this taxon as *P. albida* subsp. *straminea*. It does, however, seem that *P. albida* and *P. straminea* should be treated as separate species: they have different ecology and as far as it is known they cannot hybridise (Elven et al. 2011).

AMARYLLIDACEAE J.St.-Hil.

Expos. Fam. Nat. 1: 134. (1805), nom. cons.

Hjarðiljuætt

◆ *Allium oleraceum* L.³⁸

Sp. Pl.: 299 (1753)

Villilaukur

○ ◇ *Allium schoenoprasum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 301 (1753)

Graslaukur

○ ◇ *Narcissus pseudonarcissus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 289 (1753)

Páskalilja

ASPARAGACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 40 (1789), nom. cons.

Spergilsætt

▼ *Anthericum ramosum* L.³⁹

Sp. Pl.: 310 (1753)

Sandlilja

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Hjaltalín (1830)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Maianthemum bifolium* (L.) F.W. Schmidt⁴⁰

Fl. Boëm. 4: 55 (1794)

Skógartvíbleðla

- by Olafsen and Povelsen (1772)
- by Mohr (1786) as *Convallaria bifolia* L.
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

TYPHACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 25 (1789), nom. cons.

Lókeflisætt

Sparganium angustifolium Michx.

Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2: 189 (1803)

Trjónubrúsi

- *Sparganium affine* Schnizl., Nat. Pfl.-Fam. Typhac.: 27 (1845)

38 An archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

39 *A. ramosum* has been recorded by some of the early authors. There are no collections to confirm these records.

40 *M. bifolium* has been recorded by some of the early authors, but there are no specimens to confirm these records. It is unlikely that this species has been found in Iceland.

Sparganium hyperboreum Laest. ex Beurl.

Öfvers. Förh. Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.-Akad. 9: 192 (1853)

Mógrafabrúsi

- *Sparganium submuticum* (Hartm.) Neuman, Handb. Skand. Fl., ed. 12: 108 (1889)

Sparganium natans L.

Sp. Pl.: 971 (1753)

Tjarnabrúsi

- *Sparganium minimum* Wallr., Erst. Beitr. Fl. Hercyn. 2: 297 (1840)
- *Sparganium minimum* (L.) Fr., Summa Veg. Scand. 2: 560 (1849), nom. illeg.

JUNCACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 43 (1789), nom. cons.

Sefætt

Juncus alpinoarticulatus Chaix

Pl. Vapinc.: 74 (1785)

- *Juncus alpinus* Vill., Hist. Pl. Dauphiné 2: 233 (1787)
- *Juncus nodulosus* auct. non Wahlenb. (1820)
- *Juncus alpinus* subsp. *nodulosus* auct. non Lindm. (1918)
- ***Juncus alpinoarticulatus*** subsp. ***alpestris*** (Hartm.) Hämet-Ahti
Mýrasef
Ann. Bot. Fenn. 17: 342 (1980)
- *Juncus alpestris* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl.: 141 (1820)
- *Juncus alpinus* subsp. *alpestris* (Hartm.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Rep. Dept. Agric. Univ. Inst. Appl. Sci. (Reykjavik), ser. B, 3: 23 (1948)

Juncus arcticus Willd.

Sp. Pl. 2, 1: 206 (1799)

Juncus arcticus Willd. subsp. ***arcticus***

Tryppanál

Juncus arcticus subsp. ***intermedius*** Hyl.⁴¹

Bot. Not. 106: 353 (1953)

Hrossanál

Juncus articulatus L.

Sp. Pl.: 327 (1753)

- ? *Juncus lamprocarpus* Ehrh. ex Hoffm.

Juncus articulatus L. subsp. ***articulatus***

Laugasef

Juncus balticus

Ges. Naturf. Freunde Berlin Mag. Neuesten Entdeck. Gesammten Naturk. 3: 298 (1809)

Juncus balticus Willd. subsp. ***balticus***

Krakanál

Juncus biglumis L.

Sp. Pl.: 328 (1753)

Flagasef

41 *J. arcticus* subsp. *intermedius* (a plant combining features of *J. arcticus* and *J. balticus*) is the most common taxon of the group in Iceland. It seems that extensive occurrence of such intermediates outside Iceland is not common (Elven et al. 2011). Icelandic plants are fertile and it is difficult to say whether they are a product of a local divergence (from *J. arcticus*) or they evolved due to a breakdown of the reproductive barriers between *J. arcticus* and *J. balticus*, subsequent hybridisation, introgression and homogenisation towards an intermediate morphotype (Elven et al. 2011).

◆ *Juncus bufonius* L.⁴²

Sp. Pl.: 328 (1753)

Lækjasef

***Juncus bulbosus* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 327 (1753)

Hnúðsef

– *Juncus supinus* Moench, Enum. Pl. Hass. 1. (1777)***Juncus castaneus* Sm.**

Fl. Brit. 1: 383 (1800)

Dökkasef

▼ *Juncus effusus* L.⁴³

Sp. Pl.: 326 (1753)

Ljósasef

– by König and Müller (1770)

– by Lauder Lindsay (1861) and Babington (1871) as *Juncus communis*

– rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Juncus filiformis* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 326 (1753)

Þráðsef

■ ***Juncus gerardii* Loisel.**⁴⁴

J. Bot. (Desvaux) 2: 284 (1809)

Fitjasef

– ? *Juncus bulbosus* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)– ? *Juncus compressus* auct. non Jacq. (1762)▼ *Juncus jacquinii* L.⁴⁵

Mant. Pl. 1: 63 (1767)

– by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)

– rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Juncus leucochlamys* V.J. Zinger ex V.I. Krecz.**

Fl. Transbaical. 2: 141 (1931)

Vestrased

– *Juncus castaneus* subsp. *leucochlamys* (V.J. Zinger ex V.I. Krecz.) Hultén, Ark. Bot., n.s., 7, 1: 31 (1968)– *Juncus leucochlamys* var. *borealis* Tolm., Fl. Arct. URSS 4: 21 (1963)– *Juncus leucochlamys* subsp. *borealis* (Tolm.) Novikov, Sosud. Rast. Sovet. Dalnego Vostoka 1: 74 (1985)

42 *J. bufonius* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

43 *J. effusus* has been mentioned from Iceland by some early authors. No specimens are available to confirm these records.

44 A doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

45 *J. jacquinii* has been recorded only once and most probably by mistake. There are no specimens available to confirm this finding.

Juncus ranarius Songeon & E.P. Perrier

Annot. Fl. France Allemagne: 192 (1859)

Lindasef

- *Juncus bufonius* subsp. *ranarius* (Songeon & E.P. Perrier) Hiitonen, Suom. Kasvio: 122 (1933)
- *Juncus ambiguus* auct. non Guss. (1827)

Juncus squarrosus L.

Sp. Pl.: 327 (1753)

Stinnasef

Juncus trifidus L.

Sp. Pl.: 326 (1753)

Móasef

Juncus triglumis L.

Sp. Pl.: 328 (1753)

Blómsef

Luzula arcuata (Wahlenb.) Swartz

Summa Veg. Scand.: 13 (1814)

Boghæra

- *Juncus arcuatus* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 87 (1812) nom. et typ. cons.

Luzula confusa Lindeb.

Bot. Not. 1855: 9 (1856)

Fjallhæra

- ? *Luzula arcuata* var. *confusa* (Lindeb.)⁴⁶

▼ ***Luzula pilosa*** (L.) Willd.⁴⁷

Enum. Pl.: 393 (1809)

Skógarhæra

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Juncus pilosus*
- by Thienemann and Guenter (1827)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Luzula multiflora (Ehrh.) Lej.

Fl. Spa 1: 169 (1811)

- *Luzula campestris* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Juncus campestris* auct. non L. (1753)
- ▶ *Luzula multiflora* (Ehrh.) Lej. subsp. *multiflora*⁴⁸

Luzula multiflora subsp. ***frigida*** (Buchenau) V.I. Krecz.

Zhurn. Russk. Bot. Obshch. Akad. Nauk SSSR 12: 490 (1927)

Vallhæra

Luzula spicata (L.) DC.

Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 3: 161

Axhæra

- *Juncus spicatus* L., Sp. Pl.: 330 (1755)

46 Accepted by Stefánsson (1901)

47 *L. pilosa* was recorded by early authors with locality: Eyjafjörður. No specimens are available to confirm these records, and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland later.

48 *L. multiflora* subsp. *multiflora* is a non-native taxon of unknown age – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

Luzula sudetica (Willd.) DC.

Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 4: 306 (1805)

Dökkhæra

- *Juncus sudeticus* Willd., Sp. Pl. 2, 1: 221 (1799)
- *Luzula nigricans* Desv., J. Bot. (Desvaux) 1: 158 (1809)
- *Luzula multiflora* var. *nigricans* (Gaudin) W.D.J. Koch, Syn. Fl. Germ. Helv.: 734 (1837)

▼ *Luzula sylvatica* (Huds.) Gaudin.⁴⁹

Agrost. Helv. 2: 240 (1811)

Lundahæra

- by Bennett (1886)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

CYPERACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 26 (1789), nom. cons.

Stararætt

▼ *Blysmus compressus* (L.) Panz. ex Link⁵⁰

Hort. Berol. 1: 278 (1827)

Flóasef

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Carex uliginosa*
- by Gliemann (1824) *Scirpus caricis*
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Blysmus rufus* (Huds.) Link

Hort. Berol. 1: 278 (1827)

- by Vahl (1840) as *Schoenus rufus*
- by Baring-Gould (1863) and Babington (1871) as *Blysmus rufus*
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Bolboschoenus maritimus* (L.) Palla⁵¹

Syn. Deut. Schweiz. Fl., ed. 3: 2532 (1905)

Flæðastrandnál

- by Babington (1850) *Scirpus maritimus*
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex adelostoma V.I. Krecz.

Fl. USSR 3: 275, 603 (1935)

Hrísastör

- *Carex buxbaumii* var. *mutica* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl.: 41 (1820)
- *Carex buxbaumii* subsp. *mutica* (Hartm.) Isov., Ann. Bot. Fenn. 14: 208 (1977)
- *Carex buxbaumii* var. *alpina* Hartm., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Handl. 1818: 160 (1818)
- *Carex buxbaumii* subsp. *alpina* (Hartm.) Liro, Ann. Acad. Sci. Fenn., Ser. A, 42: 523(1938)

49 *L. sylvatica* was recorded by Bennett (1886) from "Havebrugscand" a non-existing locality. No specimens are available to confirm this record.

50 *B. compressus* was recorded by König and Müller (1770), Gliemann (1824), Baring-Gould (1863) and Babington (1871). There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

51 *B. maritimus* was recorded by Babington (1871). There are no specimens available to confirm this dubious record.

▼ *Carex aquatilis* Wahlenb.⁵²

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl.: 165 (1803)

Vætustör

- by Jónsson (1896)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Carex arenaria* L.⁵³

Sp. Pl.: 973 (1753)

Sandstör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Carex atrata L.

Sp. Pl.: 976 (1753)

Sótstör

▼ *Carex atrofusca* Schkuhr⁵⁴

Beschr. Riedgräs. 1: 106 (1801)

Ryðstör

- by Hornemann (1821)
- by Drejer (1841) as *Carex ustulata* Wahlenb.
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Carex bicolor All.

Fl. Pedem. 2: 267 (1785)

Hvítstör

Carex bigelowii Torr.

Ann. Lyceum Nat. Hist. New York 1: 67 (1824)

- *Carex anguillata* Drejer., Fl. Dan.: t. 2846 (1871)
- *Carex hyperborea* Drejer, Naturhist. Tidsskr. 3: 465 (1841)

Carex bigelowii subsp. ***rigida*** (Gooden.) W. Schultze-Motel, Willdenowia 4: 326 (1968)

Stinnastör

- *Carex rigida* Gooden., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 2: 193, t. 22 (1794), non Schrank (1789)
- *Carex bigelowii* subsp. *nardeticola* Holub, Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 3: 190 (1968)
- *Carex bigelowii* subsp. *dacica* (Heuff.) T.V. Egorova, Fl. Evropeiskoi Chasti SSSR 2: 202 (1976)

Carex brunnescens (Pers.) Poir.

Encycl. Suppl. 3: 286 (1813)

- *Carex curta* var. *brunnescens* Pers., Syn. Pl. 2, 2: 539 (1807)

Carex brunnescens (Pers.) Poir. subsp. ***brunnescens***

Línstör

52 *C. aquatilis* was recorded by Jónsson (1896). There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

53 *C. arenaria* was recorded by several early authors (most probably as a result of copying the initial records of König and Müller (1770). There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

54 *C. atrofusca* was recorded by two different authors in the 19th century. There are no specimens available to confirm these findings and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland later.

Carex buxbaumii Wahlenb.⁵⁵

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 163 (1803)

Klumbustör

- *Carex adelostoma* auct.

Carex canescens L.

Sp. Pl.: 974 (1753)

Blátoppastör

- *Carex cinerea* Pollich, Hist. Pl. Palat. 2: 571 (1777)
- *Carex curta* Gooden., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 2: 145 (1794)
- ? *Carex loliacea* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)

Carex capillaris L.⁵⁶

Sp. Pl.: 977 (1753)

Hárleggjastör

Carex capillaris L. subsp. **capillaris****Carex capillaris** subsp. **fuscidula** (V.I. Krecz. ex T.V. Egorova) Á. Löve & D. Löve

- *Carex fuscidula* V.I. Krecz. ex T.V. Egorova, Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 1: 36 (1964)

Carex capitata L.

Syst. Nat., ed. 10, 2: 1261 (1759)

Hnappstör

Carex caryophyllea Latourr.

Chlor. Lugd.: 27 (1785)

Vorstör

Carex chordorrhiza L. f.

Suppl. Pl.: 414 (1781)

Vetrarkvíðastör

- ? *Carex uliginosa* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)

Carex demissa Hornem.

Fors. Oecon. Plantel., ed. 3, 1: 939 (1821)

Grænstör

- *Carex tumidicarpa* Andersson, Bot. Not. 1849: 16 (1849)
- *Carex oederi* subsp. *oedocarpa* Andersson, Pl. Scand 1: 25 (1849)
- *Carex viridula* subsp. *oedocarpa* (Andersson) B. Schmid, Watsonia 14: 316 (1983)

▼ **Carex depauperata** Gooden.⁵⁷

Trans. Linn. Soc. London 2: 181 (1794)

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

55 The presence of *C. buxbaumii* in Iceland has been much debated. Kristinsson (2008) as well as Elven (2011) stated that reports of *C. buxbaumii* from Iceland are referable to *C. adelostoma*, but a recent finding by Rannveig Thoroddsen (determination by H. Wieclaw and J. Koopman) revealed that the species is present in Iceland, although currently known just from one locality.

56 *C. capillaris* subsp. *fuscidula* is common in Iceland, while subsp. *capillaris* is rather rare.

57 *C. depauperata* was recorded by two different authors in the 19th century. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

Carex diandra Schrank

Cent. Bot. Anmerk.: 57 (1781)

Safastör

- *Carex teretiuscula* Gooden., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 2: 163 (1794)
- *Carex paniculata* auct. non Schrank (1781)

Carex dioica L.

Sp. Pl.: 972 (1753)

Sérbýlisstör

- *Carex dioeca* orth. var.

Carex echinata Murray

Prodr. Stirp. Gott.: 76 (1770)

Ígulstör

- *Carex stellulata* Gooden., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 2: 144 (1794)

▼ ***Carex elongata*** L.⁵⁸

Sp. Pl.: 974 (1753)

Langstör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex flacca Schreber

Spic. Fl. Lips., App.: 178 (1771)

Grástör

- *Carex glauca* Scop., Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 2: 223 (1772)

Carex flava L.

Sp. Pl.: 975 (1753)

Trjónustör

▼ ***Carex fuliginosa*** Schkuhr⁵⁹

Beschr. Riedgräs. 1: 91 (1801)

Dökkvastör

- by Hornemann (1821)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex glacialis Mack.

Bull. Torrey Bot. Club 37: 244 (1910)

Dvergstör

- *Carex pedata* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 239 (1812), nom. illeg.

Carex glareosa Wahlenb.

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 146 (1803)

Heigulstör

- *Carex marina* auct. non Dewey (1836)

58 *C. elongata* was recorded from Iceland by two early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

59 *C. fuliginosa* was recorded from Iceland by several authors in 19th century. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

▼ *Carex globularis* L.⁶⁰

Sp. Pl.: 976 (1753)

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex heleonastes Ehrh. ex L. f.

Suppl. Pl.: 414 (1782)

Heiðastör

- ? *Carex pairaei* sensu Grøntved (1942) non F.W. Schultz (1868)

▼ *Carex hirta* L.⁶¹

Sp. Pl.: 975 (1753)

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Carex holostoma* Drejer⁶²

Naturhist. Tidsskr. 3: 447 (1841)

Deiglustör

- by Löve (1970)

Carex krausei Boeck.

Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 7: 279 (1886)

Toppastör

- *Carex capillaris* subsp. *krausei* (Boeck.) Böcher, Meddel. Grønland 147(9): 52 (1952)
- *Carex capillaris* var. *porsildiana* Polunin, J. Linn. Soc., Bot. 52: 373 (1943)
- *Carex krausei* subsp. *porsildiana* (Polunin) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20, 4:175 (1956)

Carex lachenalii Schkuhr

Beschr. Riedgräs.: 51 (1801), nom. cons.

Rjúpastör

- *Carex lagopina* Wahlenb., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 145 (1803)
- *Carex tripartita* All., Fl. Pedem. 2: 265 (1785)
- *Carex leporina* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Carex elongata* auct. non L. (1753)

▼ *Carex laevirostris* (Blytt ex Fr.) Andersson⁶³

Pl. Scand. 1: 17 (1849)

- by Rostrup (1887)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

60 *C. globularis* was recorded by two early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

61 *C. hirta* was recorded by several early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

62 Löve (1970) included *C. holostoma* in his flora, citing observations (!) from Vaðlaheiði made in 1883 and 1947. There are, however, no collections to confirm these records and the species has never been found again in this locality.

63 There is just one record of *C. laevirostris* in the literature. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

Carex limosa L.

Sp. Pl.: 977 (1753)

Flóastör

Carex livida (Wahlenb.) Willd.

Sp. Pl. 4, 1: 285 (1805)

Fölvastör

- *Carex limosa* var. *livida* Wahlenb., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 162 (1803)

Carex lyngbyei Hornem.

Fl. Dan. 11, 32: 6 (1827)

Gulstör

- *Carex cryptocarpa* C.A. Mey., Mém. Sav. Étr. Acad. St. Pétersbourg 1: 226 (1831)
- *Carex capillipes* Drejer, Naturhist. Tidsskr. 3: 472 (1841)
- *Carex filipendula* Drejer, Naturhist. Tidsskr. 3: 468 (1841)

Carex mackenziei V.I. Krecz.

Fl. URSS 3: 183 (1935)

Skriðstör

- *Carex norvegica* Willd. ex Schkuhr, Besch. Riedgräs. 1: 50 (1801), nom. illeg.

Carex macloviana d'Urv.

Mém. Soc. Linn. Paris 4: 599 (1826)

Kollstör

- *Carex festiva* Dewey, Amer. J. Sci. Arts 29: 246 (1835)

Carex maritima Gunnerus

Fl. Norveg. 2: 131 (1776)

Bjúgstör

- *Carex incurva* Lightf., Fl. Scot. 2: 544 (1777)
- *Carex incurva* f. *argyrolepis* Ostf.
- *Carex arenaria* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)

Carex microglochin Wahlenb.

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 140 (1803)

Broddastör

Carex nardina Fr.

Novit. Fl. Svec. Mant. 2: 55 (1839)

Finnungsstör

Carex nigra (L.) Reichard⁶⁴

Fl. Moeno-Francof. 2: 96 (1778)

Mýrastör

- *Carex acuta* var. *nigra* L., Sp. Pl.: 978 (1753)
- *Carex fusca* All., Fl. Pedem. 2: 269 (1785)
- *Carex goodenowii* J. Gay, Ann. Sci. Nat., Bot., sér. 2, 11: 191 (1839)⁶⁵
- *Carex vulgaris* Fr., Novit. Fl. Suec. Mant. 3: 153 (1843), nom. superfl.
- ? *Carex caespitosa* auct. non L. (1753)
- ? *Carex turfosa* auct. non Fr. (1843)

Carex nigra (L.) Reichard var. **nigra****Carex nigra** var. **juncea** (Fr.) Hyl.

Nordisk Kärlväxtfl. 2: 115 (1966)

- *Carex vulgaris* var. *juncea* Fr., Novit. Fl. Svec. Mant. 3: 154 (1845)
- *Carex nigra* subsp. *juncea* (Fr.) Soó, Feddes Repert. 83: 148 (1972)
- *Carex vulgaris* subsp. *juncella* Fr., Bot. Not. 1843: 105 (1843)
- *Carex juncella* (Fr.) Th. Fr., Bot. Not. 1857: 207 (1857)
- *Carex nigra* subsp. *juncella* (Fr.) Lemke, Feddes Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 67: 4 (1963)

▼ **Carex montana** L.⁶⁶

Sp. Pl.: 975 (1753)

Smalastör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Drejer (1841)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ **Carex muricata** L.⁶⁷

Sp. Pl.: 974 (1753)

Gaddastör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Drejer (1841)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Carex myosuroides Vill.

Hist. Pl. Dauphiné: 17 (1779)

pursaskegg

- *Carex bellardii* All., Fl. Pedem. 2: 264 (1785)
- *Kobresia scirpina* Willd., Sp. Pl. 4: 205 (1805)
- *Kobresia bellardii* (All.) Degl. ex Loisel., Fl. Gall. 2: 626 (1807)
- *Elyna bellardii* (All.) K. Koch, Linnaea 21: 616 (1848)
- *Kobresia myosuroides* (Vill.) Fiori, Fl. Italia 1: 125 (1896)

64 Kristinsson (2008) accepted two races from Iceland differing in growth form: var. *nigra* – forming open mats and var. *juncea* – forming dense tussocks. Elven et al. (2011) also accepted these two taxa as ecological or geo-ecological races.

65 *Carex "goodenoughii"* in Stefánsson (1901)

66 *C. montana* was recorded only by two early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

67 *C. muricata* was recorded only by two early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

Carex norvegica Retz.

Fl. Scand. Prodr.: 179 (1779), nom. cons.

Fjallastör

- *Carex halleri* Gunnerus, Fl. Norveg. 2: 106 (1776), nom. rej.
- *Carex vahlii* Schkuhr, Beschr. Riedgräs. 1: 87 (1801)
- *Carex alpina* Sw. ex Wahlenb., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl.: 160 (1803), nom. illeg.

▼ *Carex ornithopoda* Willd.⁶⁸

Sp. Pl. 4: 255 (1805)

Fuglastör

- by Hornemann (1821)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Carex paleacea* Schreb. ex Wahlenb.⁶⁹

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 164

- by Knuth (1837) as *Carex maritima* O.F. Müll.
- by Drejer (1841)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex pallescens L.

Sp. Pl.: 977 (1753)

Gljástör

Carex panicea L.

Sp. Pl.: 977 (1753)

Belgjastör

▼ *Carex pauciflora* Lightf.⁷⁰

Fl. Scot. 2: 543 (1777)

- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex paupercula Michx.

Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2: 172 (1803)

Keldustör

- *Carex limosa* var. *irrigua* Wahlenb., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 162 (1803)
- *Carex irrigua* (Wahlenb.) Sm. ex Hoppe, Caricolog. Germ.: 72 (1826)
- *Carex magellanica* subsp. *irrigua* (Wahlenb.) Hiitonen, Suom. Kasvio: 161 (1933)
- *Carex magellanica* auct. non Lam. (1792)

Carex pilulifera L.

Sp. Pl.: 976 (1753)

Dúnhulstrastör

68 *C. ornithopoda* was recorded from Iceland in 19th century. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

69 *C. paleacea* was recorded from Iceland in 19th century. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

70 *C. pauciflora* was recorded from Iceland in 19th century. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

▼ *Carex pseudocyperus* L.⁷¹

Sp. Pl.: 978 (1753)

Sefstör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Hornemann (1821)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Carex pulicaris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 972 (1753)

Hagastör

***Carex ramenskii* Kom.⁷²**

Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 13: 164 (1914)

Marstör

- *Carex subspathacea* subsp. *ramenskii* (Kom.) T.V. Egorova, Bot. Zhurn. 75: 864 (1990)
- *Carex salina* sensu Stefánsson (1901) non Wahlenb. (1803)
- *Carex salina* var. *borealis* sensu Stefánsson (1901) non Almq. (1879)
- *Carex salina* var. *kattegatensis* sensu Stefánsson (1901) non Almq. (1879)

***Carex rariflora* (Wahlenb.) Sm.**

Engl. Bot. 35: t. 2516 (1813)

Hengistör

- *Carex limosa* var. *rariflora* Wahlenb., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 162 (1803)
- *Carex rariflora* var. *androgyna* A.E. Porsild, Sargentia 4: 20 (1943)

***Carex rostrata* Stokes**

Bot. Arr. Brit. Pl., ed. 2, 2: 1059 (1787), nom. cons.

Tjarnastör

- *Carex inflata* Huds., Fl. Angl.: 354 (1762), nom. rej.
- *Carex ampullacea* Gooden., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 2: 207 (1794), nom. superfl.
- *Carex hymenocarpa* Drejer, Fl. Dan.: t. 2849 (1871)
- *Carex vesicaria* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)

***Carex rufina* Drejer**

Naturhist. Tidsskr. 3: 446 (1841)

Rauðstör

***Carex rupestris* All.**

Fl. Pedem. 2: 264 (1785)

Móastör

***Carex saxatilis* L.**

p. Pl.: 976 (1753)

Hrafnastör

- *Carex pulla* Gooden., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 3: 78 (1797)

71 *C. pseudocyperus* was recorded by some of the early botanists. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

72 Standley et al. (2002) suggest that *C. ramenskii* might be a stabilized hybrid species from *C. lyngbyei* × *C. subspathacea*. See also discussion in Elven et al. (2011)

▼ *Carex stenophylla* Wahlenb.⁷³

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 24: 142 (1803)

- by Thienemann and Guenter (1827)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex subspathacea Wormsk.

Fl. Dan. 9, 26: 6, t. 1530 (1816)

Flæðastör

- *Carex salina* var. *subspathacea* (Wormsk. ex Hornem.) Tuck., Enum. Meth. Caric.: 12 (1843)

Carex vaginata Tausch

Flora 4: 557 (1821)

Carex vaginata Tausch subsp. ***vaginata***

Slíðrastör

- *Carex quasivaginata* C.B. Clarke, Bull. Misc. Inform. Add., ser. 8: 79 (1908)
- *Carex vaginata* subsp. *quasivaginata* (C.B. Clarke) Malyshev, Fl. Vost. Sayana: 90 (1965)
- *Carex panicea* var. *sparsiflora* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 236 (1812)
- *Carex sparsiflora* (Wahlenb.) Steud., Nomencl. Bot., ed. 2, 1: 296 (1840)

▼ *Carex vesicaria* L.⁷⁴

Sp. Pl.: 979 (1753)

Bólustör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Carex viridula Michx.

Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2: 170 (1803)

- *Carex oederi* subsp. *viridula* (Michx.) Hultén, Ark. Bot., n.s., 7, 1: 30 (1968)
- *Carex pulchella* (Lönnr.) Lindm., Sv. Fanerogamfl.: 143 (1918), nom. illeg.
- *Carex scandinavica* E.W. Davies, Watsonia 3: 66 (1953)
- *Carex flava* auct. non L. (1753)

Carex viridula Michx. var. ***viridula***

Gullstör

- *Carex serotina* Mérat, Nouv. Fl. Env. Paris, ed. 2, 2: 54 (1821)
- *Carex oederi* Ehrh., Beitr. Naturk. 6: 83 (1791), nom. illeg.

▼ *Carex vulpina* L.⁷⁵

Sp. Pl.: 973 (1753)

Refastör

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Drejer (1841)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

73 *C. stenophylla* was recorded by several authors in 19th century. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

74 *C. vesicaria* was recorded by several early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

75 *C. vulpina* was recorded by several early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

Eleocharis acicularis (L.) Roem. & Schult.

Syst. Veg. 2: 154 (1817)

Efjuskúfur

- *Scirpus acicularis* L., Sp. Pl.: 48 (1753)
- *Heleocharis acicularis* orth. var.

▼ ***Eleocharis multicaulis*** (Sm.) Desv.⁷⁶

Observ. Pl. Angers: 74 (1818)

Dýjaskúfur

- by Gliemann (1824) as *Valeriana multicaulis*⁷⁷
- by Babington (1871) as *Scirpus multicaulis*
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Eleocharis palustris (L.) Roem. & Schult.

Syst. Veg. 2: 151 (1817)

- *Scirpus palustris* L., Sp. Pl.: 47 (1753)- *Heleocharis palustris* orth. var.***Eleocharis palustris*** (L.) Roem. & Schult. subsp. ***palustris***

Vatnsnál

Eleocharis quinqueflora (Hartmann) O. Schwarz

Mitt. Thüring. Bot. Ges. 1: 89 (1949)

Fitjaskúfur

- *Scirpus quinqueflorus* Hartmann, Primae Lin. Inst. Bot., ed. 2: 85 (1767)
- *Scirpus pauciflorus* Lightf., Fl. Scot. 2: 1078 (1777)
- *Eleocharis pauciflora* (Lightf.) Link, Hort. Berol. 1: 284 (1827)

Eleocharis uniglumis (Link) Schult.

Mant. 2: 88 (1824)

Vætuskúfur

- *Scirpus uniglumis* Link in Spreng., Schrad. & Link, Jahrb. Gewächsk. 1, 3: 77 (1820)
- *Heleocharis uniglumis* orth. var.

Eriophorum angustifolium Honck.

Verz. Gew. Teutschl.: 153 (1782)

Klóífa

- *Eriophorum polystachion* L., Sp. Pl.: 52 (1753), nom. rej.
- *Eriophorum subarcticum* V.N. Vassil., Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk SSSR 13: 58 (1950)
- *Eriophorum angustifolium* subsp. *subarcticum* (V.N. Vassil.) Hultén ex Kartesz & S.K. Gandhi, Phytologia 72: 22 (1992)

76 *E. multicaulis* was recorded by two 19th century botanists. No specimens are available to confirm these dubious records.

77 Typographical error in Gliemann (1824)

▼ *Eriophorum russeolum* Fr. ex Hartm.⁷⁸

Handb. Skand. Fl., ed. 3: 13 (1838)

Rauðfífa

- by Löve (1970)

Eriophorum scheuchzeri Hoppe

Bot. Taschenb. Anfänger Wiss. Apothekerkunst 11: 104 (1801)

Hrafnafífa

 - *Eriophorum capitatum* Host, Icon. Descr. Gram. Austriac. 1: 30 (1801)

 ▼ *Eriophorum triste* (Th. Fr.) Hadac & Á. Löve⁷⁹

Bot. Not. 103: 34 (1950)

Kuldafífa

- by Löve (1970)

 ▼ *Isolepis setacea* (L.) R. Br.⁸⁰

Prodr. Fl. Nov. Holl.: 222 (1810)

Burstasef

 - by König and Müller (1770) as *Scirpus setaceus*

 - by Baring-Gould (1863) as *Isolepis setacea*

 - by Babington (1871) and Grøntved (1942) as *Scirpus setaceus*

 ▼ *Schoenoplectus lacustris* (L.) Palla⁸¹

Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 10: 299 (1888)

Vatnasefnál

 - by König and Müller (1770) as *Scirpus lacustris*

- by Baring-Gould (1863)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

 ▼ *Trichophorum alpinum* (L.) Pers.⁸²

Syn. Pl. 1: 70 (1805)

Lófinnungur

 - by König and Müller (1770) as *Eriophorum alpinum* L.

- by Babington (1871)

- by Grønlund (1881)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

78 Records of *E. russeolum* from Iceland belong to the series of doubtful and discounted records made by Löve that are, most probably, fictitious (Elven et al. 2011).

79 Records of *E. triste* from Iceland belong to the very doubtful series of records by Áskell Löve that may be fictitious (Elven et al. 2011).

80 This species is mentioned by several early authors as well as by Grøntved (1942), who treated old records as confirmed based on collections made in 1932 by Schwabe. The present location of this collection is unknown and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland by other authors.

81 Recorded by König and Müller (1770), Baring-Gould (1863) and Babington (1871). There are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

82 *T. alpinum* was recorded by several authors but there are no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

***Trichophorum cespitosum* (L.) Schur**

Verh. Mitth. Siebenbürg. Vereins Naturwiss. Hermannstadt 4: 78 (1853)

– *Scirpus cespitosus* L., Sp. Pl.: 48 (1753)

– *Baeothryon cespitosum* (L.) A. Dietr., Sp. Pl. 2: 89 (1832)

Trichophorum cespitosum* (L.) Schur subsp. *cespitosum

Mýrafinnungur

– *Trichophorum austriacum* Palla, Ber. Deutsch. Bot. Ges. 15: 468 (1897)

– *Scirpus cespitosus* (Palla) Asch. & Graebn., Syn. Mitteleur. Fl. 2, 2: 300 (1904)

POACEAE Barnhart (= Gramineae Juss. nom. cons.)

Bull. Torrey Bot. Club 22(1): 7 (1895), nom. cons.

Grasætt

▼ *Agrostis alpina* Scop.⁸³

Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 1: 60 (1771)

Hlíðalíngresi

– by Gliemann (1824)

– by Vahl (1840)

– by Babington (1871)

– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Agrostis capillaris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 62 (1753)

Hálíngresi

– *Agrostis tenuis* Sibth., Fl. Oxon.: 36 (1794)

– *Agrostis vulgaris* With., Arr. Brit. Pl. ed. 3, 2: 132 (1796)

○ *Agrostis gigantea* Roth

Tent. Fl. Germ. 1: 31 (1788)

Stórlíngresi

***Agrostis stolonifera* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 62 (1753)

Skriðlíngresi

– *Agrostis alba* auct. non L. (1753)⁸⁴

83 Species mentioned in some old lists, but it is very unlikely that it has ever been present in Iceland. No specimens are available.

84 It seems that some early authors (Grønlund 1881, Stefánsson 1901) applied this name to *Agrostis stolonifera*. Currently, the name *Agrostis alba* is treated as a synonym of *Poa nemoralis*.

Agrostis vinealis Schreb.

Spic. Fl. Lips.: 47 (1771)

Týtulíngresi

- *Agrostis canina* var. *montana* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl., ed. 2: 19 (1832)
- *Agrostis canina* subsp. *montana* (Hartm.) Hartm., Sv. Norsk Exc.-Fl.: 13 (1846)
- *Agrostis hyperborea* Laest. ex Nyman, Consp. Fl. Eur. 4: 802 (1882)
- *Agrostis coarctata* subsp. *hyperborea* (Laest.) H. Scholz, Willdenowia 5: 482 (1969)
- ? *Agrostis vinealis* subsp. *hyperborea* (Laest.) Á. Löve
- *Agrostis rubra* auct. non Wahlenb. ex Nyman (1882)
- ? *Agrostis rubra* auct. non L. (1753)⁸⁵
- *Agrostis canina* auct. non L. (1753)

 ▼ *Aira praecox* L.⁸⁶

Sp. Pl.: 65 (1753)

Vorlíngresi

- from Mohr (1786)
- up to Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Alopecurus aequalis Sobol.

Fl. Petrop.: 16 (1799)

Vatnsliðagras

- *Alopecurus aristulatus* Michx., Fl. Bor.-Amer. 1: 43 (1803)
- *Alopecurus fulvus* Sm., Engl. Bot. 21: t. 1467 (1805)
- *Alopecurus geniculatus* var. *natans* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 22 (1812)
- *Alopecurus aequalis* subsp. *natans* (Wahlenb.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20: 94 (1956)

Alopecurus geniculatus L.⁸⁷

Sp. Pl.: 60 (1753)

Knjáliðagras

 ○ *Alopecurus myosuroides* Huds.

Fl. Angl. 1: 23 (1762)

Akurliðagras

 ● *Alopecurus pratensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 60 (1753)

Háliðagras

85 The species *Agrostis rubra* L. was first recorded by König and Müller (1770) and then copied by some early authors. The name is now treated as a synonym of *Agrostis mertensii* Trin., Linnaea 10: 302 (1836) (syn. *A. borealis* Hartm.), that has never been recorded in Iceland Elven et al. (2011). It is very probable that older records of *A. rubra* are due to misidentified *A. vinealis*.

86 The species recorded by most of the early authors. No specimens are available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

87 Elven et al. (2011) suggest that *A. geniculatus* could be an adventive at least in northern, Arctic part of Iceland.

▼ *Ammophila arenaria* (L.) Link ⁸⁸

Hort. Berol. 1: 105 (1827)

Sandhólapuntur

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Arundo arenaria* L.
- by Thienemann and Guenter (1827)
- by Babington (1871) as *Psamma arenaria* Beauv.
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Anisantha tectorum* (L.) Nevski

Trudy Sredne-Aziatsk. Gosud. Univ., ser. 8b, Bot. 17: 22 (1934)

Þakfax

- *Bromus tectorum* L., Sp. Pl.: 77 (1753)

▶ *Anthoxanthum odoratum* L. ⁸⁹

Sp. Pl.: 28 (1753)

Ununarreyr

Anthoxanthum nipponicum Honda

Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 40: 317 (1926)

Ilmreyr

- *Anthoxanthum odoratum* subsp. *nipponicum* (Honda) Tzvelev, Spisok Rast. Gerb. Fl. SSSR Bot. Inst. Vsesoyuzn. Akad. Nauk 17: 31 (1967)
- *Anthoxanthum alpinum* Á. Löve & D. Löve, Rep. Dept. Agric. Univ. Inst. Appl. Sci. (Reykjavik), ser. B, 3: 105 (1948)
- *Anthoxanthum odoratum* subsp. *alpinum* (Á. Löve & D. Löve) B.M.G. Jones & Melderis, Bot. Soc. Brit. Isles Proc. 5: 376 (1964) nom. illeg.
- *Anthoxanthum odoratum* auct.

○ *Apera spica-venti* (L.) P. Beauv.

Ess. Agrostogr. 31: 151 (1812)

Akurvindgresi

- *Agrostis spica-venti* L., Sp. Pl.: 61 (1753)

■ ***Arrhenatherum elatius*** (L.) P. Beauv. ex J. Presl & C. Presl⁹⁰

Fl. Cech.: 17 (1819)

Ginhafri

- *Avena elatior* L., Sp. Pl.: 79 (1753)

○ *Avena fatua* L.

Sp. Pl.: 80 (1753)

Flughafnar

○ *Avena sativa* L.

Sp. Pl.: 79 (1753)

Hafrar

88 Babington (1871) suggests that the species was found near "Kinnæstadt" (probably Skinnastaðir, NE Iceland). Very doubtful records impossible to confirm due to the lack of herbarium material.

89 There are two different races of *Anthoxanthum* present in Iceland. Differences between the two groups are clear not only in terms of cytology (tetraploid vs. diploid) but also in terms of morphology. It seems therefore that they should be treated as two separate species. *A. odoratum* is treated here as a non-native of unknown age – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

90 *A. elatius* grows only in one place: under bird cliffs close to Pétursey in southern Iceland (Kristinsson 2008). It is therefore probable that it has been brought there with birds. Otherwise it could be classified as an old adventive. Here it is classified as doubtfully native – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

Avenella flexuosa (L.) Drejer⁹¹

Fl. Excurs. Hafn.: 32 (1838)

Bugðupuntur

- *Aira flexuosa* L., Sp. Pl.: 65 (1753)
- *Deschampsia flexuosa* (L.) Trin., Bull. Sci. Acad. Imp. Sci. Saint-Petersbourg 1: 66 (1836)
- *Lerchenfeldia flexuosa* (L.) Schur, Enum. Pl. Transsilv.: 753 (1866)
- *Aira montana* L., Sp. Pl.: 65 (1753)
- *Deschampsia flexuosa* var. *montana* (L.) Griseb. in Ledeb., Fl. Ross. 4: 420 (1852)
- *Avenella flexuosa* subsp. *montana* (L.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20, 4: 128 (1956)
- *Lerchenfeldia flexuosa* subsp. *montana* (L.) Tzvelev, Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 7: 44 (1971)
- *Lerchenfeldia montana* (L.) A.P. Khokhr., Byull. Moskovsk. Obshch. Isp. Prir., Otd. Biol. 97(6): 98 (1993)

● *Avenula pubescens* (Huds.) Dumort.

Bull. Soc. Roy. Bot. Belgique 7: 68 (1868)

Dúnhafri

- *Avena pubescens* Huds., Fl. Angl.: 42 (1762)
- *Helictotrichon pubescens* (Huds.) Pilg., Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 45: 6 (1938)
- *Avenochloa pubescens* (Huds.) Holub, Acta Horti Bot. Prag. 1962: 84 (1962)

▶ *Briza media* L.⁹²

Sp. Pl.: 70 (1753)

Hjartapuntur

● *Bromopsis inermis* (Leyss.) Holub

Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 8: 167 (1973)

Sandfax

- *Bromus inermis* Leyss., Fl. Halens.: 16 (1761)
- *Zerna inermis* (Leyss.) Lindm., Sv. Fanerogamfl.: 101 (1918)

○ *Bromus arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 77 (1753)

Akurfax

▼ *Bromus briziformis* Fisch. & C.A. Mey⁹³

Index Seminum (LE) 3: 30 (1837)

Hjartafax

- by Rostrup (1887)
- by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Bromus hordeaceus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 77 (1753)

Mjúkfax

- *Bromus mollis* L., Sp. Pl. ed.2 : 112 (1762)

91 It seems that there is sufficient evidence to recognise *Avenella* as a separate genus (Chiapella 2007).

92 *B. media* is an extremely rare non-native species in Iceland, growing only within a very small area close to Grafarvogur. It is very difficult to date its arrival to Iceland with some degree of certainty. See Wasowicz (2018) for details.

93 Recorded just once from Blöndudalsbakki and most probably occurred as casual alien. It was impossible to verify the specimen.

▼ *Bromus racemosus* L.⁹⁴

Sp. Pl. (ed. 2): 114 (1762)

Túnfax

- by Bennett (1890)
- by Stefánsson (1901)
- by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Bromus secalinus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 76 (1753), nom. cons.

Rúgfax

○ *Calamagrostis epigejos* (L.) Roth

Tent. Fl. Germ. 1: 34 (1788)

Melahálmgresi

Calamagrostis neglecta (Ehrh.) P. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb.⁹⁵

Oekon. Fl. Wetterau 1: 94 (1799)

- *Arundo stricta* Timm, Mag. Naturk. Oekon. Meklenburgs 2: 235 (1795)
- *Achnatherum calamagrostis* P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr.: 19 (1812)
- ? *Agrostis arundinacea* sensu König and Müller (1770)
- ? *Arundo epigejos* sensu König and Müller (1770)
- ? *Calamagrostis varia* auct. non Host (1809)

Calamagrostis neglecta subsp. ***groenlandica*** (Schrank) Matuszk.

Hálmgresi

Ann. Univ. Lublin, sect. C, 3: 242 (1948)

- *Arundo groenlandica* Schrank, Denkschr. Königl.-Baier. Bot. Ges. Regensburg 1, 2: 8 (1818)
- *Calamagrostis groenlandica* (Schrank) Kunth, Révis. Gramin. 1: 79 (1829)
- *Calamagrostis stricta* subsp. *groenlandica* (Schrank) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 299 (1970)
- ? *Calamagrostis stricta* var. *borealis* (Laest.) Lange, Consp. Fl. Groenland. 3: 161 (1880)

○ *Calamagrostis purpurea* (Trin.) Trin.

Gram. Unifl. Sesquifl.: 219 (1824)

Purpurahálmgresi

- *Arundo purpurea* Trin. in K.P.J. Sprengel, Neue Entd. 2: 52 (1821)
- *Calamagrostis phragmitoides* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl., ed. 4: 25 (1843)

Catabrosa aquatica (L.) P. Beauv.

Ess. Agrostogr.: 19, 97 (1812)

Vatnsnarfagras

- *Aira aquatica* L., Sp. Pl.: 64 (1753)

○ *Cynosurus cristatus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 72 (1753)

Kambgras

● *Dactylis glomerata* L.

Sp. Pl.: 71 (1753)

Axfnoðapuntur

94 Recorded several times by two relatively recent authors but specimens are lacking to verify these records. Most probably casual alien.

95 There is no general agreement on what name should be treated as valid for this species. Provisionally Elven et al. (2011) was followed here.

■ ***Danthonia decumbens*** (L.) DC.⁹⁶

Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 3: 33 (1805)

Knjápuntur

- *Festuca decumbens* L., Sp. Pl.: 75 (1753)
- *Sieglingia decumbens* (L.) Bernh., Syst. Verz. 20: 44 (1800)

Deschampsia alpina (L.) Roem. & Schult.⁹⁷

Syst. Veg. 2: 686 (1817)

Fjallapuntur

- *Aira alpina* L., Sp. Pl.: 65 (1753)
- *Aira cespitosa* var. *alpina* sensu Stefánsson (1901)

▼ ***Deschampsia atropurpurea*** (Wahlenb.) Scheele⁹⁸

Flora 27: 56 (1884)

- by Hornemann (1806) as *Aira alpina*
- by Gliemann (1824) as *Aira atropurpurea* Wahlenb.
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Deschampsia cespitosa (L.) P. Beauv.⁹⁹

Ess. Agrostogr.: 91, 149, 160 (1812)

- *Aira cespitosa* L., Sp. Pl.: 64 (1753)
- *Deschampsia caespitosa* P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr.: 91 (1812), orth. var.
 - ***Deschampsia cespitosa*** (L.) P. Beauv. subsp. ***cespitosa***
 - Snarrótarpuntur
 - *Deschampsia cespitosa* subsp. *beringensis* (Hultén) W.E. Lawr.
 - Beringspuntur
 - *Deschampsia beringensis* Hultén, Fl. Kamtchatka 1: 107 (1927)

○ ***Digitaria ischaemum*** (Schreb.) Muhl.

Descr. Gram.: 131 (1817)

Fingurax

- *Panicum ischaemum* Schreb. in A.F. Schweigger & F. Koerte, Spec. Fl. Erlang. 1: 16 (1804)

Elymus alaskanus (Scribn. & Merr.) Á. Löve

Taxon 19: 299 (1970)

Elymus alaskanus subsp. ***borealis*** (Turcz.) Á. Löve & D. Löve

Bot. Not. 128: 502 (1976)

Bláhveiti

- *Agropyron boreale* (Turcz.) Drobow, Trudy Bot. Muz. Imp. Akad. Nauk 16:84 (1916)
- *Roegneria borealis* (Turcz.) Nevski, Fl. URSS 2: 624 (1934)
- *Elymus kronokensis* subsp. *borealis* (Turcz.) Tzvelev, Nov. Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 10: 24 (1973)
- *Agropyron kronokense* Kom., Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 13: 87 (1914)
- *Roegneria kronokensis* (Kom.) Tzvelev, Fl. Arct. URSS 2: 246 (1964)
- *Elymus kronokensis* (Kom.) Tzvelev in Grubov, Rast. Tsentr. Azii 4: 216 (1968)
- *Roegneria scandica* Nevski, Fl. URSS 2: 624 (1934)

96 *D. decumbens* is a doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

97 There are many characters that clearly differentiate *D. alpina* from *D. cespitosa* [bulbils formation, smooth panicle branches (vs. rough), short, regularly involute blades with nearly smooth ribs (vs. mostly flat and very rough)]. Therefore, it seems that treating *D. alpina* merely as a synonym of *D. cespitosa* would be a mistake.

98 No specimens available. Most probably a mistake (misidentification) made by Hornemann and copied by other authors including Hultén.

99 *D. cespitosa* is a doubtfully native taxon – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

- *Elymus alaskanus* subsp. *scandicus* (Nevski) Melderis, Bot. J. Linn. Soc. 76: 375 (1978)
- *Elymus kronokensis* subsp. *scandicus* (Nevski) Tzvelev, Nov. Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 32: 182 (2000)
- *Triticum violaceum* f. *subalpinum* Neuman, Sver. Fl.: 726 (1901)
- *Elymus kronokensis* subsp. *subalpinus* (Neum.) Tzvelev, Nov. Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 10:24(1973)
- *Elymus alaskanus* subsp. *subalpinus* (Neum.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 502 (1976)
- *Bromus cristatus* sensu König and Müller (1770), non L. (1753)
- *Triticum cristatum* auct. non Schreb. (1770)
- *Triticum biflorum* auct. non Brign. (1810)
- *Agropyron trachycaulum* auct. non Steud. (1854)
- *Agropyron violaceum* auct. non Lange (1880)

Elymus alopex B. Salomon¹⁰⁰

Willdenowia 35: 248–249 (2005)

Kjarrhveiti

- ? *Elymus donianus* var. *stefanssonii* (Meld.) Á. Löve
- *Elymus caninus* auct. non L. (1755)
- *Triticum caninum* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Agropyron caninum* auct. non P. Beauv (1812)

○ *Elymus smithii* (Rydb.) Gould

Madroño 9: 127 (1947)

Herpuntur

- *Agropyron smithii* Rydb., Mem. New York Bot. Gard. 1: 64 (1900)
- *Elytrigia smithii* (Rydb.) Nevski, Trudy Bot. Inst. Akad. Nauk S.S.S.R., Ser. 1, Fl. Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 1: 25 (1933)
- *Pascopyrum smithii* (Rydb.) Á. Löve, Taxon 29: 168 (1980)

◆ *Elytrigia repens* (L.) Desv. ex Nevski¹⁰¹

Trudy Bot. Inst. Akad. Nauk S.S.S.R., Ser. 1, Fl. Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 1: 14 (1933)

Húsapuntur

- *Triticum repens* L., Sp. Pl.: 86 (1753)
- *Agropyron repens* (L.) P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr.: 102 (1812)
- *Elymus repens* (L.) Gould, Madroño 9: 127 (1947)

○ *Festuca ovina* L.

Sp. Pl.: 73 (1753)

Sauðvingull

Festuca richardsonii Hook.

Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2: 250 (1840)

Túnvingull

- *Festuca rubra* subsp. *pruinosa* (Hack.) Piper, Contr. U.S. Natl. Herb. 10: 22 (1906)
- *Festuca cryophila* V.I. Krecz. & Bobrov, Fl. URSS 2: 519 (1934)
- *Festuca rubra* subsp. *arctica* (Hack.) Govor., Fl. Ural.: 127 (1937)
- *Festuca rubra* subsp. *richardsonii* (Hook.) Hultén, Acta Univ. Lund., n.s., sect. 2, 38, 1: 246 (1942)

100 Salomon (2005) described *E. alopex* from N Iceland and considered it different from *E. caninus* (L.) L. Although the species was not accepted by Elven et al. (2011), it is preliminary accepted in the present list until its status will be clarified.

101 An archaeophyte, see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

Festuca rubra L.

Sp. Pl.: 74 (1753)

– *Festuca duriuscula* L., Sp. Pl.: 74 (1753)

● *Festuca rubra* L. subsp. *rubra*¹⁰²

Rauðvingull

Festuca vivipara (L.) Sm.

Fl. Brit. 1: 114 (1800)

Blávingull

– *Festuca ovina* taxon *vivipara* L., Fl. Suec., ed. 2: 31 (1755)

– *Festuca ovina* auct. non L. (1755)

– *Festuca duriuscula* auct. non L. (1753)

– *Festuca heterophylla* auct. non Lam. (1778/79)

– *Festuca hyperborea* auct. non Holmen (1957)

Glyceria fluitans (L.) R. Br.

Prodr. 1: 179 (1810)

Flóðapuntur

– *Festuca fluitans* L., Sp. Pl.: 75 (1753)

– *Poa fluitans* (L.) Scop., Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 1: 73 (1771)

– *Glyceria fluitans* var. *islandica* Á. Löve, Bot. Not.: 237 (1951)

▼ *Glyceria maxima* (Hartm.) Holmb.¹⁰³

Bot. Not. 1919: 97 (1919)

Fenjapuntur

– by Preyer and Zirkel (1862) as *Glyceria aquatica* (L.) Wahlb.

– by Baring-Gould (1863) as *Poa aquatica* L.

– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Hierochloë odorata (L.) Wahlenb.¹⁰⁴

Fl. Upsal.: 32 (1820)

– *Holcus odoratus* L., Sp. Pl.: 1048 (1753)

– *Hierochloë borealis* (Schrad.) Roem. & Schult., Syst. Veg. 2: 513 (1817)

Hierochloë odorata (L.) Wahlenb. subsp. ***odorata***

Reyrgresi

► *Holcus lanatus* L.¹⁰⁵

Sp. Pl.: 1048 (1753)

Loðgresi

○ *Hordeum jubatum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 85 (1753)

Silkibýgg

– *Critesion jubatum* (L.) Nevski, Fl. URSS 2: 721 (1934)

102 Recent and established adventive.

103 Listed just by two early authors and never confirmed nowadays. No specimens are available.

104 Elven et al. (2011) accepted three subspecies from the Arctic: subsp. *odorata*, subsp. *arctica* and subsp. *kolymensis*. Only nominal subspecies is present in Iceland.

105 A non-native species of unknown age – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

Hordeum marinum Huds.

Fl. Angl., ed. 2: 57 (1778)

- *Hordeum marinum* subsp. *gussoneanum* (Parl.) Thell.

Vierteljahrsschr. Naturf. Ges. Zürich 52: 441 (1908)

Mararbygg

- *Hordeum gussoneanum* Parl., Fl. Palerm. 1: 244 (1845)
- *Hordeum hystrix* Roth, Catal. Bot. 1: 23 (1797)

- *Hordeum murinum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 85 (1753)

Músabygg

- *Triticum murale* Salisb., Prodr. Stirp. Chap. Allerton: 27 (1796), nom. superfl.
- *Zeocriton murinum* (L.) P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr.: 114 (1812)
- *Critesion murinum* (L.) Á. Löve Taxon 29: 350 (1980)

- ◇ *Hordeum vulgare* L.

Sp. Pl.: 84 (1753)

Bygg

Leymus arenarius (L.) Hochst.

Flora 31: 118 (1848)

Melgresi

- *Elymus arenarius* L., Sp. Pl.: 83 (1753)

- *Leymus mollis* (Trin.) Pilg.

Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 74: 6 (1947)

Dúnmelur

- *Elymus mollis* Trin., Neue Entdeck. Pflanzenk. 2: 72 (1821)

- *Lolium arundinaceum* (Schreb.) Darbysh.

Novon 3: 241 (1993)

Tágavingull

- *Festuca arundinacea* Schreb., Spic. Fl. Lips.: 57 (1771), nom. cons.
- *Schedonorus arundinaceus* (Schreb.) Dumort., Observ. Gramin. Belg.: 106 (1824), nom. cons.

- *Lolium multiflorum* Lam.

Fl. Franç. 3: 621 (1779)

Slétturýgresi

- *Lolium perenne* L.

Sp. Pl.: 83 (1753)

Vallarrýgresi

- *Lolium remotum* Schrank

Baier. Fl. 1: 382 (1789)

Línrýgresi

- *Lolium temulentum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 83 (1753)

Eiturrýgresi

Milium effusum L.

Sp. Pl.: 61 (1753)

Skrautpuntur

▼ *Molinia caerulea* (L.) Moench¹⁰⁶

Methodus: 183 (1794)

Bláax

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Aira caerulea* L.
- by Mohr (1786)
- by Thienemann and Guenter (1827)
- by Babington (1871) as *Molinia caerulea*
- by Grønlund (1881) as *Enodium caeruleum* Gaudin
- by Jónsson (1896)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Nardus stricta* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 53 (1753)

Finnungur

 ○ *Phalaris canariensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 54 (1753)

Kanarígras

 ○ *Phalaris arundinacea* L.

Sp. Pl.: 55 (1753)

Strandreyr

- *Typhoides arundinacea* (L.) Moench, Methodus: 202 (1794)
- *Phalaroides arundinacea* (L.) Rauschert, Feddes Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 79: 409 (1969)

***Phippsia algida* (Sol.) R. Br.**

Chlor. Melvill.: 27 (1823)

Snænarfagras

- *Agrostis algida* Sol. in C.J. Phipps, Voy. North Pole: 200 (1774)
- *Catabrosa algida* (Sol.) Fr., Novit. Fl. Suec. Mant. 3: Add. 173, 174 (1843)

***Phleum alpinum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 59 (1753)

Fjallafoxgras

- *Phleum commutatum* Gaudin, Alpina 3: 4 (1808)
- *Phleum alpinum* var. *americanum* E. Fourn., Mexic. Pl. 2: 90 (1886)
- *Phleum haenkeanum* J. Presl, Reliq. Haenk. 1: 245 (1830)
- *Phleum commutatum* var. *americanum* (E. Fourn.) Hultén, Ark. Bot., n.s., 7, 1: 9 (1968)

 ● *Phleum pratense* L.

Sp. Pl.: 59 (1753)

Vallarfoxgras

 ○ *Phragmites australis* (Cav.) Trin. ex Steud.¹⁰⁷

Nomencl. Bot., ed. 2, 2: 324 (1841)

Þakreyr

- *Arundo phragmites* L., Sp. Pl.: 81 (1753)
- *Phragmites communis* Trin., Fund. Agrost.: 134 (1820)

106 Many times listed from Iceland by different authors probably copying the species from previously published lists. There are no specimens available to confirm these doubtful records.

107 Although the species was mentioned by many early authors including König and Müller (1770), it is very doubtful whether it was really present in Iceland before 1995 (Wasowicz et al., 2013).

***Poa alpina* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 67 (1753)

Fjallasveifgras

Poa alpina* L. var. *alpina***Poa alpina* var. *vivipara* L., Sp. Pl.: 67 (1753)**▼ *Poa arctica* R. Br.

Chlor. Melvill.: 30 (1823)

▼ *Poa arctica* subsp. *depauperata* (Fr.) Nannf.¹⁰⁸

Symb. Bot. Upsal. 4(4): 61 (1940)

Heimskautasveifgras

- by Löve (1970)

◆ *Poa annua* L.¹⁰⁹

Sp. Pl.: 68 (1753)

Varpasveifgras

▼ *Poa compressa* L.¹¹⁰

Sp. Pl.: 69 (1753)

Flatsveifgras

- by König and Müller (1770)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Poa flexuosa* Sm.**

Fl. Brit. 1: 101 (1800)

Lotsveifgras

- *Poa laxa* subsp. *flexuosa* (Sm.) Hyl., Nomenkl. Stud. Nord. Gefässpfl.: 78 (1945)***Poa glauca* Vahl**

Fl. Dan. 6, 17: 3, t. 964 (1790)

Blásveifgras

- *Poa caesia* Sm., Fl. Brit. 1: 103 (1800)- *Poa nemoralis* taxon *caesia* Gaudin, Agrost. Helv. 1: 184 (1811)- *Poa bryophila* Trin., Bull. Sci. Acad. Imp. Sci. Saint-Pétersbourg 1: 69 (1836)- *Poa balfourii* Parn., Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. 10: 122, t. 5 (1842)***Poa nemoralis* L.¹¹¹**

Sp. Pl.: 69 (1753)

- *Poa angustifolia* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)***Poa nemoralis* L. subsp. *nemoralis***

Kjarrsveifgras

○ *Poa palustris* L.

Syst. Nat., ed. 10, 2: 874 (1759)

Mýrasveifgras

108 Records of *P. arctica* subsp. *depauperata* from Iceland belong to the series of doubtful and discounted records made by Löve that are, most probably, fictitious (Elven et al., 2011).

109 *P. annua* is most probably an old adventive (archaeophyte) – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

110 Very doubtful record first mentioned by König and Müller (1770) and copied by other authors. No specimens are available and the species has never been confirmed from Iceland.

111 Three subspecies were accepted by Elven et al. (2011) from the Arctic: subsp. *nemoralis*, subsp. *lapponica* and subsp. *subpolaris* but only subsp. *nemoralis* has been found in Iceland.

Poa pratensis L.¹¹²

Sp. Pl.: 67 (1753)

Vallarsveifgras

- *Poa pratensis* L. subsp. *pratensis*¹¹³

Poa pratensis subsp. ***irrigata*** (Lindm.) H. Lindb.¹¹⁴

Pl. Finl. Exsicc. 2: 20 (1916)

- *Poa irrigata* Lindm., Bot. Not. 1905: 88 (1905)
- *Poa humilis* Ehrh. ex Hoffm., Deutschl. Fl. 3: 45 (1800)
- *Poa subcaerulea* Sm. in Sowerby, Engl. Bot. 14: t. 1004 (1802)
- *Poa pratensis* subsp. *subcaerulea* (Sm.) Hiitonen, Suom. Kasvio: 205, f. 5 (1933)

Poa pratensis subsp. ***alpigena*** (Lindm.) Hiitonen

Suom. Kasvio: 205 (1933)

- *Poa alpigena* Lindm., Sv. Fanerogamfl.: 91 (1918)
- ? *Poa rigens* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl.: 448 (1820)

Poa trivialis L.

Sp. Pl.: 67 (1753)

Hásveifgras

Poa* × *jemtlandica (Almq.) K. Richt

Pl. Eur. 1: 84 (1890)

Hjallasveifgras

- *Poa alpina* var. *jemtlandica* Almq., Bot. Centralbl. 14: 135 (1859)

 ▼ *Polypogon monspeliensis* (L.) Desf.¹¹⁵

Flora Atlant. 1: 67 (1798)

Bartagras

- by Babington (1871) as *Alopecurus monspeliensis* L.
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Puccinellia coarctata Fernald & Weath.

Rhodora 18: 13 (1916)

Varpafitjungur

- *Phippsia coarctata* (Fernald & Weath.) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 299 (1970)
- *Puccinellia retroflexa* subsp. *borealis* Holmb., Bot. Not. 1926: 182 (1926)
- *Puccinellia retroflexa* var. *borealis* (Holmb.) Hyl., Nomenkl. Stud. Nord. Gefässpfl.: 79 (1945)
- *Phippsia nutkaënsis* subsp. *borealis* (Holmb.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 500 (1976)
- *Puccinellia distans* subsp. *borealis* (Holmb.) W.E. Hughes, Bot. J. Linn. Soc. 76: 363 (1978)
- ? *Glyceria arctica* auct. non Hook. (1840)
- ? *Glyceria borrieri* auct. non Bab. (1843)
- *Glyceria distans* auct. non Wahlenb. (1820)
- *Poa distans* auct. non Jacq. (1764)
- *Sclerochloa distans* auct. non Bab. (1843)

112 *P. pratensis* represents another difficult and at least partly agamospermic species complex. The limits between taxa are unclear and more research is needed to elucidate both taxonomy and biogeography of the species in Iceland.

113 *P. pratensis* subsp. *pratensis* is an established adventive in Iceland.

114 *P. pratensis* subsp. *irrigata* is a native, seashore plant.

115 Very weird record listed by Babington (1871) who refers this finding to Solander and states that "it is an exceedingly unlikely plant to grow in Iceland".

Puccinellia maritima (Huds.) Parl.

Fl. Ital. 1: 370 (1850)

Sjávarfitjungur

- *Poa maritima* Huds., Fl. Angl.: 35 (1762)
- *Sclerochloa maritima* (Huds.) Lindl., Man. Brit. Bot.: 370 (1843), nom. illeg.
- *Phippsia maritima* (Huds.) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 299 (1970)
- ? *Glyceria maritima* (Huds.) Wahlenb., Fl. Gothob.: 17 (1820)

▼ *Rostraria cristata* (L.) Tzvelev¹¹⁶

Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 7: 47 (1970)

- by Bennett (1886) as *Koeleria cristata* L.■ ***Schedonorus pratensis*** (Huds.) P. Beauv.¹¹⁷

Ess. Agrostogr.: 99 (1812)

Hávingull

- *Festuca pratensis* Huds., Fl. Angl.: 37 (1762)
- *Schedonorus pratensis* (Huds.) P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr.: 99 (1812)
- *Lolium pratense* (Huds.) Darbysh., Novon 3: 242 (1993)
- ? *Festuca elatior* sensu König and Müller (1770) non L. (1753)
- ? *Festuca arundinacea* auct. non Schreb. (1771), nom. cons.

○ *Secale cereale* L.

Sp. Pl.: 84 (1753)

Rúgur

Sesleria albicans Kit. in J.A. Schultes

Oestr. Fl., ed. 2, 1: 216 (1814)

Blátoppa

- *Cynosurus caeruleus* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Sesleria caerulea* auct. non Ard. (1764)
- ? *Sesleria albicans* var. *hadacii* (Deyl) Á. Löve

Trisetum spicatum (L.) K. Richt.¹¹⁸

Pl. Eur. 1: 59 (1890)

Fjallalógresi

- *Aira spicata* L., Sp. Pl.: 64 (1753)
- *Trisetum spicatum* var. *villosissimum* (Lange) Louis-Marie, Rhodora 30: 239 (1928)

Trisetum molle (Michx.) Kunth

Révis. Gramin. 1: 101 (1829)

Móalógresi

- *Avena mollis* Michx., Fl. Bor.-Amer. 1: 72 (1803), non Salisb. (1796)
- *Trisetum spicatum* var. *molle* (Michx.) Beal, Grass. N. Amer. 2: 377 (1887)
- *Trisetum spicatum* subsp. *molle* (Michx.) Hultén, Svensk Bot. Tidskr. 53: 216 (1959)
- *Trisetum triflorum* subsp. *molle* (Kunth) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Univ. Colorado Stud., Ser. Biol. 17: 8 (1965)

116 Bennett (1886) states: "Dyrafjord, N.W. coast, by Wendil (1881) in herb. Berlin". No specimens are available, and the species has never been confirmed again from Dýrafjörður. It was most probably a misidentification.

117 *S. pratensis* is a doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

118 *T. spicatum* aggregate is a polymorphic group and different views and approaches to this taxon result in very different classifications. Here, two separate species were accepted from Iceland: *T. spicatum* and *T. molle* (= *T. triflorum*). In Iceland they co-occur in many places without any clear signs of transitions, which suggests reproductive isolation. This fact, as well as clear morphological differences, supports recognition of two separate species. The same view was accepted by Kristinsson (2008) and Elven et al. (2011). Some taxonomists, however, synonymize *T. molle* with *T. spicatum*.

- *Melica triflora* Bigelow, New Engl. J. Med. Surg. 5: 334 (1816)
- *Trisetum triflorum* (Bigelow) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Univ. Colorado Stud., Ser. Biol. 17: 7 (1965)
- *Trisetum majus* Vasey ex Rydb., Agric. Exp. Sta. Agric. Coll. Colorado Bull. 100: 34 (1906)
- *Trisetum spicatum* var. *majus* (Vasey ex Rydb.) Farw., Rep. Michigan Acad. Sci. 21: 352 (1920)
- *Trisetum spicatum* var. *pilosiglume* Fernald, Rhodora 18: 195 (1916)
- *Trisetum spicatum* subsp. *pilosiglume* (Fernald) Hultén, Svensk Bot. Tidskr. 53: 215 (1959)
- *Trisetum subspicatum* P. Beauv., Ess. Agrostogr.: 88 (1812), nom. superfl.

○ *Triticum aestivum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 85 (1753)

Hveiti

○ *Triticum compactum* Host

Icon. Descr. Gram. Austriac. 4: 4 (1809)

Dverghveiti

CERATOPHYLLACEAE Gray

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 395, 554 (1822), nom. cons.

Kransblaðætt

▼ *Ceratophyllum demersum* L.¹¹⁹

Sp. Pl.: 1992 (1753)

Hnotkransblað

- by König and Müller (1770)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

PAPAVERACEAE Gray

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 235 (1789), nom. cons.

Draumsóleyjaætt

○ *Fumaria officinalis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 700 (1753)

Reykjurt

○ *Papaver cambricum* L.¹²⁰

Sp. Pl.: 508 (1753)

Gulsól

- *Meconopsis cambrica* (L.) Vig., Hist. Nat. Pavots: 48 (1814)

● *Papaver croceum* Ledeb.¹²¹

Fl. Altaic. 2: 271 (1830)

Garðasól

- ? *Papaver nudicaule* sensu Grønlund (1881), non L. (1753)

- *Papaver nudicaule* auct. non L. (1753)

119 Recorded by some early authors most probably by a mistake (probably misdiagnosed *Myriophyllum* sp.)

120 Previously treated by Kristinsson (2008), as *Meconopsis cambrica*. Recently published study (Kadereit et al. 2011) has shown that the taxon should revert to its former name *Papaver cambricum*.

121 The name *Papaver croceum* was misapplied to this Asian species native to southern Siberia, Central Asia and Northern China (Elven et al. 2011).

Papaver radicum Rottb.

Skr. Kiøbenhavnske Selsk. Lærd. Elsk. 10: 455 (1770)

- *Papaver alpinum* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Papaver nudicaule* auct. non L. (1753)

Papaver radicum Rottb. subsp. ***radicum***

Skr. Kiøbenhavnske Selsk. Lærd. Elsk. 10: 455 (1770)

Melasól

- *Papaver nordhagenianum* subsp. *islandicum* (C.E. Lundstr.) Á. Löve, Nytt Mag. Bot. 4: 16 (1955)

- *Papaver nordhagenianum* var. *islandicum* (Á. Löve) Á. Löve, Bot. Not.: 113 (1960)

- *Papaver relictum* var. *islandicum* (Á. Löve) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 300 (1970)

- * ***Papaver radicum*** subsp. ***stefanssonii*** (Á. Löve) Jonsell & Ö. Nilsson

Stefánsól

Nordic J. Bot. 20: 521 (2001)

- *Papaver nordhagenianum* subsp. *stefanssonii* Á. Löve, Taxon 11: 137 (1962)

- *Papaver stefanssonianum* Á. Löve, Nytt Mag. Bot. 4: 14 (1955)

- *Papaver relictum* var. *stefanssonii* (Á. Löve) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 300 (1970)

- * ***Papaver radicum*** subsp. ***steindorssonianum*** (Á. Löve) Knaben ex Ö. Nilsson

Nordic J. Bot. 20: 521 (2001)

- *Papaver steindorssonianum* Á. Löve, Nytt Mag. Bot. 4: 15 (1955)

- *Papaver nordhagenianum* subsp. *steindorssonianum* (Á. Löve) Á. Löve, Taxon 11: 137 (1962)

- *Papaver relictum* var. *steindorssonianum* (Á. Löve) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 300 (1970)

- *Papaver radicum* f. *albiflora* Stefánsson (1901)

- *Papaver radicum* f. *rubriflora* Stefánsson (1901)

○ *Papaver somniferum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 508 (1753)

Draumsól

RANUNCULACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 231 (1789), nom. cons.

Sóleyjaætt

○ *Aconitum* × *stoerkianum* Rchb.

Flora 1: 202 (1818)

Fagurhjálmur

- *Aconitum intermedium* DC., Syst. Nat. 1: 374 (1817)

- *Aconitum* × *cammarum* auct. non L. (1762)

Aconitum napellus L.

Sp. Pl.: 532 (1753)

○ *Aconitum napellus* subsp. *lusitanicum* Rouy

Naturaliste 6(51): 405 (1884)

Venusvagn

● *Anemone nemorosa* L.

Sp. Pl.: 541 (1753)

Skógarsóley

***Caltha palustris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 558 (1753)

Hófsóley

Caltha palustris* L. subsp. *palustris***Caltha palustris* subsp. *radicans* (T.F. Forst.) Syme**

Engl. Bot., ed. 3, 1: 49 (1873)

- *Caltha radicans* T.F. Forst., Trans. Linn. Soc. London 8: 324, t. 17 (1807)
- *Caltha palustris* var. *radicans* (T.F. Forst.) Beck, Verh. K.K. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 36: 350 (1886)
- *Caltha arctica* R. Br., Chlor. Melvill.: 7 (1823)
- *Caltha palustris* var. *arctica* (R. Br.) Huth, Helios 9: 18 (1892)
- *Caltha palustris* subsp. *arctica* (R. Br.) Hultén, Ark. Bot., n.s., 7, 1: 56 (1968)
- *Caltha minor* subsp. *arctica* (R. Br.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 510 (1976)

○ *Ranunculus aconitifolius* L.

Sp. Pl.: 551 (1753)

Silfursóley

○ *Ranunculus acris* L.

Sp. Pl.: 554 (1753)

Ranunculus auricomus* L. sensu lato, Sp. Pl.: 551 (1753)¹²²**[Ranunculus islandicus*** (Fagerstr. & Kvist) Ericsson Ann. Bot. Fenn. 29: 142 (1992)]

Sifjarsóley

- *Ranunculus auricomus* subsp. *islandicus* Fagerstr. & Kvist, Náttúrufræðingurinn 50(2): 139 (1980)

***Ranunculus confervoides* (Fr.) Fr.**

Summa Veg. Scand. 1: 139 (1845)

Lónasóley

- *Batrachium confervoides* Fr., Bot. Not. 1845: 121 (1845)
- *Batrachium eradatum* (Laest.) Fr., Bot. Not. 1843: 114 (1843)
- *Batrachium trichophyllum* Van den Bosch, Prodr. Fl. Bat. 1: 5 (1850)
- *Ranunculus trichophyllus* var. *eradicatus* (Laestr.) Drew, Rhodora 38: 33 (1936)
- *Ranunculus aquaticus* auct, non Neck (1768)
- *Batrachium drouetii* sensu Grønlund (1881), non Nyman (1852)
- *Batrachium paucistamineum* var. *eradicatum* sensu Stefánsson (1901), non Gelert (1894)

***Ranunculus glacialis* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 553 (1753)

- *Beckwithia glacialis* (L.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20, 4: 252 (1956)

Ranunculus glacialis* L. subsp. *glacialis

Jöklasóley

***Ranunculus hyperboreus* Rottb.**

Skr. Kjøbenhavnske Selsk. Lærd. Elsk. 10: 458 (1770)

- *Ranunculus ammanni* Gunnerus, Fl. Norveg. 2: 103 (1772)
- *Ranunculus hederaceus* auct. non L. (1753)

Ranunculus hyperboreus* Rottb. subsp. *hyperboreus

Trefjasóley

¹²² A large complex (605 species) of apomictic plants have been recorded from the Nordic countries (Ericsson 2001). Plants from *Ranunculus auricomus* group have been studied in Iceland (Fagerström and Kvist 1980, Ericsson 1992, 2001) and classified as a single microspecies *Ranunculus islandicus*. *Ranunculus auricomus* L. s.str. is not known from Iceland.

▼ *Ranunculus lapponicus* L.¹²³

Sp. Pl.: 553 (1753)

Lappasóley

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Hooker (1811)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Ranunculus montanus* L.¹²⁴

Sp. Pl.: 1321 (1753)

Hnúðsóley

- by Thienemann and Guenter (1827)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Ranunculus nivalis* L.¹²⁵

Sp. Pl. 553 (1753)

Snæsóley

- by Mohr (1786)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Ranunculus polyanthemos* L.¹²⁶

Sp. Pl. 554 (1753)

Runnasóley

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Thienemann and Guenter (1827)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Ranunculus pygmaeus* Wahlenb.**

Fl. Lapp.: 157 (1812)

Dvergsóley

◆ *Ranunculus repens* L.¹²⁷

Sp. Pl.: 554 (1753)

Skriðsóley

***Ranunculus reptans* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 549 (1753)

Flagasóley

123 *R. lapponicus* was reported by König and Müller (1770) and subsequently copied by some of the early authors. There are no specimens available to confirm these findings.

124 *R. montanus* was recorded once from Iceland. This record was then copied by Babington (1871). There is no evidence to confirm the presence of the species in Iceland.

125 *R. nivalis* was recorded from several places in Iceland, but these old records have never been confirmed by recent findings.

126 *R. polyanthemos* was recorded by some early authors but never confirmed from Iceland.

127 *R. repens* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

Ranunculus subborealis Tzvelev¹²⁸

Byull. Moskovsk. Obshch. Isp. Prir., Otd. Biol. 99(5): 70 (1994)

Brennisóley

Ranunculus subborealis subsp. ***pumilus*** (Wahlenb.) Elven

J. Bot. Res. Inst. Texas 2: 437 (2008)

– *Ranunculus acris* var. *pumilus* Wahlenb., Fl. Suec. 1: 351 (1824)– *Ranunculus acris* subsp. *pumilus* (Wahlenb.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Taxon 34: 164 (1985), comb. illeg.***Ranunculus subborealis*** subsp. ***villosus*** (Drabble) Elven

J. Bot. Res. Inst. Texas 2: 437 (2008)

– *Ranunculus acris* f. *villosus* Drabble, Bot. Soc. Exch. Club Brit. Isles 9: 472 (1930)– *Ranunculus acris* var. *villosus* (Drabble) S.M. Coles, Watsonia 8: 240 (1971)***Thalictrum alpinum*** L.

Sp. Pl.: 545 (1753)

Brjóstagras

○ *Trollius europaeus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 556 (1753)

Gullhnappur

GROSSULARIACEAE DC.

Fl. Franc. [de Candolle & Lamarck], ed. 3, 4(2): 405 (1805), nom. cons.

Stikilsberjaætt

○ *Ribes nigrum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 201 (1753)

Sólberjarifs

● *Ribes pallidum* Otto & A.Dietr.

Allg. Gartenzeitung 10: 268 (1842)

Rifsberjarunn

○ *Ribes spicatum* Robson¹²⁹

Arr. Br. Pl. ed. 3, 2: 265 (1796)

Skógarrifs

○ *Ribes rubrum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 200 (1753)

Rauðberjarif

○ *Ribes uva-crispa* L.

Sp. Pl.: 201 (1753)

Stikilsberjarunni

128 *R. subborealis* belongs to *Ranunculus acris* aggregate. Different treatments for this widespread aggregate have been published. They range from treating *R. acris* as one mega-species to dividing it into five or more taxa. All treatments of this complex are provisional and further studies are needed to elucidate morphological, taxonomic and phylogenetic relationships among the taxa (Nurmi 2001, Elven et al. 2011). We follow here treatment proposed by Elven et al. (2011) and subsequently classified Icelandic plants as *R. subborealis*. It should, however, be acknowledged that Nurmi (2001) considered the aggregate as a group of closely related, diploid and inter-fertile subspecies and varieties within *R. acris* and classified Icelandic plants as *R. acris* subsp. *borealis* (Regel) Nyman, Consp. Fl. Eur.: 12 (1878). See also Nurmi (2001) and Elven et al. (2011) for more discussion on that topic.

129 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

SAXIFRAGACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 308 (1789), nom. cons.

Steinbrjótsætt

Micranthes foliolosa (R. Br.) Gornall

J. Bot. Res. Inst. Texas 1: 1020 (2007)

Hreistursteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga foliolosa* R. Br., Chlor. Melvill.: 17 (1823)
- *Saxifraga stellaris* var. *foliolosa* (R. Br.) Turcz., Pl. Imag. Descr. Fl. Russ. 7: 80 (1846)
- *Spatularia foliolosa* (R. Br.) Small, N. Amer. Fl. 22(2): 149 (1905)

Micranthes nivalis (L.) Small

N. Amer. Fl. 22(2): 136 (1905)

Snæsteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga nivalis* L., Sp. Pl.: 401 (1753)

▼ ***Micranthes punctata*** (L.) Losinsk.¹³⁰

Izv. Glavn. Bot. Sada SSSR 27: 601 (1928)

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Saxifraga punctata*
- by Hooker (1811) as *Saxifraga punctata*
- by Babington (1871) as *Saxifraga punctate*
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Micranthes stellaris (L.) Galasso, Banfi & Soldano

Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. Mus. Civico Storia Nat. Milano 146(2): 231 (2005)

- *Saxifraga stellaris* L., Sp. Pl.: 400 (1753)
- *Spatularia stellaris* (L.) Haw., Saxifr. Enum.: 49 (1821)

Micranthes stellaris (L.) Galasso, Banfi & Soldano subsp. ***stellaris***¹³¹

Stjörnusteinbrjótur

Micranthes tenuis (Wahlenb.) Small

N. Amer. Fl. 22(2): 136 (1905)

Dvergsteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga nivalis* var. *tenuis* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 114 (1812)
- *Saxifraga tenuis* (Wahlenb.) Smith ex Lindman, Svensk Fanerogamfl.: 300 (1918)

Saxifraga aizoides L.

Sp. Pl.: 403 (1753)

Gullsteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga autumnalis* L., Sp. Pl. 402 (1753)
- *Leptasea aizoides* (L.) Haw., Saxifr. Enum.: 40 (1821)

○ *Saxifraga* × *arendsii* Engel.

Roðasteinbrjótur

Saxifraga cernua L.

Sp. Pl.: 403 (1753)

Laukasteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga bulbifera* Oed., Fl. Dan. t. 390 (1768)

130 The probability of finding this Far East, Asian species in Iceland is very low and these records are most probably misidentifications.

131 Other subspecies were recorded from mountains in Europe in Iceland only subsp. *stellaris* is present.

***Saxifraga cespitosa* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 404 (1753)

- *Muscaria cespitosa* Haw., Saxifr. Enum.: 37 (1821)
- *Saxifraga decipiens* sensu Grønlund (1881), non Ehrh. (1790)¹³²

Saxifraga cespitosa* L. subsp. *cespitosa

Þúfusteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga groenlandica* L., Sp. Pl.: 404 (1753)
- *Saxifraga uniflora* R. Br., Chlor. Melvill.: 16 (1823)
- *Saxifraga cespitosa* subsp. *uniflora* (R. Br.) A.E. Porsild, Bull. Natl. Mus. Canada 135: 135 (1955)
- *Saxifraga groenlandica* subsp. *exaratooides* Simmons, Vasc. Pl. Ellesmereland: 73
- *Saxifraga cespitosa* subsp. *exaratooides* (Simmons) Irmsch. in Engl., Pflanzenreich IV-117, 67: 375 (1916)
- *Saxifraga cespitosa* var. *aurea* Hadac, Studia Bot. Cech. 5, 1-2: 4 (1942)
- *Saxifraga aurea* (Hadac) Rønning, Svalb. Fl., ed. 3: 115 (1996), comb. illeg.
- *Saxifraga cespitosa* f. *laxiuscula* Engl. & Irmsch. in Engl., Pflanzenreich IV-117, 67: 371 (1916)
- *Saxifraga cespitosa* subsp. *laxiuscula* (Engl. & Irmsch.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 53 (1961)
- *Muscaria cespitosa* subsp. *laxiuscula* (Engler & Irmscher) Á. Löve, Phytologia, 50(3): 171 (1982)

***Saxifraga cotyledon* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 398 (1753)

Klettafrú

- *Saxifraga cotyledon* var. *multicaulis* Stefansson, Flóra Íslands: 127 (1901), nom. inval.
- *Chondrosea cotyledon* (L.) Á. Löve, Phytologia 50(3): 171 (1982)

▼ ***Saxifraga cuneifolia* L.**¹³³

Sp. Pl.: 574 (1753)

Rökkursteinbrjótur

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Hjaltalín (1830)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ ***Saxifraga geranioides* L.**¹³⁴

Amoen. Acad. 4: 271 (1759)

Storkasteinbrjótur

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

● ***Saxifraga granulata* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 403 (1753)

Kornasteinbrjótur

132 Grønlund (1881) uses the name *Saxifraga decipiens* Ehrh. as a synonym of *Saxifraga cespitosa* L. and mention that the taxon in question is very common ("meget almindelig").

133 *S. cuneifolia* has been most probably recorded due to a misidentification present in some of the old floristic records from Iceland.

134 It is very unlikely that *S. geranioides* known just from E-Pyrenees and NE-Spain has been found in Iceland. It is most probably a misidentification.

***Saxifraga hirculus* L.¹³⁵**

Sp. Pl.: 402 (1753)

Gullbrá

- *Leptasea hirculus* (L.) Small, N. Amer. Fl. 22(2): 152 (1905)
- *Hirculus ranunculoides* Haw., Saxifr. Enum.: 40 (1821)
- *Saxifraga hirculus* subsp. *alpina* sensu Löve (1983)

Saxifraga hirculus* L. subsp. *hirculus***Saxifraga hirculus* subsp. *compacta* O.Hedb.**

Bot. J. Linn. Soc. 109: 388 (1992)

***Saxifraga hypnoides* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 405 (1753)

Mosasteinbrjótur

- *Muscaria hypnoides* Jord. & Fourr., Ann. Soc. L. Lyon, N.s. 16: 386 (1868)

***Saxifraga oppositifolia* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 402 (1753)

- *Antiphylla oppositifolia* (L.) Fourr., Ann. Soc. Linn. Lyon, sér. 2, 16: 386 (1868)

Saxifraga oppositifolia* L. subsp. *oppositifolia

Vetrarsteinbrjótur (Vetrarblóm)

***Saxifraga paniculata* Mill.**

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: Saxifraga no. 3 (1768)

- *Saxifraga aizoon* Jacq., Fl. Austriac. 5: 18 (1778)

***Saxifraga paniculata* subsp. *laestadii* (Neuman) Karlsson¹³⁶**

Svensk Botanisk Tidskrift 91(5): 249 (1997)

Bergsteinbrjótur

- *Saxifraga aizoon* subsp. *laestadii* Neuman, Bot. Not.: 263–265, f. 2–3 (1905)
- *Saxifraga aizoon* var. *neogaea* Butters, Rhodora 46(543): 65–67, pl. 817, f. 6–11 (1944)
- *Saxifraga paniculata* subsp. *neogaea* (Butters) D. Löve, Taxon 17(1): 89 (1968)
- *Chondrosea paniculata* subsp. *neogaea* (Butters) Á. Löve, Phytologia, 50(3): 171 (1982)

▼ *Saxifraga petraea* L.¹³⁷

Syst. Nat., ed. 10. 2: 1027 (1759)

- by Zoëga (1772)
- by Mohr (1786)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Saxifraga rivularis* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 404 (1753)

Saxifraga rivularis* L. subsp. *rivularis

Lækjasteinbrjótur

135 The presence of both subspecies within *S. hirculus* was confirmed in Iceland by Hedberg (1992). Iceland is a contact zone between subsp. *hirculus* (more southern taxon) and subsp. *compacta* (a taxon with more northern distribution pattern). Intermediate forms are frequent.

136 *S. paniculata* subsp. *laestadii* is an amphi-Atlantic and arctic-alpine species. Icelandic specimens have been classified as subsp. *paniculata* by Hulten and Fries (1986), but Butters (1944) and Jørgensen et al. (1958) assigned Icelandic material to subsp. *neogaea*. New research on *S. paniculata* carried out by Reisch (2008) showed that Icelandic populations are genetically similar to those from northern Norway. Since the northern Norwegian population was recognised as a separate taxon as early as in 1905 the subspecific name subsp. *laestadii* Neuman has a priority over var. *neogaea* Butters described in 1944. See also discussion in Elven et al. (2011)

137 It is very unlikely that *S. petraea* known from NE-Italy and Slovenia has been found in Iceland. It is most probably a misidentification.

Saxifraga rosacea Moench¹³⁸

Methodus: 106 (1794)

- ? *Saxifraga palmata* Sm., Engl. Bot. t. 455 (1797)
- ? *Muscaria decipiens* (Ehrh.) Á. Löve, Phytologia, 50(3): 171 (1982)

Saxifraga rosacea Moench. subsp. ***rosacea***

Toppasteinbrjótur

▼ *Saxifraga tridactylites* L.¹³⁹

Sp. Pl.: 404 (1753)

Prenningarsteinbrjótur

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Zoëga (1772)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Saxifraga tricuspidata* Rottb.¹⁴⁰

Skrift. Kioeb. Selsk. 10: 446

Þyrnisteinbrjótur

- by Hooker (1811)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Saxifraga umbrosa* L.

Sp. Pl. (ed. 2): 574 (1762)

Skuggasteinbrjótur

CRASSULACEAE J.St.-Hil.

Expos. Fam. Nat. 2: 123. (1805), nom. cons.

Hnoðraætt

Crassula aquatica (L.) Schönland

Nat. Pflanzenfam. 51, III, 2a: 37 (1890)

Vatnsögn

- *Tillaea aquatica* L., Sp. Pl.: 128 (1753)
- *Bulliarda aquatica* (L.) DC., Bull. Sci. Soc. Philom. Paris 3(49): 2 (1801)

○ *Hylotelephium maximum* (L.) Holub

Severoceskou Prirod., 89(2): 144 (1978)

Völvuhnoðri

- *Sedum maximum* Suter, Fl. Helvet.: 270 (1222)

○ *Hylotelephium telephium* (L.) H. Ohba

Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 90: 53 (1977)

Sumarhnoðri

- *Sedum telephium* L., Sp. Pl.: 430 (1753)

138 The question of the presence of *S. rosacea* in Iceland and its delimitation from *S. caespitosa* remains unresolved but here the presence of the species was accepted following Kristinsson (2008) and Elven et al. (2011)

139 There are several reports of *S. tridactylites* by some of the early authors. It has been recorded from Grænafell, Þingvellir, Mývatn and Öxará. There are no specimens available to confirm these records and the species has not been recorded from Iceland by more recent authors.

140 *S. tricuspidata* was recorded by Hooker (1811) from Reykjavík. Most probably misidentification.

***Rhodiola rosea* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1035 (1753)

- *Sedum rosea* (L.) Scop., Fl. Carniol. ed. 2, 1: 326 (1771)
- *Sedum rhodiola* DC., Fl. Fr. 4: 386 (1805)

Rhodiola rosea* L. subsp. *rosea

Burnirót

- *Rhodiola arctica* Boriss., Fl. URSS 9: 471 (1939)
- *Rhodiola rosea* subsp. *arctica* (Boriss.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 52 (1961)
- *Sedum rosea* subsp. *arcticum* (Boriss.) Engelskjøn & H.J. Schweitzer, Astarte 3: 16 (1970)

***Sedum acre* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 432 (1753), nom. cons.

Helluhnoðri

○ *Sedum album* L.

Sp. Pl.: 432 (1753)

Ljósahnoðri

▼ *Sedum anglicum* Hudson¹⁴¹

Fl. Angl. ed. 2: 196 (1778)

Bretahnoðri

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Vahl (1840)
- by Baring-Gould (1863)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Sedum annuum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 432 (1753)

Skriðuhnoðri

- *Sedum saxatile* Weber, Prim. Fl. Holsat.: 35 (1780)
- *Etiosedum annuum* (L.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Taxon 34: 163 (1985)

***Sedum villosum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 432 (1753)

Flagahnoðri

- *Oreosedum villosum* (L.) Grulich, Preslia 56: 45 (1984)
- *Hjaltalínia villosa* (L.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Taxon 34: 163 (1985)

HALORAGACEAE R. Br.

Voy. Terra Austral. 2: 549 (1814), nom. cons.

***Myriophyllum alterniflorum* DC.**

Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 6: 529 (1815)

Síkjamari

141 *S. anglicum* was recorded by some of the early authors but it has never been confirmed more recently. There are no specimens available to confirm these findings.

Myriophyllum sibiricum Kom.

Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 13: 168 (1914)

Vatnamari

- *Myriophyllum exalbescens* Fernald, Rhodora 21: 120 (1919)
- *Myriophyllum spicatum* subsp. *exalbescens* (Fernald) E. Murray, Kalmia 12: 22 (1982)
- *Myriophyllum spicatum* subsp. *squamosum* Laest. ex C. Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl., ed.7: 150 (1858)
- *Myriophyllum spicatum* auct. non L. (1753)

▼ *Myriophyllum verticillatum* L.¹⁴²

Sp. Pl.: 992 (1753)

Tjarnamari

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Grønlund (1881)
- by Stefánsson (1901)
- by Ostenfeld and Grøntved (1934)
- by Grøntved (1942)
- by Stefánsson (1948)

FABACEAE Lindl. (= Leguminosae Juss., nom. cons.)

Intr. Nat. Syst. Bot. ed. 2.: 148 (1836), nom. cons.

Ertublómaætt

Anthyllis vulneraria L.

Sp. Pl.: 719 (1753)

Anthyllis vulneraria subsp. ***borealis*** (Rouy) Jalas

Ann. Bot. Soc. Zool.-Bot. Fenn. Vanamo 24(1): 40 (1950)

Gullkollur

- ? *Anthyllis vulneraria* var. *borealis* Á. Löve

○ *Astragalus alpinus* Willd.

Sp. Pl.: 760 (1753)

Seljahnúta

Lathyrus japonicus Willd.¹⁴³

Sp. Pl. ed.4. 3(2): 1092 (1802)

Baunagras

- *Pisum maritimum* L., Sp. Pl.: 727 (1753)
- *Lathyrus maritimus* Bigelow, Fl. Boston., ed. 3: 286 (1840)
- *Lathyrus maritimus* (L.) Fr., Fl. Scan.: 106 (1835)

142 *M. verticillatum* has been present in many species lists by early authors as well as recorded by more contemporary botanists. It seems that there are no specimens available to confirm its presence in Iceland (all older herbarium materials were redetermined as *M. alternifolium*). More field studies are needed to elucidate the question of the presence of *M. verticillatum* in Iceland.

143 The subdivision of this species has long been debated and it seems that the pubescence received much attention as an important character. Hulten and Fries (1986) have mapped glabrous vs. pubescent specimens and stated that glabrous form occurs in SW Iceland, whereas all other Icelandic localities on their map are marked as "pubescence unknown". It is clear, however, that most specimens in Icelandic herbaria are more or less pubescent. Löve (1983) recognised two separate subspecies from Iceland: hairless (*Lathyrus maritimus* (L.) Bigel subsp. *maritimus*) and pubescent *L. maritimus* (L.) Bigel subsp. *pubescens* (C. Hartm.) C. Regel. On the other hand Kristinsson (2008) mentioned just one pubescent taxon: *Lathyrus japonicus* Willd. subsp. *maritimus* (L.) P.W. Ball. Taking all these complications into account it seems safer not to accept any subdivision within *L. japonicus* and to inform the reader that pubescent form is most probably predominant in Iceland, just as in other northern regions (Hulten and Fries 1986, Elven et al. 2011).

***Lathyrus palustris* L.¹⁴⁴**

Sp. Pl.: 733 (1753)

■ ***Lathyrus palustris* subsp. *pilosus* (Cham.) Hultén¹⁴⁵**

Fl. Aleut. Isl.: 236 (1937)

Mýraertur

■ ***Lathyrus pratensis* L.¹⁴⁶**

Sp. Pl.: 733 (1753)

Fuglaertur

○ *Lotus corniculatus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 775 (1753)

Akurmaríuskór

○ *Lupinus arcticus* S. Watson

Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts 8: 526 (1873)

Skollalúpína

● *Lupinus nootkatensis* Donn ex Sims¹⁴⁷

Bot. Mag. 32: t. 1311 (1810)

Alaskalúpína

○ *Lupinus polyphyllus* Lindl.

Bot. Reg. 13: t. 1096 (1827)

Garðalúpína

○ *Medicago lupulina* L.

Sp. Pl.: 779 (1753)

Úlfasmári

○ *Medicago sativa* L.

Sp. Pl.: 778 (1753)

Refasmári

○ *Melilotus albus* Medik.

Vorles. Churpfälz. Phys.-Öcon. Ges. 2: 382 (1787)

Mjallarsteinsmári

○ *Melilotus officinalis* (L.) Lam.

Fl. Franç.: 594 (1779)

Mánasteinsmári

– *Melilotus arvensis* Wallr., Sched. Crit.: 391 (1822)○ *Pisum arvense* L.

Sp. Pl.: 727 (1753)

Gráertur

144 There are two subspecies recognised within *L. palustris*: glabrous - subsp. *palustris* and pubescent - subsp. *pilosus* (Cham.) Hultén. Contrary to Hultén and Fries (1986) all Icelandic material was assigned to subsp. *pilosus* since all the plants deposited in Icelandic herbaria have the hairs characteristic for this taxon.

145 *L. palustris* subsp. *pilosus* is a doubtfully native taxon – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

146 *L. pratensis* is a doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

147 *L. nootkatensis* is a highly invasive species intentionally introduced to Iceland in 1945 (Kristinsson 2008).

- *Pisum sativum* L.
 Sp. Pl.: 727 (1753)
 Garðertur
- ▼ *Trifolium arvense* L.¹⁴⁸
 Sp. Pl.: 769 (1753)
 Hérasmári
 - by König and Müller (1770)
 - by Baring-Gould (1863)
 - by Babington (1871)
 - rejected by Grøntved (1942)
- *Trifolium aureum* Pollich
 Hist. Pl. Palat. 2: 344 (1777)
 Gullsmári
 - *Trifolium agrarium* L., Sp. Pl.: 772 (1753)
- *Trifolium dubium* Sibth.
 Fl. Oxon.: 231 (1794)
 Músasmári
 - *Trifolium minus* Sm. in Relham, Fl. Cantabr. ed. 2: 290 (1802)
- *Trifolium hybridum* L.
 Sp. Pl.: 766 (1753)
 Túnsmári
- *Trifolium medium* L.
 Amoen. Acad., Linnaeus ed. 4: 105 (1759)
 Skógarsmári
- *Trifolium pratense* L.
 Sp. Pl.: 768 (1753)
 Rauðsmári
- ***Trifolium repens*** L.¹⁴⁹
 Sp. Pl.: 767 (1753)
 Hvítsmári
 - *Amoria repens* (L.) C. Presl, Symb. Bot. 1: 47 (1831)
- *Vicia angustifolia* L.
 Amoen. Acad., Linnaeus ed. 4: 105 (1759)
 Sumarflækja
- ◆ *Vicia cracca* L.¹⁵⁰
 Sp. Pl.: 735 (1753)
 Umfeðmingur
 - *Vicia oreophila* Zertová, Novit. Bot. Horti Bot. Univ. Carol. Prag. 1962: 51 (1962)
 - *Vicia cracca* subsp. *oreophila* (Zertová) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Preslia 46: 132 (1974)

148 *T. arvense* was recorded by some early authors. It is certainly not native, but there are no specimens available to confirm this species as casual alien.

149 *T. repens* is a doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

150 *V. cracca* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

○ *Vicia hirsuta* (L.) Gray
Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 614 (1821)
Loðflækja
– *Ervum hirsutum* L., Sp. Pl.: 738 (1753)

○ *Vicia sativa* L.
Sp. Pl.: 736 (1753)
Fóðurflækja (Akurflækja)

▶ *Vicia sepium* L.¹⁵¹
Sp. Pl.: 737 (1753)
Giljaflækja

○ *Vicia villosa* Roth
Tent. Fl. Germ. 2(2): 182 (1793)
Dúnflækja

POLYGALACEAE Hoffmanns. & Link
Fl. Portug. [Hoffmannsegg] 1: 62 (1809), nom. cons.
Blávængjuætt

▼ *Polygala vulgaris* L.¹⁵²
Sp. Pl.: 456 (1753)
Blávængja
– by Babington (1871)

ROSACEAE Juss.
Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 334 (1789), nom. cons.
Rósaætt

▼ *Aphanes arvensis* L.¹⁵³
Sp. Pl.: 123 (1753)
Dvergastakkur
– *Alchemilla arvensis* (L.) Scop., Fl. Carn. ed. II. 1: 115 (1771)
– by Lauder Lindsay (1861)
– by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
– by Babington (1871)
– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Alchemilla alpina L.
Sp. Pl.: 123 (1753)
Ljónslappi

151 *V. sepium* is a non-native species of unknown age – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

152 *P. vulgaris* was recorded by some early authors. There are no specimens available to confirm these records.

153 *A. arvensis* was recorded by some early authors but never mentioned by some more recent botanists. There is no herbarium material available to verify its presence in Iceland.

Alchemilla faeroënsis (Lange) Buser

Ber. Schweiz. Bot. Ges. 4: 58 (1894)

Maríuvöttur

- *Alchemilla fissa* var. *faeroënsis* Lange, Nomencl. Fl. Danic.: 137 (1887)
- *Potentilla faeroënsis* (Lange) Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 2 (2012)
- *Alchemilla conjuncta* auct. non Bab. (1842)

Alchemilla filicaulis Buser

Bull. Herb. Boissier 1, App. 2: 22 (1893)

Maríustakkur

- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *filicaulis* (Buser) Murb., Bot. Not. 1895: 265 (1895)
- ? *Alchemilla minor* Huds., Fl. Angl. ed. I.: 59 et auct. (1762)

Alchemilla filicaulis Buser var. *filicaulis*
Alchemilla filicaulis var. *vestita* (Buser) H.J. Coste

Bull. Herb. Boissier 2 (app. 4): 7 (1894)

- *Alchemilla filicaulis* f. *vestita* Buser, Bull. Herb. Boissier 1 (app. 2): 23 (1893)
- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *vestita* (Buser) Murb., Bot. Not. 1895: 265 (1895)
- *Alchemilla vestita* (Buser) Raunk., Dansk Ekursionsfl., ed. 2: 145 (1906)
- *Alchemilla filicaulis* subsp. *vestita* (Buser) M.E. Bradshaw, Watsonia 5(5): 305 (1963)
- *Potentilla salmoniana* (Jaquet) Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 3 (2012)

 ► *Alchemilla glabra* Neygenf.¹⁵⁴

Ench. Bot.: 67 (1821)

Brekkumariustakkur

- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *glabra* O. Bolòs & Vigo, Butl. Inst. Catalana Hist. Nat. 38, Bot. 1: 68 (1974)
- *Alchemilla vulgaris* var. *alpestris* F.W. Schmidt, Fl. Boëm. 3: 88 (1794)
- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *alpestris* (F.W. Schmidt) Murb., Bot. Not. 1895: 266 (1895)
- *Alchemilla alpestris* (F.W. Schmidt) Opiz., Oekon.-Techn. Fl. Böhm. 2(1): 18 (1838)
- *Potentilla psilophylla* (Borbás) Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 3 (2012)

Alchemilla glomerulans Buser

Herb. Boissier 1, App. 2: 30 (1893)

Hnoðamaríustakkur

- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *glomerulans* (Buser) Murb., A.J. Melan Suomen kasvio: 346 (1906)
- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *glomerulans* (Buser) O. Bolòs & Vigo, Butl. Inst. Catalana Hist. Nat. 38, Bot. 1: 68 (1974)
- *Potentilla glomerulans* Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 3 (2012)

 ● *Alchemilla mollis* (Buser) Rothm.

Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 33: 347 (1934)

Garðamaríustakkur

- *Alchemilla acutiloba* var. *mollis* Buser., Bull. Herb. Boissier 4: 759 (1896)
- *Potentilla alchemollis* Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 3 (2012)

 ▼ *Alchemilla montana*¹⁵⁵

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Babington (1871)

154 *A. glabra* is a non-native species of unknown age (Wasowicz 2018).

155 There are no specimens available to confirm what taxon has been recorded by some early authors under the name *A. montana*.

● *Alchemilla subcrenata* Buser

Scrin. Fl. Select. 12: 285 (1893)

Engjamariústakkur

- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *subcrenata* (Buser) Murb., Bot. Not. 1895: 266 (1895)
- *Potentilla subcrenata* (Buser) Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 4 (2012)

Alchemilla wichurae (Buser) Stefánsson

Fl. Ísl. 135 (1901)

Silfurmaríústakkur

- *Alchemilla vulgaris* var. *wichurae* (Buser) Boivin, Naturaliste Canad. 94(5): 627 (1963)
- *Alchemilla connivens* var. *wichurae* Bus., Bull. Herb. Boissier 2: 110 (1894)
- *Alchemilla vulgaris* subsp. *wichurae* (Bus.) Gams, Ill. Fl. von Mitt. Eur.: 966 (1906)
- *Alchemilla wichurae* Buser, Bull. Herb. Boiss. 2: 110 (1894)
- *Potentilla wichurae* (Buser) Christenh. & Väre, Phytotaxa 57: 4 (2012)
- ? *Alchemilla acutidens* (Buser) Lind. fil., Acta Soc. Fenn. 37 (10): 111 (1909)

Comarum palustre L.

Sp. Pl.: 502 (1753)

Engjarós

- *Potentilla palustris* (L.) Scop., Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 1: 359 (1771)
- *Potentilla comarum* Nestl., Monogr. Potent.: 36 (1816)
- *Comarum arcticum* Gand., Bull. Soc. Bot. France 56: 533 (1909)
- *Comarum palustre* subsp. *arcticum* (Gand.) Tzvelev, Bot. Zhurn. 92: 898 (2007)
- *Comarum angustifolium* Raf., Fl. Tellur. 2: 56 (1836)
- *Comarum palustre* subsp. *angustifolium* (Raf.) Tzvelev, Bot. Zhurn. 92: 897 (2007)

○ *Dasiphora fruticosa* (L.) Rydb.

Monogr. N. Amer. Potentill.: 188 (1898)

Runnamura

- *Potentilla fruticosa* L., Sp. Pl.: 495 (1753)

Dryas octopetala L.

Sp. Pl.: 501 (1753)

Holtasóley

○ *Filipendula camschatica* (Pall.) Maxim.

Trudy Imp. S.-Peterburgsk. Bot. Sada 6: 284 (1879)

Risamjaðjurt

Filipendula ulmaria (L.) Maxim.

Trudy Imp. S.-Peterburgsk. Bot. Sada 6: 251 (1879)

Mjaðjurt

- *Spiraea ulmaria* L., Sp. Pl.: 490 (1753)
- *Spiraea denudata* J. Presl & C. Presl, Fl. Cech.: 101 (1819)
- *Filipendula ulmaria* var. *denudata* (J. Presl & C. Presl) Maxim., Trudy Imp. S.-Peterburgsk. Bot. Sada 6: 252 (1879)
- *Filipendula denudata* (J. Presl & C. Presl) Fritsch, Verh. K.K. Zool.-Bot. Ges. Wien 39: 591 (1889)
- *Filipendula ulmaria* subsp. *denudata* (J. Presl & C. Presl) Hayek, Fl. Steiermark 1: 872 (1909)

○ *Fragaria moschata* Duchesne¹⁵⁶

Hist. Nat. Frais.: 145 (1766)

Moskusjarðarber

***Fragaria vesca* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 494 (1753)

Jarðarber

▼ *Fragaria viridis* Duchesne

Hist. Nat. Frais. 135 (1766)

Brekkujarðarber

– *Fragaria collina* Ehrh., Beitr. Naturk. 7: 26 (1792)

– by Lauder Lindsay (1861)

– by Babington (1871)

– by Grønlund (1881)

– by Stefánsson (1901)

– rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Geum* × *heldreichii* hort. ex Bergmans

Vaste Pl. Rotsheesters 245 (1924)

Skrúðdalafífill

○ *Geum macrophyllum* Willd.

Enum. Pl.: 557 (1809)

Skógdalafífil

***Geum rivale* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 501 (1753)

Fjalldalafífill

– *Geum rivale* subsp. *islandicum* Löve & Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 53 (1961)

○ *Geum sudeticum* Tausch

Hort. Canal. Enum.: 90 (1823)

Blikdalafífill

○ *Malus pumila* Mill.

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: no. 3 (1768)

Eplatré

– *Malus domestica* Borkh., Theor.-prak. Hand. Forstbot. Forsttech.: 1272 (1803) nom. illeg.,
nom. superfl. for *M. communis* Desf. (1798)

¹⁵⁶ For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

Potentilla anserina L.

Sp. Pl.: 495 (1753)

- *Argentina anserina* (L.) Rydb., Monogr. N. Amer. Potentill.: 159 (1898)

Potentilla anserina L. subsp. **anserina**

Tágamura

Potentilla anserina subsp. **groenlandica** Tratt.

Rosac. Monogr. 4: 13 (1824)

Skeljamura

- *Potentilla egedii* var. *groenlandica* (Tratt.) Polunin, Rhodora 41: 40 (1939)
- *Argentina anserina* subsp. *groenlandica* (Tratt.) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 300 (1970)
- *Potentilla egedii* Wormsk., Fl. Dan. 9, 27: 5, t. 1578 (1818)
- *Argentina egedii* (Wormsk.) Rydb., Monogr. N. Amer. Potentill.: 158 (1898)
- *Potentilla anserina* subsp. *egedii* (Wormsk.) Hiitonen, Suom. Kasvio: 449 (1933)
- *Argentina anserina* subsp. *egedii* (Wormsk.) Á. Löve & Ritchie, Canad. J. Bot. 44: 435 (1966)

▼ *Potentilla argentea* L.¹⁵⁷

Sp. Pl. 497 (1753)

Silfurmura

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Potentilla crantzii (Crantz) Beck ex Fritsch

Excursionsfl. Oesterreich: 295 (1897)

Gullmura

- *Fragaria crantzii* Crantz, Inst. Rei Herb. 2: 178 (1766)
- *Potentilla scandica* Soják, Preslia 57: 264 (1985)
- ? *Potentilla maculata* sensu Grønlund (1881), non Pourr. (1788)¹⁵⁸
- *Potentilla alpestris* Hall. fil., Ser. Mus. Helvet. 1: 53 (1818)
- *Potentilla verna* sensu Stefánsson (1901), non L. (1753)

● *Potentilla erecta* (L.) Räuschel¹⁵⁹

Nomencl. Bot. ed. 3: 152 (1797)

Blóðmura

- *Tormentilla erecta* L., Sp. Pl.: 500 (1753)
- *Fragaria tormentilla* Crantz, ASTirp. Austr. ed. I. fasc. 2: 23 (1763)
- *Tormentilla erecta* (Cr.) Neck., Act. Acad. Theod. Palat. 2: 491 (1770)

○ *Potentilla norvegica* L.

Sp. Pl.: 499 (1753)

Noregsmura

- *Potentilla monspeliensis* L., Sp. Pl.: 499 (1753)

○ *Prunus padus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 473 (1753)

Heggur

- *Padus avium* Mill., Gard. Dict., ed. 8: no. 1 (1768)

157 There are no collections available to confirm the presence of *P. argentea* in Iceland.

158 Grønlund (1881) used the name *Potentilla maculata* to describe plants known currently under the name of *Potentilla crantzii*. It is, however, unclear whether these two names are synonymous.

159 The status of *Potentilla erecta* is not clear. It seems that it is an (old?) adventive. Elven et al. (2011) treat the species as native to Iceland, which is very questionable. Here, we follow the view of Löve (1970), Kristinsson (2008) and Wasowicz et al. (2013) and treat the species as an established adventive.

○ *Rosa acicularis* Lindl.¹⁶⁰

Ros. Monogr. 44 (1820)

Heiðarós

Rosa dumalis Bechst.¹⁶¹

Forstbot. ed. 5.: 582 (1843)

Glitrós

- *Rosa glauca* Vill. ex Loisel., Desv. Journ. Bot. 2: 336 (1809) non Pourr.
- *Rosa vosagiaca* Desportes, Ros. Gall.: 88 (1828)
- *Rosa afzeliana* Fr., Fl. Halland.: 87 (1827)
- *Rosa afzeliana* subsp. *vosagiaca* (Desportes) R. Keller & Gams, Ill. Fl. Mitt.Eur.: 1035 f. 1230 a-e (1923)
- *Rosa canina* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Berberis vulgaris* auct. non L. (1753)

○ *Rosa majalis* Herrm.

De Rosa: 8 (1762)

Kanelrós

Rosa spinosissima L.

Sp. Pl.: 491 (1753)

Þyrnirós

- *Rosa pimpinellifolia* L., Syst. Nat.: 1062 (1759)
- *Rosa tackholmii* Hurst, Z. Indukt. Abstammungs- Vererbungsbl. Suppl.-Band 2: 890 (1928)
- ? *Rosa hibernica* sensu Hooker (1811)
- ? *Rosa villosa* var. *hibernica* sensu Lauder Lindsay (1861)

○ *Rosa rugosa* Thunb.

Fl. Jap.: 213 (1784)

Ígulrós

○ *Rubus idaeus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 492 (1753)

Hindber

Rubus saxatilis L.

Sp. Pl.: 494 (1753)

Hrútaber

○ *Rubus spectabilis* Pursh

Fl. Amer. Sept. 1: 348 (1814)

Laxaber

● *Sanguisorba alpina* Bunge

Fl. Altaic. 1: 142 (1829)

Höskollur

- *Sanguisorba linostemon* Hand.-Mazz., Österr. Bot. Z. 87: 121–122 (1938)

160 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

161 *R. dumalis* is an interesting species with a very limited distribution. It was found in 1756 growing in a birch forest south of Vatnajökull glacier. Here, the species is accepted as native, but more research is needed to elucidate its origin.

○ *Sanguisorba canadensis* L.

Sp. Pl. 117 (1753)

Kanadakollur

***Sanguisorba officinalis* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 116 (1753)

Blóðkollur

– *Sanguisorba polygama* F. Nyl., Spic. Pl. Fenn. 1: 19 (1843)

– *Poterium officinale* (L.) Benth. & Hook. fil. ex Hemsl. & Forb., Journ. L. Soc. 23: 247 (1887)

***Sibbaldia procumbens* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 284 (1753)

Fjallasmári

○ *Sorbaria sorbifolia* (L.) A. Braun

Fl. Brandenb. 1: 177 (1864)

Reyniblaðka

***Sorbus aucuparia* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 477 (1753)

– *Pyrus aucuparia* (L.) Gaertn., Fruct. Sem. Pl. 2(1): 45 (1790)

– *Pyrus aucuparia* (L.) Ehrh., Beitr. Naturk. (Ehrhart) 6: 94 (1791)

***Sorbus aucuparia* L. subsp. *aucuparia*¹⁶²**

Reynir

– *Sorbus aucuparia* subsp. *glabrata* sensu Löve (1983), non Hedl., Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.- Akad. Handl. 35(1): 45 (1901)

○ *Sorbus mougeotii* Godr. & Soyer-Willem.

Bull. Soc. Bot. Fr. 5: 447 (1858)

Alpareynir

○ *Spiraea salicifolia* L.

Sp. Pl.: 489 (1753)

Víðikvistur

○ *Spiraea* × *billardii* Hérincq

(*S. alba* × *S. douglasii*)

Úlfakvistur

RHAMNACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 376 (1789), nom. cons.

Hrökkviðarætt

▼ *Rhamnus cathartica* L.¹⁶³

Sp. Pl.: 193 (1753)

Geitastafur

– by Babington (1871)

– rejected by Gröntved (1942)

¹⁶² Some authors (e.g. Hulten and Fries 1986) classified Icelandic material as *Sorbus aucuparia* subsp. *glabrata* (Wimm. & Grab.) Hayek. It is clear, however, that Icelandic plants conform to subsp. *aucuparia*.

¹⁶³ *R. cathartica* has been reported just once from Iceland and most probably by mistake.

CANNABACEAE Martinov

Tekhno-Bot. Slovar: 99 (1820), nom. cons.

Hampætt

○ *Cannabis sativa* L.

Sp. Pl. 1027 1753.

Hampjurt

URTICACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 400 (1789), nom. cons.

Netluætt

● *Urtica dioica* L.

Sp. Pl.: 984 (1753)

Brenninetla

◆ *Urtica urens* L.¹⁶⁴

Sp. Pl. 984 (1753)

Smánetla

BETULACEAE Gray

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 222, 243 (1822), nom. cons.

Bjarkætt

Alnus alnobetula (Ehrh.) K.Koch

Dendrologie 2(1): 625

● *Alnus alnobetula* subsp. *sinuata* (Regel) Raus

Willdenowia 41: 129 (2011)

Sitkaölmur

– *Alnus sinuata* (Regel) Rydb., Bull. Torrey Bot. Club 24: 190 (1897)– *Alnus viridis* subsp. *sinuata* (Regel) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Univ. Colorado Stud., Ser. Bibliogr. 17: 20 (1965)◇ *Alnus incana* subsp. *kolaënsis* (N.I. Orlova) Á. Löve & D. Löve

Sp. Pl.: 1021 (1753)

Gráölmur

Betula nana L.

Sp. Pl.: 983 (1753)

Betula nana L. subsp. ***nana***

Fjalldrapi

¹⁶⁴ *U. urens* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

Betula pubescens Ehrh.

Beitr. Naturk. 6: 98 (1791)

- *Betula alba* L., Sp. Pl.: 982 (1753), nom. rej.
 - *Betula odorata* Bechst., Arch. Bot. (Leipzig) 2: 73 (1799)
 - *Betula glutinosa* Wallr., Sched. Crit.: 497 (1822)
 - ? *Betula subalpina* Laest., Bot. Not.: 110 (1857)
- Betula pubescens*** subsp. ***tortuosa*** (Ledeb.) Nyman¹⁶⁵
Consp. Fl. Eur. 3: 672 (1881)
Birki
- *Betula tortuosa* Ledeb., Fl. Ross. 3, 2: 652 (1850)

CELASTRACEAE R. Br.

Voy. Terra Austral. 2: 554 (1814), nom. cons.

Beinviðarætt

Parnassia palustris L.

Sp. Pl.: 273 (1753)

Parnassia palustris L. subsp. ***palustris***

Mýrasóley

- *Parnassia palustris* var. *tenuis* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 74 (1812)
- *Parnassia obtusiflora* Rupr., Fl. Samojed. Cisural.: 23 (1845)
- *Parnassia palustris* subsp. *obtusiflora* (Rupr.) D.A. Webb, Feddes Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 64: 25 (1961)

OXALIDACEAE R. Br.

Narr. Exped. Zaire: 433 (1818), nom. cons.

Súrsmæruætt

Oxalis acetosella L.

Sp. Pl.: 433 (1753)

Súrsmæra

○ *Oxalis corniculata* L.

Sp. Pl.: 435 (1753)

Hornsmæra

HYPERICACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 254 (1789), nom. cons.

Gullrunnaætt

○ *Hypericum maculatum* Crantz

Stirp. Austr. Fasc. 2: 64 (1763)

Flekkjagullrunni

○ *Hypericum perforatum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 785 (1753)

Jóhannesarjurt (Doppugullrunni)

165 This taxon has been interpreted as a hybrid, product from introgression of the diploid *Betula nana* into the tetraploid *B. pubescens* (subsp. *pubescens*) through the fertile hybrid (Elven et al. 2011). Differentiation between the plants from the western and eastern part of Iceland is evident and supported by both morphological (Elven et al. 2011) and genetic data (Thórsson et al. 2010).

VIOLACEAE Batsch

Tab. Affin. Regni Veg.: 57 (1802), nom. cons.

Fjóluætt

○ *Viola arvensis* Murray

Prodr. Stirp. Gott.: 73 (1770)

Arfafjóra

Viola canina L.¹⁶⁶

Sp. Pl.: 935 (1753)

Týsfjóra (Urðafjóra)

- *Viola canina* subsp. *montana* Hartm., Bot. Not. 1841: 82 (1841)
- *Viola nemoralis* Kütz., Linnaea 7: 46 (1832)
- *Viola canina* subsp. *nemoralis* (Kütz.) Elven, Norsk flora: 549 (2005), nom. illeg.
- *Viola montana* auct. non L., Sp. Pl.: 935 (1753)
- ? *Viola ericetorum* auct. non Schrad. ex Link (1821)
- ? *Viola sylvatica* sensu Grønlund (1881)

Viola epipsila Ledeb.¹⁶⁷

Index Sem. Hort. Dorpat.: 5 (1820)

Viola epipsila subsp. ***repens*** (Turcz. ex Trautv. & C.A. Mey.) W. Becker

Bot. Centralbl. 34, 2: 406 (1917)

Birkifjóra

- *Viola repens* Turcz. ex Trautv. & C.A. Mey. in Middend., Reise Sibir. 1, 2, 2: 18 (1851), non Schwein (1822)
- *Viola epipsiloides* Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 516 (1976)

Viola palustris L.

Sp. Pl.: 934 (1753)

Viola palustris L. subsp. ***palustris***

Mýrfjóra

Viola riviniana Rchb.

Iconogr. Bot. Pl. Crit. 1: 81 (1823)

Skógfjóra

166 Two different morphological types within *V. canina* have been recognised from Iceland. Type 1 is ascending and has middle stem leaves with stipules less than $\frac{1}{2}$ (or by $\frac{1}{3}$) as long as the petiole. Leaf blade in this form is less than twice as long as wide, has concave margins and cordate base. Type 2 is erect and has middle stem leaves with stipules more than $\frac{1}{3}$ (or by $\frac{1}{2}$) as long as the petiole. Leaf blades are about twice as long as wide or longer, with straight to convex margins and subtruncate base (Marcussen and Karlsson 2010). Several studies have been carried out to explain this pattern of variation. Bergdolt (1932) showed that many characters considered diagnostic for these two types (often treated as separate subspecies) may be induced by habitat factors. This fact, as well as other findings described in detail in Marcussen and Karlsson (2010) lead to a conclusion that maintaining subspecies within *V. canina* has no biological justification.

167 Marcussen and Karlsson (2010) recognised two different morphological types of *V. epipsila* from Scandinavia: northern and southern type. They included both types in *V. epipsila* and classified Icelandic material under this name. Elven et al. (2011) proposed another view on the geographically structured variation within the species. They argue that according to Russian botanists a complex of three species is present in the north, namely: *Viola epipsila* s.str, *Viola epipsiloides* A. Löve & D. Löve (*Viola repens* Turcz. ex Trautv. & C.A. Mey., non Schwein) and *Viola palustroides* (W. Beck.) N.N. Tsvelev. Elven et al. (2011) argue that the southern type recognised by Marcussen and Karlsson (2010) correspond to *V. epipsila* s.str, while the northern type correspond to *Viola repens*. This would mean that *Viola epipsila* s.str. is not present in Iceland. This point of view is accepted here.

- ▼ *Viola rupestris* F. W. Schmidt¹⁶⁸
Abh. Böhm. Ges. Wiss. ser. 2, 1: 60 (1791)
Sandfjóra
- by Gröntved (1942)

- Viola tricolor* L.**
Sp. Pl.: 935 (1753)
Viola tricolor* L. subsp. *tricolor
Þrenningarfjóra

SALICACEAE Mirb.

Elém. Physiol. Vég. Bot. 2: 905 (1815), nom. cons.
Víðisætt

- Populus tremula* L.**¹⁶⁹
Sp. Pl.: 1034 (1753)
Blæösp

- *Populus trichocarpa* Torr. & A. Gray ex Hook.
Icon. Pl. 9: t. 878 (1852)
Balsamösp (Alaskaösp)
- *Populus balsamifera* subsp. *trichocarpa* (Torr. & A. Gray ex Hook.) Brayshaw, Canad. Field-Naturalist 79: 95 (1965)

- ◇ *Populus* × *wettsteinii* Hämet-Ahti
(*P. tremula* × *P. tremuloides*)
Memoranda Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 65:8 (1989)
Blæsparbróðir

- *Salix alaxensis* (Andersson) Coville
Proc. Wash. Acad. Sci. 2: 280 (1900)
Alaskavíðir
- *Salix speciosa* var. *alaxensis* Andersson in DC., Prodr. 16, 2: 275 (1868)

- Salix arctica* Pall.**¹⁷⁰
Fl. Ross. 1, 2: 86 (1789)
Fjallavíðir
- *Salix glauca* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Salix callicarpaea* auct. non Trautv. (1832)
- *Salix glauca* subsp. *callicarpaea* auct. non. Böcher (1952)
- *Salix cordifolia* sensu Löve (1983), non Pursh (1813)

168 *V. rupestris* was recorded by Gröntved (1942), who cites collection by Hornemann deposited in C. The species, however, has never been found again. It is hard to say whether the species has been misidentified or recorded due to a mistake in labelling plant material.

169 *P. tremula* is a very rare and probably native species, found only in N and E Iceland. Otherwise present in gardens and sometimes as a garden escape.

170 Plant material from Iceland classified nowadays as *S. arctica* was in the past referred to as *Salix glauca* L. Sp. Pl. 1029 (1753) by Grönlund (1881); Stefánsson (1901); Gröntved (1942); Löve (1945) and Stefánsson (1948). Plants growing in Iceland, however, are different from *S. glauca* growing in Scandinavia and N. America. As their morphology agree better with *S. arctica* they were referred to that species in more recent works (Pálsson 2000, Kristinsson 2008, Elven et al. 2011).

▼ *Salix arctophila* Cockerell ex Heller¹⁷¹

Cat. N. Amer. Pl., ed. 3: 89 (1910)

Grænlandsvíðir

- by Jónsson (1896) as *Salix groenlandica*
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

 ▼ *Salix arenaria* L.¹⁷²

Sp. Pl.: 1019 (1753)

Sandvíðir

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

 ● *Salix borealis* Fr.

Bot. Not. 1840: 193 (1840)

Viðja

- *Salix myrsinifolia* subsp. *borealis* (Fr.) Hyl., Nordisk Kärleväxtfl. 2: 387 (1966)
- *Salix nigricans* var. *borealis* Fr., Bot. Not. 1840: 193 (1840)
- *Salix borealis* (Fr.) Nasarow, Fl. URSS 5: 87 (1936)

 ● *Salix caprea* (Andersson) Coville¹⁷³

Sp. Pl. 1020 (1753)

Selja

 ▼ *Salix cinerea* L.¹⁷⁴

Sp. Pl.: 1021 (1753)

Gráselja

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

 ▼ *Salix glabra* Scop.¹⁷⁵

Fl. Carn. ed. 2, 2: 255 (1772)

Snoðvíðir

- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Salix herbacea* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1018 (1753)

Grásvíðir

 ◇ *Salix hookeriana* Barratt ex Hook.

Fl. Bor.-Amer. 2: 145 (1839)

Jörfavíðir

171 *S. arctophila* was reported just once by Jónsson (1896) and there are no specimens to confirm this single report.

172 Records of *Salix arenaria* from Iceland should be treated as misidentifications.

173 *S. caprea* is present in some old lists: König and Müller (1770), Baring-Gould (1863) and Babington (1871), but the earliest confirmed records are from 1948 (Wasowicz et al. 2013) and suggest that *S. caprea* is a naturalized alien in Iceland. Earlier records are probably due to misidentification.

174 There is no evidence available to confirm the presence of *Salix cinerea* from Iceland.

175 Babington (1871) mentioned *S. glabra* from Iceland citing Hjaltalín (1830), there is no evidence to confirm these records.

***Salix lanata* L.**

Sp. Pl. 1019 (1753)

Loðvíðir

- *Salix chrysanthos* Vahl, Fl. Dan, t. 1057 (1792)

▼ *Salix lapponum* L.¹⁷⁶

Sp. Pl.: 1019 (1753)

Lappavíðir

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Bennett (1886)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

◇ *Salix lasiandra* Fr.

Pl. Hartw. 335 (1857)

Lensuvíðir

◇ *Salix myrsinites* L.

Sp. Pl.: 1018 (1753)

Myrtuvíðir

▼ *Salix myrtilloides* L.¹⁷⁷

Sp. Pl.: 1019 (1753)

Lyngvíðir

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

◇ *Salix pentandra* L.¹⁷⁸

Sp. Pl.: 1016 (1753)

Gljávíðir

***Salix phylicifolia* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 1016 (1753)

Gulvíðir

- *Salix arbuscula* sensu Grønlund (1881) non L. (1753)

▼ *Salix purpurea* L.¹⁷⁹

Sp. Pl.: 1017 (1753)

Purpuravíðir

- by Mohr (1786)
- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

176 There is no evidence to confirm the presence of *Salix lapponum* from Iceland.

177 There is no evidence (specimens) to confirm *Salix myrtilloides* from Iceland.

178 Early records of *Salix pentandra* in Iceland König and Müller (1770) and Babington (1871) are dubious and can be treated as misidentification.

179 There is no evidence (specimens) to confirm *Salix purpurea* from Iceland.

▼ *Salix repens* L.¹⁸⁰

Sp. Pl.: 1020 (1753)

Skriðvíðir

- by Mohr (1786) as *Salix fusca*
- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Hjaltalín (1830) as *Salix fusca*
- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)
- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862) as *Salix argentea*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

 ▼ *Salix reticulata* L.¹⁸¹

Sp. Pl.: 1018-1019 (1753)

Netvíðir

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

 ◇ *Salix sitchensis* Sanson ex Bong.

Mém. Acad. Imp. Sci. Saint.-Pétersbourg, Sér. 6, Sci. Math. 2: 162 (1833)

Sitkavíðir

 ◇ *Salix viminalis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 1021 (1753)

Körfuvíðir

EUPHORBIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 384 (1789), nom. cons.

Mjólkurjurtaætt

 ○ *Euphorbia cyparissias* L.

Sp. Pl.: 461 (1753)

Sedrusmjólk

 ▼ *Euphorbia peplus* L.¹⁸²

Sp. Pl.: 456 (1753)

Garðamjólk

- by Babington (1871)

LINACEAE DC. ex Perleb

Vers. Arzneikr. Pfl.: 107 (1818), nom. cons.

Línætt

Linum catharticum L.

Sp. Pl.: 281 (1753)

Villilín

- *Cathartolinum catharticum* (L.) Small, N. Amer. Fl. 25(1): 74 (1907)
- *Cathartolinum catharticum* subsp. *suecicum* (Hayek) Á. Löve, Phytologia 50(3): 172 (1982)

180 There is no evidence (specimens) to confirm *Salix repens* from Iceland.

181 There is no evidence (specimens) to confirm *Salix reticulata* from Iceland.

182 *E. peplus* was reported just once in the 19th century (no specimens available), and never subsequently observed in Iceland.

- *Linum usitatissimum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 277 (1753)

Spunalín

GERANIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 268 (1789), nom. cons.

Blágresisætt

- *Erodium cicutarium* (L.) L'Hér. ex Aiton

Hort. Kew. 2: 414 (1789)

Hegranef

- *Geranium* × *magnificum* Hyl.

Kóngablágresi

- *Geranium molle* L.

Sp. Pl.: 682 (1753)

Loðblágresi

- ▼ *Geranium phaeum* L.¹⁸³

Sp. Pl.: 681 (1753)

Brúngresi

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Geranium montanum* J. König ex O. Müll.

- by Hjaltalín (1830) as *Geranium fuscum* L.

- by Lauder Lindsay (1861) as *Geranium phaeum* var. *fuscum* L.

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

- *Geranium pratense* L.

Sp. Pl.: 681 (1753)

Garðablágresi

- *Geranium pusillum* L.

Syst. Nat. (ed. 10) 2: 1144 (1759)

Dvergblágresi

- *Geranium robertianum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 681 (1753)

Rauðgresi

Geranium sylvaticum L.

Sp. Pl.: 681 (1753)

- *Geranium fastigiatum* (Fr.) Gliemann, Geogr. Besch. Island: 145 (1824)

Geranium sylvaticum L. subsp. ***sylvaticum***

Blágresi

183 *G. phaeum* is mentioned by some of the early authors, but its presence as a native element of Icelandic flora is unlikely. It might have been recorded as an old adventive, but there are no specimens available to confirm the species as casual alien.

ONAGRACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 317 (1789), nom. cons.

Eyrarósarætt

Chamerion angustifolium (L.) Holub

Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 7: 86 (1972)

- *Epilobium angustifolium* L., Sp. Pl.: 347 (1753)
- *Chamaenerion angustifolium* (L.) Scop., Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 1: 271 (1771), nom. illeg.

Chamerion angustifolium (L.) Holub subsp. ***angustifolium***

Sigurskúfur

- ? *Chamerion angustifolium* subsp. *intermedium* auct. non Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 301 (1970)

Chamerion latifolium (L.) Holub

Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 7: 86 (1972)

Eyrarrós

- *Epilobium latifolium* L., Sp. Pl.: 347 (1753)
- *Chamaenerion latifolium* (L.) Sweet, Hort. Brit., ed. 2: 198 (1830)
- *Chamaenerion subdentatum* Rydb., Fl. Rocky Mts.: 585 (1917)
- *Chamerion subdentatum* (Rydb.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 516 (1976)
- *Epilobium montanum* auct. non L. (1753)
- ? *Chamaenerion angustifolium* subsp. *intermedium* auct. non Á. Löve (1970)

Epilobium alsinifolium Vill.

Prosp. Hist. Pl. Dauphiné: 45 (1779)

Lindadúnurt

- *Epilobium organifolium* Lam., Encycl. 2: 376 (1786)

Epilobium anagallidifolium Lam.

Encycl. 2: 376 (1786)

Fjalladúnurt

Epilobium ciliatum Raf.

Med. Repos., ser. 2, 5: 361 (1808)

- *Epilobium ciliatum* Raf. subsp. *ciliatum*

Vætudúnurt

- *Epilobium adenocaulon* Hausskn., Oesterr. Bot. Z. 29: 119 (1879)
- *Epilobium glandulosum* var. *adenocaulon* (Hausskn.) Fernald, Rhodora 20: 35 (1918)
- *Epilobium americanum* Hausskn., Oesterr. Bot. Z. 29: 118 (1879)
- *Epilobium watsonii* auct.

- *Epilobium ciliatum* subsp. *glandulosum* (Lehm.) Hoch & P.H. Raven, Kirtildúnurt

Ann. Missouri Bot. Gard. 64: 136 (1977)

- *Epilobium glandulosum* Lehm., Nov. Stirp. Pug. 2: 14 (1830)

Epilobium collinum C.C. Gmel.

Fl. Bad. 4: 265 (1826)

Klappadúnurt

▼ *Epilobium dodonaei* Vill.¹⁸⁴

Prosp. Hist. Pl. Dauphine: 45 (1779)

- *Epilobium angustissimum* Weber, Pl. Minus Cogn. Dec.: 3 (1784)
- *Epilobium rosmarinifolium* Haenke, Collectanea 2: 50 (1789)
- by Hjaltalín (1830)
- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)
- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)

▼ *Epilobium fleischeri* Hochst.¹⁸⁵

Flora (Regensburg) 9: 85 (1826)

- by Hjaltalín (1830) as *Epilobium angustissimum*
- by Lauder Lindsay (1861) as *Epilobium rosmarinifolium*
- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862) as *Epilobium angustissimum*
- by Babington (1871) as *Epilobium fleischeri*
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Epilobium hornemannii Rchb.

Iconogr. Bot. Pl. Crit. 2: 73, t. 180 (1824)

Epilobium hornemannii Rchb. subsp. ***hornemannii***

Heiðadúnurt

Epilobium lactiflorum Hausskn.

Oesterr. Bot. Z. 29: 89 (1879)

Ljósadúnurt

- *Epilobium hornemannii* var. *lactiflorum* (Hausskn.) D. Löve, Taxon 17: 89 (1968)
- *Epilobium alpinum* L., Sp. Pl.: 348 (1753), nom. rej.

○ *Epilobium montanum* L.¹⁸⁶

Sp. Pl.: 348 (1753)

Runnadúnurt

Epilobium palustre L.

Sp. Pl.: 348 (1753)

Mýradúnurt

- *Epilobium palustre* var. *labradoricum* Hausskn., Monogr. Epilobium: 131 (1884)
- *Epilobium tundrarum* Sam., Bot. Not. 1922: 264 (1922)
- ? *Epilobium virgatum* sensu Babington (1850)

▼ *Epilobium tetragonum* L.¹⁸⁷

Sp. Pl.: 348 (1753)

Stokkadúnurt

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

184 *E. dodonaei* was mentioned only by some early authors, there is no evidence to confirm its presence in Iceland.

185 *E. fleischeri* is present only in some older lists, there are no evidence available to confirm its presence in Iceland.

186 *E. montanum* is present in almost all older lists. This is probably due to misapplication of the name to specimens that are currently known as *Chamerion latifolium*. First confirmed records of *E. montanum* in Iceland come from the 20th century (Wasowicz et al. 2013).

187 Included in all lists of early authors. There are no specimens available to confirm its presence in Iceland.

MALVACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 271 (1789), nom. cons.

Stokkrósaætt

○ *Malva pusilla* Sm.

Engl. Bot. 4: pl. 241 (1795)

Dvergastokkrós (Hænsnarós)

– *Malva borealis* Wallr., Liljebl., Sv. Flora ed. 3: 374 (1816)○ *Malva verticillata* L.

Sp. Pl.: 689 (1753)

Kransstokkrós (Kransmalva)

– *Malva crispa* (L.) L., Syst. Nat. ed. 10: 1147 (1759)**LIMNANTHACEAE** R. Br.

London Edinburgh Philos. Mag. & J. Sci. 3: 71 (1833), nom. cons.

Deigjurtætt

○ *Limnanthes douglasii* R. Br.

London Edinburgh Philos. Mag. & J. Sci. 3: 71 (1833)

Eggjablóm

BRASSICACEAE Burnett (= Cruciferae Juss. nom. cons.)

Outlines Bot. (Burnett) 854: 1093, 1123 (1835), nom. cons.

Krossblómaætt

○ *Alliaria petiolata* (M.Bieb.) Cavara & Grande

Bull. Orto Bot. Regia Univ. Napoli 3: 418 (1913)

Laukkarsi

Arabidopsis petraea (L.) V.I. Dorof.

Turczaninowia 5: 35. 2002

Melablóm

– *Cardamine petraea* L., Sp. Pl.: 654 (1753)– *Arabis petraea* (L.) Lam., Encycl. 1: 221 (1783)– *Cardamine faeroensis* Hornem., Fl. Dan. t. 1392 (1810)– *Cardaminopsis petraea* (L.) Hiitonen in Hyl., Förteckn. Skand. Växt., ed. 3: 62 (1941)– *Arabidopsis lyrata* subsp. *petraea* (L.) O’Kane & Al-Shehbaz, Novon 7: 326 (1997)– *Arabidopsis petraea* (L.) Kolnik & Marhold, Willdenowia 33: 70 (2003), nom. superfl.– *Cardaminopsis hispida* (L.) Hayek, Fl. Steiermark 1: 478 (1908)○ *Arabidopsis thaliana* (L.) Heynh.¹⁸⁸

G. Fl. Sachsen 1: 538 (1842)

Vormelablóm

Arabis alpina L.

Sp. Pl.: 664 (1753)

Skriðnablóm

– *Brassica alpina* auct. non L. (1753)

188 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

- *Armoracia rusticana* P. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb.

Oekon. Fl. Wetterau 2: 426 (1800)

Piparrót

- *Barbarea stricta* Andr.

Enum. Pl.: 72 (1822)

Hlíðableikja

- *Barbarea vulgaris* W.T. Aiton¹⁸⁹

Hort. Kew., ed. 2, 4: 109 (1812)

Garðableikja

- *Erysimum barbarea* L., Sp. Pl.: 660 (1753)
- *Erysimum arcuatum* Opiz. ex J. Presl & C. Presl, Fl. Cech.: 138 (1819)
- *Barbarea arcuata* (Opiz. ex J. Presl & C. Presl) Rchb., Flora 5: 296 (1822)
- *Barbarea vulgaris* var. *arcuata* (Opiz ex J. Presl & C. Presl) Fr., Novit. Fl. Svec. Alt.: 205 (1828)

- *Berteroa incana* (L.) DC.

Syst. Nat. 2: 291 (1821)

Hvítduðra

- *Alyssum incanum* L., Sp. Pl.: 650 (1753)

Brassica napus L.

Sp. Pl.: 666 (1753)

- *Brassica napus* L. subsp. *napus*

Repja

Sp. Pl.: 666 (1753)

- *Brassica napus* ?*oleifera* DC., Syst. Nat. (Candolle) 2: 592 (1821)
- *Brassica napus* subsp. *oleifera* (DC.) Metzg., Syst. Besch. Kohllart.: 40 (1833)
- *Brassica napus* subsp. *rapifera* Metzg. ex Sinskaya

Gulrófa

Trudy Prikl. Bot. 19(3): 262 (1928)

- *Brassica napus* subsp. *rapifera* Metzg., Syst. Besch. Kohllart.: 46 (1833)
- *Brassica napus* var. *napobrassica* (L.) Rchb., J.C. Handb. Gewächsk., ed. 3, 2: 1220 (1883)

- *Brassica oleracea* L.

Sp. Pl.: 667 (1753)

Garðakál

Brassica rapa L.

Sp. Pl.: 666 (1753)

- *Brassica rapa* L. subsp. *rapa*

Næpa

- *Brassica rapa* subsp. *oleifera* (DC.) Metzg.

Arfanæpa

Syst. Besch. Kohllart.: 49–50 (1833)

- *Brassica campestris* L., Sp. Pl. 2: 666 (1753)
- *Brassica rapa* subsp. *campestris* (L.) A.R. Clapham, Fl. Brit. Isles: 153 (1952)

¹⁸⁹ *B. vulgaris* is an established adventive in Iceland. There are two races within the species "*vulgaris*" and "*arcuata*" (Icelandic: Akurbleikja). The latter one is predominant in Iceland, but more studies are needed before subspecific taxa can be accepted (Elven et al. 2011). Therefore here var. *arcuata* (Opiz ex J. Presl & C. Presl) Fr. is synonymized with *B. vulgaris*.

▼ *Braya glabella* subsp. *purpurascens* (R. Br.) Cody¹⁹⁰

Canad. Field-Naturalist 108: 93 (1994)

Fjallakál

- *Braya purpurascens* (R. Br.) Bunge ex Ledeb., Fl. Ross. 1: 195 (1841)
- by Löve (1970)

Cakile maritima Scop.

Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 2: 35 (1772)

Cakile maritima subsp. ***islandica*** (Gand.) Hyl. ex Elven

Nordic J. Bot. 16: 8 (1996)

Fjörukál

- *Cakile maritima* f. *islandica* Gand., Bull. Soc. Bot. France 47: 343 (1900)
- *Cakile edentula* subsp. *islandica* (Gand.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 52 (1961)
- *Cakile arctica* Pobed., Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk SSSR 15: 64 (1953)
- *Cakile lapponica* Pobed., Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk SSSR 19: 44 (1959)
- *Bunias cakile* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Cakile edentula* sensu Á. Löve & D. Löve (1947) et auct. non Hook. (1829)

○ *Camelina microcarpa* Andr. ex DC.

Syst. Nat. 2: 517 (1821)

Hárdoðra

- *Camelina sylvestris* Wallr., Sched. Crit. 1: 437 (1882)

○ *Camelina sativa* (L.) Crantz

Stirp. Austr. Fasc. 1: 17 (1762)

Akurdoðra

◆ *Capsella bursa-pastoris* (L.) Medik.¹⁹¹

Pfl.Gatt.: 85 (1792)

Hjartarfi

- *Thlaspi bursa-pastoris* L., Sp. Pl.: 647 (1753)

Cardamine bellidifolia L.

Sp. Pl.: 654 (1753)

Jöklaklukka

○ *Cardamine flexuosa* With.

Arr. Brit. Pl. ed. 3, 3: 578 (1796)

Kjarrtannrót (Kjarrklukka)

◆ *Cardamine hirsuta* L.¹⁹²

Sp. Pl.: 655 (1753)

Lambaklukka

- ? *Cardamine multicaulis* Hoppe ex Schur, Enum. Pl. Transsilv.: 47 (1866)

¹⁹⁰ Records of *Braya glabella* from Iceland belongs to improbable and discounted reports produced by Löve that are most probably fictitious (Elven et al. 2011).

¹⁹¹ *C. bursa-pastoris* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

¹⁹² *C. hirsuta* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

***Cardamine polemonioides* Rouy¹⁹³**

Fl. France 1: 234 (1893)

Hrafnaklukka

- *Cardamine pratensis* subsp. *polemonioides* (Rouy) auct.
- *Cardamine pratensis* var. *angustifolia* Hook., Fl. Bor.-Amer. 1: 45 (1829)
- *Cardamine pratensis* subsp. *angustifolia* (Hook.) O.E. Schulz, Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 32: 529 (1903)
- *Cardamine nymanii* Gand., Bull. Soc. Bot. France 72: 1043 (1926)
- *Cardamine pratensis* auct. non L. (1753)

***Cochlearia groenlandica* L.¹⁹⁴**

Sp. Pl.: 647 (1753)

Fjallaskarfakál

- *Cochlearia officinalis* subsp. *groenlandica* (L.) A.E. Porsild, Bull. Natl. Mus. Canada 146: 92 (1957)
- *Cochleariopsis groenlandica* (L.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 514 (1976)
- *Cochlearia fenestrata* R. Br., Voy. Explor. Baffin's Bay, App.: 143 (1819)
- *Cochlearia pyrenaica* sensu Löve (1985) non DC., Syst. Nat. 2: 365 (1821)

***Cochlearia islandica* Pobed.¹⁹⁵**

Novosti Sist. Vyssh. Rast. 5: 130 (1968)

Skarfakál

- *Cochlearia groenlandica* subsp. *islandica* (Pobed.) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 300 (1970)
- *Cochlearia officinalis* subsp. *islandica* (Pobed.) Nordal & Björå, comb. ined.
- *Cochlearia danica* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Cochlearia anglica* sensu Grønlund (1881) non L. (1759)

193 A combination *C. pratensis* subsp. *polemonioides* has frequently been applied to this taxon by different European authors. Here, we accept the view of Elven et al. (2011) that the taxon was originally described as a species and therefore the name *C. polemonioides* has priority. What is more, originally *C. polemonioides* was described from "Spitzbergen" (Norway), Novaya Zemlya (European Russia), and from Iceland (!). Warwick et al. (2016) in their Brassicaceae species checklist applied the name *C. nymanii*. It is difficult to say whether only one taxon from *C. pratensis* aggregate is present in Iceland. Elven and Solstad (unpubl.) have suggested also the presence of *C. pratensis* subsp. *paludosa* (Knaf) Čelak. in W and SW Iceland. The presence of subsp. *pratensis* can not be ruled out as an adventive in lawns and gardens.

194 Two morphologically distinct groups can be identified within *Cochlearia* in Iceland: alpine type and coastal type. It is clear that strong morphological differentiation and ecological separation exists between these two groups. Löve (1970) first classified both types as *Cochlearia groenlandica* L. subsp. *islandica* (Pobed.) Á. Löve but then alpine plants were classified as *Cochlearia pyrenaica* DC. (Löve 1983). He was wrong. Firstly, by using *Cochlearia islandica* Pobed. (described on the basis of a plant from the coastal type) as a basionym for the name applied to the alpine type. Secondly, by classifying alpine plants as *C. pyrenaica* DC. Recent studies (Olsen 2015) clearly showed that there is strong genetic differentiation between Icelandic plants and those from SW Europe (*C. aesturia* and *C. pyrenaica*). The same study (Olsen 2015) have also showed that alpine type is genetically and morphologically more similar to high-arctic populations of *Cochlearia groenlandica* in Svalbard than to the coastal type. It seems therefore appropriate and justified to treat the alpine type separately from the coastal type under the name *Cochlearia groenlandica* L. Icelandic specimens of this taxon seems to have a uniform chromosome number $2n=14$ (Olsen 2015).

195 Coastal *Cochlearia* morphotype is not uniform in terms of chromosome number and recent studies showed that plants with $2n=12$ and $2n=14$ do occur within coastal populations (Olsen 2015). These two different cytogenetic types, however, can not be separated morphologically. Pobedimova (1968) described a new taxon *Cochlearia islandica* Pobed. on the basis of plant material collected in coastal areas in NW Iceland (Kollafjarðarnes), emphasizing differences between Icelandic plants and other taxa within *Cochlearia*. Initially, Löve (1970) treated both Icelandic morphotypes as *Cochlearia groenlandica* L. subsp. *islandica* (Pobed.) Löve & Löve, but later (Löve 1983) were coastal plants classified in a separate genus: *Cochleariopsis groenlandica* subsp. *islandica* (Pobed.) Löve & Löve. The question then arises how Icelandic coastal plants should be treated? In general there are two options available. If we accept the assumption about the reproductive isolation between tetraploid *C. officinalis* ($2n=24$) and Icelandic coastal diploids ($2n=12$, $2n=14$) then it seems that Icelandic coastal morphotype cannot simply be included into *C. officinalis* as has been done by Kristinsson (2008), but it should be treated separately as a subspecies of *C. officinalis* [as suggested by Elven et al. (2011)], or as the species *C. islandica* described by Pobedimova (1968) from coastal region in NW Iceland. It seems that the latter option is the only available at the moment as there is no subspecific name validly published so far that could be applied for the Icelandic coastal *Cochlearia* morphotype.

- *Conringia orientalis* (L.) Dumort.
Fl. Belg.: 123 (1827)
Káljurt

- *Descurainia incana* (Bernh. ex Fisch. & C.A. Mey.) Dorn
Vasc. Pl. Wyoming: 296 (1988)
Grápefjurt

- *Descurainia sophia* (L.) Webb
Nat. Pflanzenfam. III, 2: 192 (1891)
pefjurt
– *Sisymbrium sophia* L., Sp. Pl.: 659 (1753)

- ▼ *Draba arctogena* (E. Ekman) E. Ekman¹⁹⁶
E. Ekman in Grøntved, Vasc. Pl. Arct. N. Amer.: 83 (1936)
Heiðavorblóm
– by Löve (1970) as *D. fladnizensis*
– by Kristinsson (2008)

- ▼ *Draba aizoides* L.¹⁹⁷
Mant. Pl.: 91 (1767)
Garðavorblóm
– by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
– by Baring-Gould (1863)
– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

- ▼ *Draba glabella* Pursh¹⁹⁸
Fl. Amer. Sept. 2: 434 (1813)
Túnvorblóm
– by Löve (1970)
– by Kristinsson (2008)

- Draba incana* L.**
Sp. Pl.: 643 (1753)
Grávorbólóm

- ▼ *Draba lactea* Adams¹⁹⁹
Mém. Soc. Imp. Naturalistes Moscou 5: 104 (1817)
Snoðvorblóm
– by Kristinsson (2008)

196 *Draba arctogena* was mentioned as present in Iceland by Kristinsson (2008), but it seems that this name was misapplied and that Icelandic specimens belong to one of two major morphs of *D. rupestris* present in N Europe.

197 There is absolutely no evidence, apart from two old records not supported by collections, to confirm the presence of *D. aizoides* in Iceland.

198 *Draba glabella* (*D. daurica*) was mentioned from Iceland by different authors. Recent revision carried out by R. Elven and H. H. Grundt on Icelandic herbaria have shown that almost all the herbarium sheets annotated as *D. glabella* were misidentified. Two remaining sheets containing very characteristic plants of *D. glabella* were collected by Áskell Löve in Smiðjuvík and Hrolleifsvík in Hornstrandir (Westen Fjords) and they both differ significantly from all Icelandic specimens of *Draba* (Elven et al. 2011). Löve vouchered also some other dubious species in the same area (Hornstrandir) and in the same year (i.e. in 1932). *Eriophorum russeolum* found in Hrolleifsvík, and *Poa arctica* found in Sleppir can be mentioned as examples. These species have been never confirmed from these places as well as they have never been found elsewhere in Iceland. This strange situation can be explained either by a massive confusion of the plant material or by a conscious fake (made in order to increase “probability” of the existence of glacial refugia in Iceland) (Elven et al. 2011).

199 Recent revision of plant material from Iceland showed that all specimens annotated as *Draba lactea* belong to the polymorphic taxon *Draba rupestris*.

▼ *Draba muralis* L.²⁰⁰

Sp. Pl.: 643 (1753)

Steinavorblóm

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Draba nivalis Lilj.

Utkast Sv. Fl.: 236 (1792)

Héluvorblóm

Draba oxycarpa Sommerf.

Mag. Naturvidensk. 11: 241 (1833)

Fjallavorblóm

- *Draba alpina* auct. non L. (1753)

Draba rupestris W.T. Aiton²⁰¹

Hort. Kew., ed. 2, 4: 91 (1812)

Hagavorblóm

- ? *Draba hirta* sensu Stefánsson (1901), non L. (1759)
- ? *Draba fladnizensis* auct. non Wulfen (1778)

Draba verna L.

Sp. Pl.: 642 (1753)

Vorperla

- *Erophila verna* (L.) Chevall., Fl. Gén. Env. Paris 2: 898 (1828)

○ *Erucastrum gallicum* (Willd.) O.E. Schulz

Bot. Jahrb. Syst. 54(119): 56 (1916)

Hundakál

○ *Erysimum cheiranthoides* L.

Sp. Pl.: 661 (1753)

Akurgyllir

○ *Erysimum repandum* L.

Demonstr. Pl.: 17 (1753)

Hafnagyllir

Erysimum strictum P. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb.

Oekon. Fl. Wetterau 2: 451 (1800)

Aronsvöndur

- *Erysimum hieraciifolium* sensu Grønlund (1881), non L. (1755)

200 *Draba muralis* was recorded only by König and Müller (1770) and subsequently copied by other authrs. There is no evidence to confirm the presence of the species from Iceland.

201 The name *Draba norvegica* Gunnerus, Fl. Norveg. 2: 106 (1772) has been applied to this species in recent decades. However, it is not possible to use Oeder's illustration in Flora Danica (the only original material available for *D. norvegica* according to Elven et al. (2011)) to assign the name to the plant that is currently named *D. norvegica* (see Elven et al. (2011) and discussion therein). For this reason the name *D. rupestris* W.T. Aiton was applied to the species by Elven et al. (2011) and here we follow this provisional solution. It should also be mentioned that the variation within *D. rupestris* is probably too large to be encompassed by one taxon.

- *Hesperis matronalis* L.
Sp. Pl.: 663 (1753)
Næturfjóra

- Hornungia alpina* (L.) O. Appel
Novon 7: 339 (1997)
 - *Hornungia alpina* (L.) O. Appel subsp. *alpina*
Snæbreiða
 - *Lepidium alpinum* L., Cent. Pl. II: 23 (1756)
 - *Pritzelago alpina* (L.) Kuntze, Revis. Gen. Pl. 1: 35 (1891)

- *Lepidium campestre* (L.) R. Br.
Hortus Kew. 4: 88 (1812)
Akurperla
 - *Thlaspi campestre* L., Sp. Pl.: 646–647 (1753)

- *Lepidium densiflorum* Schrad.
Index Seminum (Goet) 1832: 4 (1832)
Þyrpiperla
 - *Lepidium neglectum* Thell., Bull. Herb. Boissier II, 4: 708 (1904)

- *Lepidium heterophyllum* Benth.
Cat. Pl. Pyrénées: 95 (1826)
Hnoðperla

- *Lepidium latifolium* L.
Sp. Pl.: 644 (1753)
Strandperla

- *Lepidium perfoliatum* L.
Sp. Pl.: 643 (1753)
Slíðurperla

- *Lepidium ruderales* L.
Sp. Pl.: 645 (1753)
Haugperla

- *Lepidium sativum* L.
Sp. Pl.: 644 (1753)
Garðperla

- *Lepidium virginicum* L.
Sp. Pl.: 645 (1753)
Virginiúperla

- *Malcolmia maritima* (L.) W.T. Aiton
Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T. Aiton] 4: 121 (1812)
Sandblóm (Martoppur)

- *Nasturtium officinale* W.T. Aiton
Hort. Kew., ed. 2 [W.T. Aiton] 4: 110 (1812)
Brunnperla
 - *Nasturtium aquaticum* Wahlenb., Svensk Bot. Tidskr. 9: tab. 624 (1824)
 - *Rorippa nasturtium-aquaticum* (L.) Hayek, Sched. Fl. Stiriac. 3-4: 22 (1905)

○ *Raphanus raphanistrum* L.
Sp. Pl.: 669 (1753)
Akurhreðka

○ *Raphanus sativus* L.
Sp. Pl.: 669 (1753)
Ætihreðka

Rorippa islandica (Oeder ex Murray) Borbás
Balaton Tud. Part. 2: 392 (1900)

- *Sisymbrium islandicum* Oeder ex Murray, Novi Comment. Soc. Regiae Sci. Gott. 3: 81 (1773)
- *Radicula islandica* (Oeder) Druce, Bot. Exch. Club Brit. Isles Rep. 3(1): 9 (1912)
- *Sisymbrium terrestre* auct. non With. (1787)
- *Nasturtium palustre* auct. non DC. (1821)
- *Nasturtium amphibium* auct. non W.T. Aiton (1812)

Rorippa islandica (Oeder ex Murray) Borbás subsp. ***islandica***²⁰²
Kattarjurt

Rorippa sylvestris (L.) Besser²⁰³
Enum. Pl.: 27 (1822)

- *Rorippa sylvestris* subsp. *sylvestris* (L.) Besser
Flækjujurt
- *Sisymbrium sylvestre* L., Sp. Pl.: 657 (1753)

○ *Sinapis alba* L.
Sp. Pl.: 668 (1753)
Hvítmustarður

○ *Sinapis arvensis* L.
Sp. Pl.: 668 (1753)
Arfamustarður

○ *Sisymbrium altissimum* L.
Sp. Pl.: 659 (1753)
Risadesurt

- *Sisymbrium sinapistrum* Crantz, Stirp. Austr. Fasc.: 52 (1769)

○ *Sisymbrium officinale* (L.) Scop.
Fl. Carniol. ed. 2, 2: 26 (1772)
Götudesurt

- *Chamaeplium officinale* (L.) Wallr., Sched. Crit. 1: 377 (1822)

Subularia aquatica L.

Sp. Pl.: 642 (1753)

Subularia aquatica L. subsp. ***aquatica***
Alurt

202 In Iceland only nominal subspecies is present according to Jonsell (1968)

203 Elven et al. (2011) list *R. sylvestris* as an established adventive in Iceland and cite Kristinsson (2008) as a source. There are no indications to treat the species as an established adventive in Iceland and both Kristinsson (2008) and Wasowicz et al. (2013) list it as a casual alien.

▼ *Teesdalia nudicaulis* (L.) W.T. Aiton²⁰⁴

Hortus Kew. 4: 83 (1812)

Flipajurt

- by Babington (1871)

 ○ *Thlaspi arvense* L.²⁰⁵

Sp. Pl.: 646 (1753)

Akursjóður

PLUMBAGINACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 92 (1789), nom. cons.

Gullintoppuætt

Armeria maritima (Miller) Willd.

Enum. Pl.: 333 (1809)

 - *Statice maritima* Mill., Gard. Dict., ed. 8: Statice no. 3 (1768)

 - *Armeria vulgaris* Willd., Enum. Pl. Hort. Berol.: 333 (1809)

 - *Statice armeria* L., Sp. Pl.: 274 (1753)

 - *Armeria vulgaris* var. *planifolia* Syme in Sowerby, Engl. Bot., ed. 3B, 7: t. 1153 (1867)

 - *Armeria maritima* subsp. *planifolia* (Syme) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 54 (1961)

 - *Armeria elongata* Boiss.

 Armeria maritima (Miller) Willd. subsp. ***maritima***

Geldingahnappur

POLYGONACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 82 (1789), nom. cons.

Súruætt

 ○ *Aconogonon alpinum* (All.) Schur

Verh. Mitth. Siebenbürg. Vereins Naturwiss. Hermannstadt 4: 64 (1853)

Snæsúra

 - *Polygonum alpinum* All., Auct. Syn. Stirp. Taurin.: 42 (1773)

 - *Persicaria alpina* (All.) H. Gross, Bull. Acad. Int. Géogr. Bot. 23: 31 (1913)

Bistorta vivipara (L.) Delarbre

Fl. Auvergne, ed. 2: 516 (1800)

Kornsúra

 - *Polygonum viviparum* L., Sp. Pl.: 360 (1753)

 - *Persicaria vivipara* (L.) Ronse Decr., Bot. J. Linn. Soc. 98: 368 (1988)

 ○ *Fagopyrum esculentum* Moench

Methodus: 290 (1794)

Bókhveiti

 - *Fagopyrum sagittatum* Gilib., Exerc. Phyt.: 435 (1792)

204 *T. nudicaulis* has been recorded by Babington (no specimens available) and never confirmed again.

205 Elven et al. (2011) erroneously cites Kristinsson (2008) as a source of information that *T. arvense* is considered to be established in Iceland. In fact, both Kristinsson (2008) and Wasowicz et al. (2013) list the species as a casual alien.

○ *Fagopyrum tataricum* (L.) Gaertn.

Fruct. Sem. Pl. 2: 182 (1790)

Tatarabókhveiti

- *Polygonum tataricum* L., Sp. Pl. 364 (1753)

○ *Fallopia convolvulus* (L.) Á. Löve²⁰⁶

Taxon 19: 200 (1970)

Vafsúra

- *Polygonum convolvulus* L., Sp. Pl. 364 (1753)

***Koenigia islandica* L.**

Mant. Pl.: 35 (1767)

Naflagras

- *Koenigia islandica* var. *arctica* Hadac, Stud. Bot. Cech. 5: 3 (1942)
- *Koenigia hadacii* Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 506 (1976)
- *Koenigia arctica* sensu König and Müller (1770)

***Oxyria digyna* (L.) Hill**

Hort. Kew.: 158 (1768)

Ólafssúra

- *Rumex digynus* L., Sp. Pl.: 337 (1753)
- *Oxyria reniformis* Hook., Fl. Scot. 3: 111 (1821)

***Persicaria amphibia* (L.) Gray**

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 268 (1821)

Tjarnablaðka

- *Polygonum amphibium* L., Sp. Pl.: 361 (1753)

○ *Persicaria bistorta* (L.) Samp.²⁰⁷

Herb. Portug. 41 (1913)

Slöngusúra

- *Polygonum bistorta* L., Sp. Pl. 360 (1753)
- *Bistorta officinalis* Delarbre, Fl. Auvergne ed. 2, 2: 516 (1800)
- *Bistorta major* S.F. Gray, Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 267 (1821)

▼ *Persicaria hydropiper* (L.) Spach²⁰⁸

Hist. Nat. Vig. 10: 536 (1841)

Piparsúra

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Polygonum hydropiper*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

206 *F. convolvulus* is a casual species with a long history in Iceland. First confirmed records come from 1888 (Wasowicz et al. 2013) but it seems that it might have been present earlier (Babington 1871, Gliemann 1824, Rostrup 1887). Despite long history of introductions the species is still only a casual alien.

207 *P. bistorta* was mentioned by Hooker (1811) and Babington (1871) as a "very doubtful native", these records cannot be confirmed due to the lack of specimens. First confirmed records are from 1956 (Wasowicz et al. 2013) and the species seems to be a casual alien.

208 *P. hydropiper* was mentioned by early authors as present in Iceland. However, there is no evidence to confirm its presence.

○ *Persicaria lapathifolia* (L.) Delarbre²⁰⁹

Fl. Auvergne ed. 2: 519 (1800)

Lóblaðka

- *Polygonum lapathifolium* L., Sp. Pl. 360 (1753)
- *Polygonum tomentosum* L., Baier. Fl. 1: 669 (1789)

Persicaria maculosa Gray

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 269 (1821), nom. cons.

Flóajurt

- *Polygonum persicaria* L., Sp. Pl. 361 1753
- *Persicaria maculata* (Raf.) A. Löve & D. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20: 164 (1956) (non S.F. Gray)
- *Persicaria maculata* auct. non S.F. Gray (1821)

Polygonum aviculare L.

Sp. Pl.: 362 (1753)

Polygonum aviculare subsp. ***boreale*** (Lange) Karlsson²¹⁰

Svensk Bot. Tidsk. 91:249 (1998)

Blóðarfi

- *Polygonum aviculare* var. *boreale* Lange, Meddel. Gronland 3, 1: 105 (1880)
 - *Polygonum arenastrum* subsp. *boreale* Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 300 (1970)
 - *Polygonum aviculare* subsp. *neglectum* (Besser) Arcang.²¹¹
- Comp. Fl. Ital. 583 (1882)
- *Polygonum neglectum* Besser, Enum. Pl. 45 (1821)

○ *Reynoutria sachalinensis* (F. Schmidt) Nakai

Enum. Pl. Corea 135 (1922)

Risasúra

- *Polygonum sachalinense* F. Schmidt, Prim. Fl. Amur. 233 (1859)
- *Fallopia sachalinensis* (F. Schmidt) Ronse Decr., Bot. J. Linn. Soc. 98: 369 (1988)

○ ◇ *Rheum rhabarbarum* L.

Sp. Pl. 372 (1753)

Rabbarbari

- *Rheum undulatum* L., Sp. Pl. ed. 2 531 (1762)

209 Babington (1871), Grönlund (1881) and Rostrup (1887) mentioned *P. lapathifolia* from Iceland (no specimens available), but first confirmed records come from 1888 (Wasowicz et al. 2013).

210 *P. aviculare* subsp. *boreale* is widespread and native in Iceland, unlike subsp. *neglectum*.

211 *P. aviculare* subsp. *neglectum* is known only from one locality in Iceland (Geysir) and should be classified as a recent antropochorous taxon.

***Rumex acetosa* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 337 (1753)

- *Acetosa pratensis* Mill., Gard. Dict., ed. 8: *Acetosa* no. 1 (1768), nomen novum for *Rumex acetosa* L.

- ▶ *Rumex acetosa* subsp. *acetosa*²¹²

- *Rumex acetosa* subsp. *pratensis* (Mill.) Blytt & O.C. Dahl, Haandb. Norges Fl. 285 (1903)

- Rumex acetosa* subsp. *islandicus* (Á. Löve) Ö. Nilsson²¹³**

Nordic J. Bot. 16: 5 (1996)

Túnsúra

- *Acetosa alpestris* subsp. *islandica* Á. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20(4): 191 (1956)
- *Rumex acetosa* var. *islandicus* (Á. Löve) Hyl. (1966)
- ? *Rumex acetosa* subsp. *alpestris* (Scop.) Á. Löve
- ? *Rumex acetosa* var. *nivalis* (Hegetschw.) Á. Löve
- ? *Acetosa pratensis* var. *islandica* Á. Löve

***Rumex acetosella* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 338 (1753)

Hundasúra

- *Acetosella vulgaris* Fourr., Ann. Soc. Linn. Lyon, sér. 2, 17: 145 (1869)

- Rumex acetosella* L. subsp. *acetosella***

- Rumex acetosella* subsp. *arenicola* Y. Mäkinen ex Elven**

Nordic J. Bot. 19: 387 (2000)

- Rumex acetosella* subsp. *tenuifolius* (Wallr.) O. Schwarz**

Mitt. Thüring. Bot. Ges. 1: 97 (1949)

- *Rumex acetosella* var. *tenuifolius* Wallr., Sched. Crit.: 186 (1822)
- *Rumex tenuifolius* (Wallr.) Á. Löve, Bot. Not. 1941: 99 (1941)
- *Acetosella tenuifolia* (Wallr.) Á. Löve, Rep. Dept. Agric. Univ. Inst. Appl. Sci. (Reykjavik), ser. B, 3: 108 (1948)
- ? *Acetosella multifida* (L.), Á. Löve, Fl. Iceland: 168 (1983)

▼ *Rumex acutus* L.²¹⁴

Sp. Pl.: 335 (1753)

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Rumex arifolius* All.²¹⁵

Auct. Syn. Stirp. Taurin.: 94 (1773), et Fl. Pedem. 2: 204 (1785)

Vallarsúra

- by Abromeit (1905)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

▼ *Rumex conglomeratus* Murray²¹⁶

Prodr. Stirp. Gött.: 52 (1770)

Hnoðasúra

- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

212 *R. acetosa* subsp. *acetosa* is a non- native taxon of unknown age (Nilsson 2000, Elven et al. 2011, Wasowicz 2018).

213 *R. acetosa* subsp. *islandicus* is considered to be a local race endemic to Iceland and the Faroe Islands (Nilsson 2000).

214 *R. acutus* has been included in some of the old lists. There is no specimens available to confirm these records.

215 *R. arifolius* has been recorded just once from Fáskrúðsfjörður, but there are no specimens available to confirm this dubious observation.

216 Babington (1871) classified earlier records of *Rumex acutus* as *Rumex conglomeratus*.

○ *Rumex crispus* L.²¹⁷

Sp. Pl.: 335 (1753)

Hrukkunjóli

○ *Rumex heterophyllus* C.F. Schultz²¹⁸

Prod. Pl. Starg. Suppl. 1: 21 (1819)

■ ***Rumex longifolius*** DC.²¹⁹

Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 6: 368 (1815)

Njóli

– *Rumex domesticus* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl.: 148 (1820)

Rumex obtusifolius L.

Sp. Pl.: 335 (1753)

○ *Rumex obtusifolius* subsp. *sylvestris* (Wallr.) Čelak.

Prodr. Fl. Böhmen: 159 (1871)

Borgarnjóli

▼ *Rumex patientia* L.²²⁰

Sp. Pl.: 333–334 (1753)

Garðsúra

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)

- by Baring-Gould (1863)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

* ○ *Rumex stenophyllus* Ledeb.²²¹

Fl. Altaic. 2: 58 (1830)

Akurnjóli

○ *Rumex thyrsiflorus* Fingerh.

Linnaea 4: 380 (1829)

Skúfasúra

○ *Rumex triangulivalvis* (Danser) Rech. f.

Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 40(20–25): 297 (1936)

Bugðunjóli

217 First confirmed records of *R. crispus* in Iceland come from 1945 (Wasowicz et al. 2013), but the species was mentioned also by some of the early authors: Benguerel (1861), Babington (1871) and Bennett (1886). These old records cannot be confirmed due to the lack of specimens.

218 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

219 *R. longifolius* is a doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

220 There are no collections to confirm the records of *R. patientia*.

221 *R. stenophyllus* was entered provisionally. The occurrence of this species is based only on one literature record and there are no collections available.

DROSERACEAE Salisb.

Parad. Lond. 2: ad t. 95. (1808), nom. cons.

Sóldaggarætt

▼ *Drosera anglica* Huds.²²²

Fl. Angl., ed. 2, 1: 135 (1778)

Gyðjudögg

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Drosera longifolia*

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Drosera rotundifolia L.

Sp. Pl.: 281 (1753)

Sóldögg

CARYOPHYLLACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 299 (1789), nom. cons.

Hjartagrasætt

○ *Agrostemma githago* L.

Sp. Pl.: 435 (1753)

Akurstjarna

Arenaria norvegica Gunnerus

Fl. Norveg. 2: 144 (1776)

Skeggsandi

- *Arenaria ciliata* var. *humifusa* sensu Grønlund (1881); Stefánsson (1901), non (Wahlenb.) Hartm.▼ *Arenaria serpyllifolia* L.²²³

Sp. Pl.: 423 (1753)

Bakkasandi

- by König and Müller (1770)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

222 There are no specimens available to confirm early records of *D. anglica* and the species has not been recorded from Iceland by more recent studies.

223 *A. serpyllifolia* was mentioned by some of the early authors but there are no specimens available to confirm these records.

***Cerastium alpinum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 438 (1753)

Cerastium alpinum* L. subsp. *alpinum

Músareyra

***Cerastium alpinum* subsp. *glabratum* (Hartm.) Á. Löve & D. Löve**

Acta Horti Gothob. 20, 4: 141 (1956)

Snoðeyra

 – *Cerastium glabratum* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl.: 180 (1820)

 – *Cerastium alpinum* var. *glabrum* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp.: 136 (1812)

***Cerastium alpinum* subsp. *lanatum* (Lam.) Ces., Notizie Naturali e Civili su la Lombardia: 290 (1844)**

Loðeyra

 – *Cerastium lanatum* Lam., Encycl. 1: 680 (1785)

 – *Cerastium alpinum* var. *lanatum* (Lam.) Hegetschw., Reisen Gebirgsstock Glarus Graubünden: 154 (1825)

 ▼ *Cerastium arvense* L.²²⁴

Sp. Pl.: 438 (1753)

Mjallareyra

– by Babington (1871)

– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

 ○ *Cerastium biebersteinii* DC.

Mém. Soc. Phys. Genève 1: 436 (1823)

Rottueyra

***Cerastium cerastoides* (L.) Britton**

Mem. Torrey Bot. Club 5: 150 (1894)

Lækjafraeyrna

 – *Stellaria cerastoides* L., Sp. Pl.: 422 (1753)

 – *Dichodon cerastoides* (L.) Rchb., Icon. Fl. Germ. Helv. 5: f. 4915 (1841)

 – *Cerastium trigynum* Vill., Prosp. Hist. Pl. Dauphiné: 48 (1779)

***Cerastium fontanum* Baumg.**

Enum. Stirp. Transsilv. 1: 425 (1816)

Cerastium fontanum* Baumg. subsp. *fontanum

Vegarfi

 – *Cerastium fontanum* subsp. *scandicum* Gartner, Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. Beih. 113: 68 (1939)

 ► *Cerastium fontanum* subsp. *vulgare* (Hartm.) Greuter & Burdet²²⁵

 – *Cerastium vulgare* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl.: 182 (1820)

 – *Cerastium triviale* Link, Enum. Hort. Berol. Alt. 1: 433 (1821)

 – *Cerastium caespitosum* Asch., Fl. Brandenburg 1, 1: 102 (1860)

 – *Cerastium vulgatum* L. (1762), non L. (1755) nom. illeg.

 ◆ *Cerastium glomeratum* Thuill.²²⁶

Fl. Env. Paris ed. 2: 226 (1799)

Hnoðafraeyrna

 – *Cerastium viscosum* L., Sp. Pl.: 437–438 (1753)

 224 *C. arvense* was recorded just once by Babington (1871), there are no specimens available to confirm this record.

 225 *C. fontanum* subsp. *vulgare* is a naturalized, non-native taxon of unknown age (Wasowicz 2018).

 226 *C. glomeratum* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

▼ *Cerastium latifolium* L.

Sp. Pl.: 439 (1753)

Alpafræhyrna

- by Zoëga (1772)
- by Hooker (1811)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Cerastium nigrescens (H.C. Watson) Edmondston ex H.C. Watson

Cybele Brit., Suppl. 1: 81 (1860)

- *Cerastium latifolium* var. *nigrescens* H.C. Watson, Cybele Brit. 1: 233 (1847)

Cerastium nigrescens var. *laxum* (Lindblad) Brysting & Elven

Taxon 49: 212 (2000)

Fjallafræhyrna

- *Cerastium latifolium* Lindblom, Physiogr. Sällsk. Tidskr. 1: 334 (1838)
- *Cerastium arcticum* auct. non Lange (1880)
- *Cerastium edmondstonii* auct. non Murb. & Ostenf. (1898)

○ *Cerastium tomentosum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 440 (1753)

Völskueyra

Cherleria biflora A.J. Moore & Dillenb.²²⁷

Willdenowia 47(1): 9 (2017)

Fjallanára

- *Stellaria biflora* L., Sp. Pl.: 421 (1753)
- *Alsine biflora* (L.) Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp. 128 (1812)
- *Minuartia biflora* (L.) Schinz & Thell., Bull. Herb. Boissier ser. 2, 7: 404 (1907)
- *Lidia biflora* (L.) A. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Notiser 128(4): 510 (1975)
- *Alsine arcitca* auct. non Fenzl (1833)

○ *Dianthus deltoides* L.

Sp. Pl.: 411 (1753)

Dvergadrottning

○ *Dianthus gratianopolitanus* Vill.²²⁸

Hist. Pl. Dauphiné 3: 598 (1789)

Laugadrottning

Honckenya peploides (L.) Ehrh.

Neues Mag. Aerzte 5: 206 (1783)

- *Arenaria peploides* L., Sp. Pl.: 423 (1753)
- *Halianthus peploides* (L.) Fr., Fl. Hall.: 75 (1817)
- *Minuartia peploides* (L.) Hiern, Journ. Bot., 322 (1899)

Honckenya peploides subsp. *diffusa* (Hornem.) Hultén ex V.V. Petrovsky

Fl. Arct. URSS 6: 71 (1971)

Fjöruarfi

- *Arenaria peploides* var. *diffusa* Hornem., Fors. Oecon. Plantel., ed. 3, 1: 501 (1821)
- *Honckenya diffusa* (Hornem.) Á. Löve, Bot. Not. 103: 39 (1950)

227 In a recent taxonomic revision and new circumscription of the genus *Minuartia* (Dillenberger and Kadereit 2014) all Icelandic species are classified outside the genus and transferred to genera *Cherleria* and *Sabulina*.

228 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

Lychnis flos-cuculi L.

Sp. Pl.: 436 (1753)

Munkahetta

- *Coronaria flos-cuculi* (L.) A. Br., Flora 26: 368 (1843)
- *Silene flos-cuculi* (L.) Greuter & Burdet, Willdenowia 12: 189 (1982)

Sabulina rubella (Wahlenb.) Dillenb. & Kadereit²²⁹

Taxon 63(1): 87 (2014)

Melanóra

- *Alsine rubella* Wahlenb., Fl. Lapp. 128 (1812)
- *Minuartia rubella* (Wahlenb.) Hiern, Journ. Bot.: 320 (1899)
- *Tryphane rubella* (Wahlenb.) Á. Löve & D. Löve ex W.A. Weber, J. Bot. Res. Inst. Texas 3(2): 501 (2000)
- *Tryphane rubella* subsp. *propinqua* (Richardson) Á. Löve & D. Löve ex W.A. Weber, J. Bot. Res. Inst. Texas 3(2): 502 (2009)
- *Alsine verna* sensu Grønlund (1881), non Bartl. (1825)
- *Alsine verna* var. *hirta* sensu Stefánsson (1901)
- *Minuartia verna* auct. non Hiern (1899)
- *Arenaria gieseckii* auct. non Hornem. (1840)

Sabulina stricta (Sw.) Rchb.²³⁰

Fl. Germ. Excurs. 2: 789 (1832)

Móanóra

- *Arenaria stricta* (Sw.) Michx., Fl. Bor.-Amer. 1: 274 (1803)
- *Alsine stricta* (Sw.) Wahlenb., Fl. Lappon.: 127 (1812)
- *Alsinanthe stricta* (Sw.) Rchb., Icon. Fl. Germ. Helv. 5: 29, t. 209 (1841)
- *Minuartia stricta* (Sw.) Hiern, J. Bot. 37: 320 (1899)
- *Arenaria stricta* var. *uliginosa* (Schleich. ex Lam. & DC.) B. Boivin, Naturaliste Canad. 93: 642 (1966)

Sagina caespitosa (J. Vahl) Lange

Grönl. Geogr. Stat. Beskr. 2(6): 133 (1857)

Fjallkrækil

- *Arenaria caespitosa* J. Vahl, Fl. Dan. 13, 39: t. 2289 (1840)
- *Spergella caespitosa* (Vahl) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 508 (1975)

Sagina nivalis (Lindblom) Fr.

Novit. Fl. Svec. Mant. 3: 31 (1842)

Snækrækil

- *Spergula saginoides* var. *nivalis* Lindblom, Physiogr. Sällsk. Tidskr. 1: 328 (1838)
- *Sagina intermedia* Fenzl in Ledeb., Fl. Ross. 1: 339 (1842 October)
- *Spergella intermedia* (Fenzl) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 508 (1976)

Sagina nodosa (L.) Fenzl

Vers. Darstell. Alsin.: t. ad 18 (1833)

- *Spergula nodosa* L., Sp. Pl.: 440 (1753)
- *Spergella nodosa* (L.) Rchb., Fl. Germ. Excurs. 795 (1832)

Sagina nodosa subsp. ***borealis*** G.E. Crow

Rhodora 80: 28 (1978)

Hnúskakrækil

229 See footnote for *Cherleria biflora*230 See footnote for *Cherleria biflora*

Sagina procumbens L.

Sp. Pl.: 128 (1753)

Skammkrækil

Sagina saginoides (L.) H. Karst.

Deut. Fl. 6: 539 (1882)

Langkrækil

- *Spergula saginoides* L., Sp. Pl.: 441 (1753)
- *Sagina linnaei* C. Presl, Reliq. Haenk. 2: 14 (1831)
- *Sagina saxatilis* Wimmer, Fl. Schlesien: 75 (1840)

Sagina subulata (Sw.) C. Presl

Fl. Sicul.: 158 (1826)

Broddkrækil

- *Spergula subulata* Sw., Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 10: 45 (1789)

▼ *Scleranthus annuus* L.²³¹

Sp. Pl.: 406 (1753)

Hnoðaknýti

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Silene acaulis (L.) Jacq.

Enum. Stirp. Vindob.: 242 (1762)

Silene acaulis (L.) Jacq. subsp. ***acaulis***

Lambagras

- *Silene acaulis* subsp. *arctica* Á. Löve & D. Löve, Univ. Colorado Stud., Ser. Biol. 17: 21 (1965)
- *Cucubalus acaulis* L., Sp. Pl.: 415 (1753)

● *Silene dioica* (L.) Clairv.

Man. Herbor. Suisse: 145 (1811)

Dagstjarna

- *Lychnis dioica* L., Sp. Pl.: 437 (1753)
- *Melandrium dioicum* (L.) Coss. & Germ., Fl. Descr. Anal. Paris: 28 (1845)
- *Melandrium rubrum* (Weigel) Garcke, Fl. N. Mitt.-Deutschland, ed. 4: 55 (1858) nom. illeg.
- *Melandrium dioicum* subsp. *rubrum* (Weig.) D. Löve

○ *Silene latifolia* Poir.

Voy. Barbarie 2: 165 (1789)

Aftanstjarna

- *Melandrium album* (Miller) Garcke, Fl. N. Mitt. Deutschland ed. 4: 55 (1858)
- *Melandrium dioicum* subsp. *album* (Mill.) D. Löve, Bot. Not. 1944(2): 200 (1944)
- *Silene latifolia* subsp. *alba* (Mill.) Greuter & Burdet, Willdenowia 12: 189 (1982)

○ *Silene noctiflora* L.

Sp. Pl.: 419 (1753)

Rökkurstjarna

- *Melandrium noctiflorum* (L.) Fries, Bot. Not. 4: 178 (1842)

231 *S. annuus* was mentioned by most of the early authors from König and Müller (1770) to Babington (1871), but has never been found later. There are no specimens available to confirm these early records.

Silene uniflora Roth²³²

Ann. Bot. (Usteri) 10: 46 (1794)

Holurt

- *Silene maritima* With., Arr. Brit. Pl., ed. 3, 2: 414 (1796)
- *Silene maritima* subsp. *islandica* Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 103: 40 (1950)
- *Silene vulgaris* subsp. *maritima* (With.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 114: 52 (1961)
- *Silene inflata* var. *litoralis* Rupr., Fl. Ingr. 1: 159 (1860)
- *Oberna uniflora* subsp. *islandica* (Á. Löve & D. Löve) Holub, Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 12(4): 427 (1977)
- *Oberna behen* subsp. *islandica* sensu Löve (1983)
- *Cucubalus behen* auct. non L. (1753)

○ *Silene vulgaris* (Moench) Garcke

Fl. N. Mitt.-Deutschland ed. 9: 64 (1869)

Garðaholurt

- *Silene inflata* Sm., Fl. Brit.: 467 (1800)

Spergula arvensis L.

Sp. Pl.: 440 (1753)

* ○ *Spergula arvensis* L. subsp. *arvensis*²³³

◆ *Spergula arvensis* subsp. *sativa* (Mert. & W.D.J. Koch) Čelak.²³⁴

Prodr. Fl. Böchmen 3: 492 (1875)

Skurfa

- *Spergula arvensis* var. *sativa* Mert. & W.D.J. Koch in Röhl., Deutschl.Fl., ed.3, 3: 360 (1831)

Spergularia salina J. Presl & C. Presl

Fl. Cech.: 95 (1819)

Flæðarbúi (Flæðaskurfa)

- *Spergularia marina* (L.) Besser, Enum. Pl.: 97 (1822)
- *Spergula marina* (L.) Bartl. & H.L. Wendl, Beitr. Bot. 2: 64 (1825)
- *Spergularia marina* (L.) Griseb., Spic. Fl. Rumel. 1: 213 (1843)

● *Stellaria alsine* Grimm²³⁵

Nova Acta Acad. Leop.-Carol. 3: app. 313 (1767)

nom. inval. ex Grande in Nuovo Giorn. B. Ital. n.s. 29: 158

Bakkaarfi

- *Stellaria uliginosa* Murray, Prod. Stirp. Gott.: 55 (1770)

Stellaria borealis Bigelow

Fl. Boston., ed. 2: 182 (1824)

Stellaria borealis Bigelow subsp. ***borealis***

Línarfi

- *Stellaria calycantha* auct. non Bong. (1833)

232 The status of Icelandic *S. uniflora* is unclear. They differ morphologically from other NW European plants and have been described as *Silene maritima* subsp. *islandica* (Löve and Löve 1950). Characters mentioned by Löve and Löve (1950) as diagnostic are, however, present in other European populations of the species. In Iceland these characters are found as a constant combination (Elven et al. 2011)

233 *S. arvensis* L. subsp. *arvensis* was entered provisionally. Uotila and Kurtto (2001) recognised this taxon from Iceland as a casual alien on the basis of two specimens from Kornsa (collected in 1889) and Laugarvatn (collected in 1931). The presence of the taxon cannot be confirmed on the basis of collections in Icelandic herbaria.

234 *S. arvensis* subsp. *sativa* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

235 There are still doubts whether *S. alsine* should be classified as native or alien (Kristinsson 2008). Here, it was classified as naturalized alien (Wasowicz et al. 2013) but further research is needed to elucidate this question.

Stellaria crassifolia Ehrh.

Hannover. Mag. 8: 116 (1784)

Stjörnuarfi

• *Stellaria graminea* L.

Sp. Pl.: 422 (1753)

Akurarfi

▼ *Stellaria longipes* Goldie²³⁶

Edinb. Phil. Journ. 6: (Apr. 1822) 327 (1822)

Stilkarfi

- by Vahl 1840 as *Stellaria edwardsii* R. Br.

- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Stellaria humifusa Rottb.

Skr. Kjøbenhavnske Selsk. Lærd. Elsk. 10: 447 (1770)

Lágarfi

◆ *Stellaria media* (L.) Vill.²³⁷

Hist. Pl. Dauphiné 3(2): 615 (1789)

Haugarfi

- *Alsine media* L., Sp. Pl.: 272 (1753)○ *Vaccaria hispanica* (Miller) Rauschert

Wiss. Z. Martin-Luther-Univ. Halle Witt., Math. -Natur. Reihe 14: 496 (1965)

Kúajurt

- *Vaccaria parviflora* Moench, Methodus: 63 (1794)***Viscaria alpina*** (L.) G. Don

Gen. Hist. 1: 415 (1831)

Ljósberi

- *Lychnis alpina* L., Sp. Pl.: 436 (1753)- *Steris alpina* (L.) Sourkova, Novit. Bot. 1973–1975: 27 (1976)- *Lychnis suecica* Lodd., Bot. Cab. 9: 881 (1824)- *Viscaria alpina* subsp. *borealis* Böcher, Biol. Skr. 11(6): 27 (1963)- *Silene suecica* (Lodd.) Greuter & Burdet, Willdenowia 12: 190 (1982)▼ *Viscaria vulgaris* Röhling²³⁸

Deutschl. Fl. ed. 2, 2: 275 (1812)

Límberi

- by Hjaltalín (1830) as *Lychnis vulgaris*

- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

236 There are no specimens available to confirm records of *S. longipes* from Iceland.

237 *S. media* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

238 *V. vulgaris* has been recorded, most probably by mistake, by Hjaltalín (1830). Subsequently this record was copied by some of the early authors.

AMARANTHACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 87 (1789), nom. cons.

Skrauthalaætt

Atriplex glabriuscula Edmondston²³⁹

Fl. Shetland: 39 (1845)

Hrímblaðka

- *Atriplex babingtonii* J. Woods, Man. Brit. Bot. ed. 3: 270 (1851)
- *Atriplex hastata* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Atriplex patula* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Atriplex laciniata* auct. non L. (1753)
- *Atriplex angustifolia* auct. non Sm. (1800)

▼ *Atriplex hortensis* L.²⁴⁰

Sp. Pl.: 1053 (1753)

Garðahrímblaðka

- by Zoëga (1772)
- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Atriplex littoralis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 1054 (1753)

Þanghrímblaðka

* ***Atriplex longipes*** Drejer

Fl. Excurs. Hafn.: 107. 1838

* ***Atriplex longipes*** subsp. ***praecox*** (Hülph.) Turesson²⁴¹

Acta Univ. Lund., n.s., sect. 2, 16: 6 (1925)

Hélublaðka

- *Atriplex praecox* Hülph. in Lindm., Sv. Fanerogamfl.: 228 (1918)
- ? *Atriplex longipes* subsp. *lapponica* (Pojark.) Á. Löve & D. Löve

○ *Atriplex patula* L.²⁴²

Sp. Pl.: 1053 (1753)

Akurhrímblaðka

* ○ *Atriplex prostrata* Boucher ex DC.²⁴³

Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 3: 387 (1805)

239 *A. glabriuscula* has earlier been misidentified and diagnosed as *A. patula* (Grønlund 1881, Stefánsson 1901, Gröntved 1942, Löve 1945, Stefánsson 1948, Löve 1970). See also comments under *A. patula*.

240 Records of *A. hortensis* from Iceland may be referred to plants found as casual aliens, but collections are lacking to verify this option.

241 *A. longipes* subsp. *praecox* has been entered provisionally. The species was recognised from Iceland by Gustafsson (2001), Kristinsson (2008) and Elven et al. (2011). However, its occurrence was confirmed only on one site in Breiðdalsvík in E Iceland. It occurs both in Scandinavia and in Greenland, so the presence of the species in Iceland is not unlikely. This question needs to be evaluated more thoroughly.

242 *A. patula* has been mentioned many times as native and widespread in Iceland as a result of misidentification. Currently, nearly all collections from Iceland were assigned to *A. glabriuscula* (see above). *A. patula* is a rare casual alien (Wasowicz et al. 2013).

243 *A. prostrata* has been entered provisionally. The species was not accepted from Iceland by neither Gustafsson (2001) nor Kristinsson (2008). Elven et al. (2011), however, listed it as present and possibly overlooked. It was accepted and classified as casual alien by Wasowicz et al. (2013). Its status in Icelandic flora requires further attention.

- *Chenopodium album* L.
Sp. Pl.: 219 (1753)
Hélunjólí
- *Chenopodium berlandieri* Moq.
Chenop. Monogr. Enum.: 23 (1840)
Texasnjólí
- *Chenopodium murale* L.
Sp. Pl.: 219 (1753)
Netlunjólí
- *Chenopodium opulifolium* Schrad. ex W.D.J. Koch & Ziz
Cat. Pl.: 6 (1814)
Hærunjólí
- *Chenopodium pratericola* Rydb.
Bull. Torrey Bot. Club 39: 310 (1912)
Gæsanjólí
- *Chenopodium suecicum* Murr
Magyar Bot. Lapok 1: 341 (1902)
Svíanjólí
- *Suaeda maritima* (L.) Dumort.
Fl. Belg. 22 (1827)
Salturt
- *Salsola tragus* L.
Cent. Pl. 2: 13 (1756)
Þornurt
 - *Salsola kali* subsp. *tragus* (L.) Čelak., Prodr. Fl. Böhmen 2: 155 (1871)

MONTIACEAE Raf.

Ann. Gen. Sci. Phys. 5: 349 (1820)
Grýtuætt

- *Claytonia sibirica* L.
Sp. Pl.: 204 (1753)
Rósagrýta

Montia fontana L.

Sp. Pl.: 87 (1753)

Lækjagrýta

- *Montia lamprosperma* Cham., Linnaea, 6: 565 (1831)
- *Montia rivularis* sensu Grønlund (1881), non C.C. Gmel. (1805)

CORNACEAE Bercht. & J. Presl

Prir. Rostlin 2(23): 91, 92 (1825), nom. cons.

Skollabersætt

Cornus suecica L.²⁴⁴

Sp. Pl.: 118 (1753)

Skollaber

– *Chamaepericlymenum suecicum* (L.) Graebn., Fl. Nordostdeut. Flachl. 4: 539 (1899)**POLEMONIACEAE** Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 136 (1789), nom. cons.

Jakobsstigaætt

○ *Polemonium caeruleum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 162 (1753)

Jakobsstigi

PRIMULACEAE Batsch ex Borkh.

Bot. Wörterb. 2: 240 (1797), nom. cons.

Maríulykilsætt

○ *Anagallis arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 148 (1753)

Nónblóm

Lysimachia europaea (L.) U. Manns & Anderb.²⁴⁵

Willendowia 39:51 (2009)

Sjöstjarna

– *Trientalis europaea* L., Sp. Pl.: 344 (1753)– *Lysimachia trientalis* Klatt, Linnea 37: 400 (1872) nom. illeg.***Lysimachia maritima*** (L.) Galasso, Banfi & Soldano²⁴⁶

Atti Soc. Ital. Sci. Nat. Mus. Civico Storia Nat. Milano 146: 229 (2005)

Sandlæðingur

– *Glaux maritima* L., Sp. Pl.: 207 (1753)

244 Some taxonomists find it more appropriate to classify the species in a separate genus: *Chamaepericlymenum* Hill. This view, adopted also by Elven et al. (2005, 2011) is in agreement with phylogenetic studies showing that all taxa within *Cornaceae* occurring in the Nordic countries could be classified to three separate, monophyletic genera: *Chamaepericlymenum*, *Swida* and *Cornus* s. str. (Murrell 1993, Xiang et al. 1993, 1998, Hulten and Fries 1986). These studies have shown that *Cornus* s.lat is also a monophyletic group. Therefore, a traditional view, also followed by Jonsell (2010), was adopted here.

245 Recent studies have shown that present generic circumscription does not account for the recent discoveries regarding evolutionary history of the *Lysimachia* generic complex, and thus a number of nomenclatural changes are necessary to meet the demand for strictly monophyletic taxa (Manns & Anderberg 2009). The transfer of *T. europaea* to *Lysimachia* is one of these changes that are now widely accepted.

246 A study by Anderberg et al. (2007) gives support for placing the monotypic genus *Glaux* within *Lysimachia*. It seems that in the future *Glaux* will not be maintained as a separate genus, but it holds very isolated position within *Lysimachia* and its closest relatives are yet to be found.

▼ *Lysimachia nummularia* L.²⁴⁷

Sp. Pl.: 148

Skildingablóm

- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Lysimachia punctata* L.

Sp. Pl.: 147 (1753)

Útlagi

† *Primula egaliksensis* Wormsk. ex Hornem.²⁴⁸

Fl. Dan. 9, 26: 4, t. 1511 (1816)

Davíðslykill

- *Primula stricta* var. *hamundarstadensis* sensu Steindorsson (1948)

○ *Primula elatior* (L.) L.²⁴⁹

Fl. Angl.: 12 (1754)

Huldulykill

Primula stricta Hornem.

Fl. Dan. 8, 24: 3, t. 1385 (1810)

Maríulykill

- *Primula farinosa* Bieb., Fl. Taur. Caucasus 1: 139 (1808)
- *Primula stricta* var. *obesior* Norman, Special. Loc. Natal.: 87 (1868)
- ? *Primula hornemanni* auct.

○ *Primula veris* L.²⁵⁰

Fl. Angl.: 12 (1754)

Sifjarlykill

DIAPENSIACEAE Lindl.

Nat. Syst. Bot. ed. 2: 233 (1836), nom. cons.

Fjallabrúðuætt

Diapensia lapponica L.

Sp. Pl.: 141 (1753)

Fjallabrúða

ERICACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 159 (1789), nom. cons.

Lyngætt

Andromeda polifolia L.

Sp. Pl.: 393 (1753)

Ljósalyng

247 There are no collections available and no recent records of *L. nummularia* from Iceland, which makes its occurrence very doubtful.

248 *P. egaliksensis* was known just from one locality in Iceland (Stóru-Hámundarstaðir, Eyjafjörður, N Iceland) but have gone extinct in 20th century due to habitat destruction.

249 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

250 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

▼ *Arctostaphylos alpinus* (L.) Sprengel²⁵¹

Syst. Veg. 2: 287 (1825)

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Arbutus alpina*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Arctostaphylos uva-ursi (L.) Spreng.

Syst. Veg. 2: 287 (1825)

Sortulyng

- *Arbutus uva-ursi* L., Sp. Pl.: 395 (1753)
- *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* var. *adenotricha* Fernald & J.F. Macbr., Rhodora 16: 213 (1914)
- *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* var. *coactilis* Fernald & J.F. Macbr., Rhodora 16: 212 (1914)
- *Arctostaphylos uva-ursi* subsp. *coactilis* (Fernald & J.F. Macbr.) Á. Löve, D. Löve & B.M. Kapoor, Arctic Alpine Res. 3: 154–155 (1971)

Calluna vulgaris (L.) Hull

Brit. Fl., ed. 2, 1: 114 (1808)

Beitilyng

- *Erica vulgaris* L., Sp. Pl.: 352 (1753)

Empetrum nigrum L.²⁵²

Sp. Pl.: 1022 (1753)

Krækilyng

- *Empetrum hermaphroditum* Lange ex Hagerup, Dansk Bot. Ark. 5, 2: 1 (1927)
- *Empetrum nigrum* var. *hermaphroditum* (Lange ex Hagerup) T.J. Sørensen, Meddel. Grønland 101(3): 95 (1933)
- *Empetrum nigrum* subsp. *hermaphroditum* (Lange ex Hagerup) Böcher, Meddel. Grønland 147(9): 81 (1952)
- *Empetrum eamesii* subsp. *hermaphroditum* (Lange ex Hagerup) D. Löve, Rhodora 62: 289 (1960)

▼ *Erica cinerea* L.²⁵³

Sp. Pl.: 352 (1753)

Roðalyng

- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

○ *Erica tetralix* L.²⁵⁴

Sp. Pl.: 353 (1753)

Haustlyng

251 The species present in almost all lists by early authors. There is no evidence available to verify these records.

252 The variation within *E. nigrum* is a complex issue. According to ploidy level two major groups can be identified within the species: (1) dioecious diploids - found in temperate and boreal regions of Europe, Siberia and temperate-boreal NE North America and in the Pacific regions of N America (2) synoecious tetraploids - found at high altitudes and latitudes throughout the species range (Elven et al. 2011, Popp et al. 2011). Both groups are represented in the Icelandic flora and have been treated as separate taxa (Stefánsson 1948, Kristinsson 2008). Murray et al. (2009) emphasised that the name *Empetrum hermaphroditum* is typified on a Greenlandic, synoecious tetraploid, but it was applied to all black-fruited synoecious plants throughout the species range. Taking into account that there are studies showing polyphyletic origin of synoecious tetraploids [see discussion in Murray et al. (2009) and Elven et al. (2011)], the name *E. hermaphroditum* (and its combinations), should be subsumed by *E. nigrum* (Murray et al. 2009).

253 Early records of *E. cinerea* from Iceland cannot be confirmed due to lack of specimens. There are no contemporary records to confirm its presence.

254 The status of this species in the flora of Iceland is very unclear. Some early authors, including Gliemann (1824), Vahl (1840) and Babington (1871) recorded it as present in Iceland. Recently (in 2003), it has been found in two localities in S Iceland, but it seems that in both cases it was a recent and unintentional introduction (Wasowicz et al., 2013). There are, however, some unconfirmed records (no voucher specimens) from the slopes of Ingólfssjall (S Iceland) dating back to 1950's, but the plant is probably no longer present there due to mining activities in the area. Here, *E. tetralix* is classified as a recent, not-established adventive since previous records cannot be verified.

Harrimanella hypnoides (L.) Coville

Proc. Wash. Acad. Sci. 3: 575 (1901)

Mosalyng

- *Andromeda hypnoides* L., Sp. Pl.: 393 (1753)
- *Cassiope hypnoides* (L.) D. Don, Edinburgh New Philos. J. 17: 158 (1834)

▼ ***Hypopitys monotropa*** Crantz²⁵⁵

Inst. Rei Herb. 2: 467 (1766)

Sníkjurót

- *Monotropa hypopitys* L., Sp. Pl.: 387 (1753)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Kalmia procumbens (L.) Gift, Kron & P.F. Stevens ex Galasso, Banfi & F. Conti²⁵⁶

Annot. Checkl. Italian Vasc. Fl.: 20 (2005)

Sauðamergur

- *Azalea procumbens* L., Sp. Pl.: 151 (1753)
- *Loiseleuria procumbens* (L.) Desv., J. Bot. Appl. 1: 35 (1813)
- *Kalmia procumbens* Gift & Kron, Nordic J. Bot. 26(1-2): 47 (2008)
- *Kalmia procumbens* Gift, Kron & P.F. Stevens, Bot. Rev. 68(3): 409 (2002)

▼ ***Moneses uniflora*** (L.) A. Gray²⁵⁷

Manual: 273 (1848)

Ólafsstjaki

- *Pyrola uniflora* L., Sp. Pl.: 397 (1753)
- by Gröntved (1942)

Orthilia secunda (L.) House

Amer. Midl. Naturalist 7: 134 (1921)

Grænlilja

- *Pyrola secunda* L., Sp. Pl.: 396 (1753)
- *Ramischia secunda* (L.) Garcke, Fl. N. Mitt.-Deutschland, ed. 4: 222 (1858)

Oxycoccus microcarpus Turcz. ex Rupr.

Hist. Stirp. Fl. Petrop.: 56 (1845)

Mýraberjalyng

- *Vaccinium microcarpum* (Turcz. ex Rupr.) Schmalh., Trudy S.Peterburgsk. Obshch. Estestvoisp. 2: 149 (1870)
- *Vaccinium oxycoccus* subsp. *microcarpum* (Turcz. ex Rupr.) A. Blytt & O.C. Dahl, Haandb. Norges Fl.: 561 (1906/1905)

Phyllodoce caerulea (L.) Bab.

Man. Brit. Bot.: 194 (1843)

Bláklukkulyng

- *Andromeda caerulea* L., Sp. Pl.: 393 (1753)
- *Bryanthus coeruleus* (L.) Dippel, Handb. Laubholzk.: 1: 385 (1889)

255 There are no herbarium specimens to confirm this record of *H. monotropa* from Iceland.

256 Results of recent phylogenetic studies showed that *Loiseleuria* belongs within *Kalmia* (Kron et al., 2002) and this view has been broadly accepted.

257 Gröntved (1942) mentioned one specimen of *M. uniflora* from herbarium C and labelled as "Reynistaðir. P. Briem ded. M. Halldórsson Friðriksson". It is difficult to say whether this collection was actually made in Iceland or mislabelled. The species has never been found growing in Iceland since the above-mentioned collection.

Pyrola grandiflora Radius²⁵⁸

Pyrola & Chimophila: 27 (1821)

Bjöllulilja

- *Pyrola rotundifolia* auct. non L. (1753)

 ▼ *Pyrola media* Sw.²⁵⁹

Kongl. Vetensk. Acad. Nya Handl. 25: 263 (1804)

Móaklukkublóm

- by Mohr (1786)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Bisiker (1902)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Pyrola minor L.²⁶⁰

Sp. Pl.: 396 (1753)

Pyrola minor var. ***conferta*** (Fisch. ex Cham. & Schltl.) A.P. Khokhr.

Sosud. Rast. Sovet. Dalnego Vostoka 5: 161 (1991)

Klukkublóm

- *Pyrola conferta* Fisch. ex Cham. & Schltl., Linnaea 1: 514 (1826)

 ▼ *Rhododendron lapponicum* (L.) Wahlenb.²⁶¹

Fl. Lapp.: 104 (1812)

Svarðlyngrós

- by Vahl (1840)
- by Baring-Gould (1863)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Rostrup (1887)
- by Bennett (1890)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

 ▼ *Rhododendron tomentosum* (Stokes) Harmaja²⁶²

Ann. Bot. Fenn. 27: 204 (1990)

Mýraflóki

- by Vahl (1840) as *Ledum latifolium*
- by Babington (1871) as *Ledum palustre*
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Vaccinium myrtillus L.

Sp. Pl.: 349 (1753)

Aðalbláberjalyng

258 It is not clear whether Icelandic plants belong to subsp. *grandiflora* or subsp. *norvegica* (Knaben) Á. Löve & D. Löve. Hulten and Fries (1986) assigned Icelandic material to subsp. *norvegica*, while Elven et al. (2011), although not without some doubts, classified Icelandic plants within subsp. *grandiflora*. Further studies are needed to elucidate this problem.

259 The records of *P. media* from Iceland most probably constitute a misidentification of *P. grandiflora* or *P. minor*.

260 The presence of an arctic-alpine race within *P. minor* has been debated and low-grown arctic (alpine) plants with less numerous flowers, with mostly a strong pink-red colour, and upper stem leaves broadly lanceolate to ovate with several veins were proposed to be classified as var. *conferta* (Elven et al., 2011). All Icelandic material was classified within var. *conferta* by Elven et al. (2011). It has to be determined, however, whether *P. minor* s. str. occurs in Iceland or not. Further research is needed to elucidate this question.

261 *R. lapponicum* was included in some old lists, but complete lack of more recent records as well as specimens in herbaria makes its presence questionable.

262 Some early authors record *R. tomentosum* species as native to Iceland and Gröntved (1942) cites herbarium specimens kept in H and annotated as "ex Islandia Steenstrup". There are no recent records to confirm the presence of the species in Iceland.

Vaccinium uliginosum L.

Sp. Pl.: 350 (1753)

Vaccinium uliginosum L. subsp. **uliginosum**²⁶³

Bláberjalyng

Vaccinium vitis-idaea L.

Sp. Pl.: 351 (1753)

Vaccinium vitis-idaea L. subsp. **vitis-idaea**

Rauðberjalyng

RUBIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 196 (1789), nom. cons.

○ *Asperula orientalis* Boiss. & Hohen

Diagn. Pl. Orient. 3: 30 (1843)

Heiðsnerpa

○ *Galium aparine* L.

Sp. Pl.: 108 (1753)

Krókamaðra

Galium boreale L.

Sp. Pl.: 108 (1753)

Krossmaðra

○ *Galium album* Mill

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: no. 7 (1768)

Ljósamaðra

– *Galium mollugo* subsp. *erectum* Syme, Engl. Bot., ed. 3B, 4: 217 (1865)**Galium normanii** O.C. Dahl

Skr. Vidensk.-Selsk. Christiania 1914, Math.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 4: 136 (1915)

Hvítmaðra

– *Galium pumilum* subsp. *islandicum* Sterner, Acta Horti Gothob. 15: 213 (1944)– *Galium normanii* var. *islandicum* (Sterner) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 301 (1970)– *Galium sylvestre* auct. non Pollich (1776), nom. illeg.– *Galium pusillum* auct. non L.– *Galium saxatile* auct. non L.○ *Galium odoratum* (L.) Scop.

Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 1: 105 (1771)

Anganmaðra (Ilmmaðra)

Galium palustre L.

Sp. Pl.: 105 (1753)

Mýramaðra

²⁶³ There are five genetic groups and three main lineages within *Vaccinium uliginosum* (Alsos et al. 2002, 2005, Elven et al. 2011). These groups are also supported by morphological differences, partially by ploidy levels and have different distribution patterns. In Iceland an octoploid, boreal-temperate, amphi-Atlantic lineage is predominant. This lineage has been classified as subsp. *uliginosum*. On the other hand the presence of another lineage: tetraploid, circumpolar and arctic-alpine subsp. *microphyllum* (Lange) Tolm. [≡ ?*Vaccinium gaultherioides* Bigelow, New Engl. J. Med. Surg. 5: 335 (1816)] has been suggested from Iceland by Elven et al. (2011). Apparently, more research on Icelandic material is needed to confirm or reject this suggestion.

***Galium trifidum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 105 (1753)

Galium trifidum* L. subsp. *trifidum

brenningarmaðra

- *Galium brandegeei* A. Gray, Proc. Amer. Acad. Arts 12: 58 (1877)
- *Galium ruprechtii* Pobed., Fl. URSS 23: 335, 713 (1958)
- *Galium brevipes* auct. non Fernald & Wiegand (1910)
- *Galium trifidum* subsp. *brevipes* auct. non Á. Löve & D. Löve (1982)

***Galium uliginosum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 106 (1753)

Laugamaðra

***Galium verum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 107 (1753)

Gulmaðra

○ *Sherardia arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 102 (1753)

Blámaðra

GENTIANACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 141 (1789), nom. cons.

Maríuvandarætt

▼ *Blackstonia perfoliata* (L.) Huds.²⁶⁴

Fl. Angl.: 146 (1762)

Gullhúfa

- by Bennett (1890) as *Chlora perfoliata*
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Centaurium erythraea* Rafn²⁶⁵

Danm. Holst. Fl. 2: 75 (1800)

Dvalinblómskúfur

- by Bennett (1890) as *Erythraea centaurium*
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Comastoma tenellum* (Rottb.) Toyok.**

Bot. Mag. (Tokyo) 74: 198 (1961)

Maríuvendlingur

- *Gentiana tenella* Rottb., Skr. Kiøbenhavnske Selsk. Lærd. Elsk. 10: 436 (1770)
- *Gentianella tenella* (Rottb.) Börner, Fl. Deut. Volk: 542 (1912)

***Gentiana nivalis* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 229 (1753)

Dýragras

- *Hippion nivale* (L.) F.W. Schmidt, Fl. Boëm. 2: 18 (1793 1794)
- *Calathiana nivalis* (L.) Delarbre, Fl. Auvergne, ed. 2: 28 (1800)

264 There is no evidence available to confirm the old records of *B. perfoliata* and the occurrence of this southern species seems very unlikely in Iceland.

265 It is very unlikely that old records of *C. erythraea* from Iceland are based on actual findings. There are no collections available to confirm these records.

▼ *Gentiana pneumonanthe* L.²⁶⁶

Sp. Pl.: 228 (1753)

Bjölluvöndur

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

▼ *Gentiana verna* L.²⁶⁷

Sp. Pl.: 228 (1753)

Vorvöndur

- by Olavius (1780)
- by Mohr (1786)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Bennett (1890)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

Gentianella amarella (L.) Börner

Fl. Deut. Volk: 542 (1912)

- *Gentiana amarella* L., Sp. Pl.: 230 (1753)

Gentianella amarella subsp. ***septentrionalis*** (Druce) N.M. Pritch.

Watsonia 4: 235 (1960)

Grænvöndur

- *Gentiana amarella* var. *septentrionalis* Druce, Bot. Soc. Exch. Club Brit. Isles 6: 505 (1922)
- *Gentianella septentrionalis* (Druce) E.F. Warb. in A.R. Clapham, Tutin & E.F. Warb., Fl. Brit. Isl.: 825 (1952)

Gentianella aurea (L.) Harry Sm.

Nomenkl. Stud. Nord. Gefässpfl.: 259 (1945)

Gullvöndur

- *Gentiana aurea* L., Syst. Nat., ed. 10, 2: 951 (1759)
- *Gentiana quinquefolia* Oeder, Fl. Dan. t. 344 (1765)
- *Gentiana involucreta* Rottb., Kiob. Skr. Selsk. 10: 434 (1770)
- *Arctogentia aurea* (L.) Á. Löve, Phytologia 50(3): 172. (1982)
- *Aloitis aurea* (L.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Taxon 34: 164 (1985)

Gentianella campestris (L.) Börner

Fl. Deut. Volk: 542 (1912)

- *Gentiana campestris* L. Sp. Pl.: 231 (1753)

Gentianella campestris subsp. ***islandica*** (Murb.) Vollm.

Fl. Bayern: 598 (1914)

Maríuvöndur

- *Gentiana campestris* var. *islandica* Murb., Acta Hort. Berg. 2, 3: 10 (1892)
- *Gentiana islandica* (Murb.) Dörf., Herb. Norm. 38: 269 (1898)
- *Gentianella campestris* var. *islandica* (Murb.) Harry Sm. in Hyl., Nomenkl. Stud. Nord. Gefässpfl.: 259 (1945)

266 There are just few and very doubtful records of *G. pneumonanthe* by some early authors. These records have never been confirmed by more recent studies.

267 *G. verna* was recorded by Olavius at Reykjalaug, which is most probably a misidentification. There are no specimens available to confirm this record.

Gentianopsis detonsa (Rottb.) Ma

Acta Phytotax. Sin. 1: 15 (1951)

Engjavöndur

- *Gentiana detonsa* Rottb., Skr. Kiøbenhavnske Selsk. Lærd. Elsk. 10: 435 (1770)
- *Gentiana serrata* (Borckh.) Gunn., Fl. Norveg. 2: 101 (1772)
- *Gentianella detonsa* (Rottb.) G. Don, Gen. Hist. 4: 179 (1837–1838)
- *Gentiana bavarica* auct. non. L. (1753)
- *Gentiana ciliata* auct. non. L. (1753)

Lomatogonium rotatum (L.) Fr. ex Fernald

Rhodora 21: 194 (1919)

- *Swertia rotata* L., Sp. Pl.: 226 (1753)
- *Pleurogyne rotata* (L.) Griseb., Gen. Sp. Gent. 309 (1838)

Lomatogonium rotatum (L.) Fr. ex Fernald subsp. ***rotatum***

Blástjarna

BORAGINACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 128 (1789), nom. cons.

Munablómsætt

○ *Asperugo procumbens* L.

Sp. Pl.: 138 (1753)

Klóajurt

○ *Borago officinalis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 137 (1753)

Hjólkróna

○ *Cynoglossum officinale* L.

Sp. Pl.: 134 (1753)

Hundatunga

○ *Echium vulgare* L.

Sp. Pl.: 139 (1753)

Naðurkollur

○ *Lappula marginata* (M. Bieb.) Gürke

Nat. Pflanzenfam. 4(3a): 107 (1893)

○ *Lappula squarrosa* (Retz.) Dumort.

Fl. Belg.: 40 (1827)

Íguljurt

- *Lappula myosotis* Moench, Methodus: 417 (1794)

- *Lappula echinata* (L.) Gilib., Fl. Lit. Inch. 1: 25 (1782)

○ *Lycopsis arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 139 (1753)

Akurtunga (Uxajurt)

- *Anchusa arvensis* (L.) M. Bieb., Fl. Taur.-Caucas. 1: 123 (1808)

Mertensia maritima (L.) Gray

Nat. Arr. Brit. Pl. 2: 354 (1821)

- *Pulmonaria maritima* L., Sp. Pl.: 136 (1753)
- *Stenhammaria maritima* Rchb.

Mertensia maritima (L.) Gray subsp. ***maritima***²⁶⁸

Blálilja

▼ *Myosotis alpestris* F.W. Schmidt²⁶⁹

Fl. Bohem. Inch. 3: 26 (1794)

Bergmunablóm

- by Bennett (1886)

◆ *Myosotis arvensis* (L.) Hill²⁷⁰

Veg. Syst. 7: 55 (1764)

Gleym-mér-ei

- *Myosotis scorpioides* var. *arvensis* L., Sp. Pl.: 131 (1753)

▼ *Myosotis ramosissima* Rochel²⁷¹

Österr. Fl. ed. 2, 1: 366 (1814)

Dvergmunablóm

- by Hjaltalín (1830) as *Myosotis collina*
- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Stefánsson (1901)
- by Stefánsson (1948) as *Myosotis hispida*
- by Gröntved (1942)

► *Myosotis discolor* Pers. ex Murray²⁷²

Syst. Veg. (ed. 15): 190 (1797/98)

Kisugras

- ? *Myosotis versicolor* sensu Grønlund (1881)

● *Myosotis scorpioides* L.

Sp. Pl.: 131 (1753)

Engjamunablóm

- *Myosotis scorpioides* var. *palustris* L., Sp. Pl.: 131 (1753)
- *Myosotis palustris* (L.) L., Fl. Monsp.: 11 (1756)

Myosotis stricta Link ex Roem. & Schult.

Syst. Veg. 4: 104 (1819)

Sandmunablóm

- *Myosotis micrantha* Pall. ex Lehm., Neue Schr. Naturf. Ges. Halle, 3: II. 24 (1817)
- *Myosotis arenaria* Schrad., Prod. Fl. Starg. Suppl. 1: 12 (1819)

268 There are three subspecies within *M. maritima*: (1) subsp. *maritima* - distributed in the boreal to subarctic N Atlantic, (2) subsp. *tenella* (Th. Fr.) Elven & Skarpaas - distributed in the Arctic from Chukotka across N America and Greenland to Svalbard, and (3) subsp. *asiatica* Takeda distributed in the N Pacific (Skarpaas et al. 2004).

269 *M. alpestris* has been recorded just once by Bennet and never confirmed again. Most probably a misidentification.

270 *M. arvensis* is an archaeophyte in Iceland - see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

271 *M. ramosissima* was recorded several times by early authors from very few locations, but never recorded by more recent authors. There are no specimens to confirm old records.

272 *M. discolor* is most probably a non-native taxon of unknown age - see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

- *Myosotis sylvatica* Ehrh. ex Hoffm.
Deut. Fl. 1: 61 (1791)
Skógmunablóm

- *Pulmonaria mollis* Hornem.²⁷³
Hort. Bot. Hafn.: 179 (1813)
Floslyfjurt

- *Symphytum asperum* Lepechin
Nova Acta Acad. Sci. Petrop. 14: 442 (1805)
Burstavalurt

- *Symphytum officinale* L.
Sp. Pl.: 136 (1753)
Valurt

CONVOLVULACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 132 (1789), nom. cons.
Vafklukkuætt

- *Calystegia sepium* (L.) R. Br.
Prodr.: 483 (1810)
Maríuvafklukka

- *Convolvulus arvensis* L.
Sp. Pl.: 153 (1753)
Akurvafklukka

- *Cuscuta campestris* Yunck.
Mem. Torrey Bot. Club 18(2): 138 (1932)
Vafsníkja

SOLANACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 124 (1789), nom. cons.
Náttskuggaætt

- *Solanum nigrum* L.
Sp. Pl.: 186 (1753)
Húmskuggi

²⁷³ For more information on this recently registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

PLANTAGINACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 89 (1789), nom. cons.

Græðisúruætt

Callitriche brutia Petagna²⁷⁴

Inst. Bot. 2: 10 (1787)

Callitriche brutia Petagna var. ***brutia***

Inst. Bot. 2: 10 (1787)

Lækjabrúða

– *Callitriche pedunculata* DC., Fl. Franç., ed. 3, 4: 415 (1805)– *Callitriche hamulata* var. *pendunculata* (DC.) Bab., Man. Brit. Bot., ed. 5: 294 (1862)***Callitriche brutia*** var. ***hamulata*** (Kütz. ex W.D.J. Koch) Lansdown

Watsonia 26: 113 (2006)

Síkjabrúða

– *Callitriche hamulata* Kütz. ex W.D.J. Koch, Syn. Fl. Germ. Helv.: 246 (1835)– *Callitriche brutia* subsp. *hamulata* (Kütz. ex Koch) O. Bolos & Vigo, But. Inst. Catalana Hist. Nat. 38 Bot. 1: 85 (1974)– ? *Callitriche intermedia* Hoffm.***Callitriche hermaphroditica*** L.

Cent. Pl. 1: 31 (1755 Febr.)

Haustbrúða

– *Callitriche autumnalis* L., Fl. Suec., ed. 2: 2 (1755 Oct.)²⁷⁵***Callitriche palustris*** L.

Sp. Pl.: 969 (1753)

Vorbrúða

– *Callitriche verna* L., Fl. Suec., ed. 2: 2 (1755)***Callitriche stagnalis*** Scop.

Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 2: 251 (1772)

Laugabrúða

Hippuris lanceolata Retz.²⁷⁶

Observ. Bot. 3: 7 (1783)

Lensulófótur

Hippuris tetraphylla L. f.

Suppl. Pl.: 81 (1782)

Flæðalófótur

– *Hippuris vulgaris* f. *maritima* Hell.

274 Löve (1983) and Kristinsson (2008) recognised two separate species from Iceland: *C. brutia* Petagna and *C. hamulata* Kütz. ex. Koch. These two taxa are without a doubt very closely related and it seems that they are not reliably distinguishable neither in the field nor herbarium except under very specific environmental conditions when *C. brutia* is able to produce its long-pedunculate fruits (Lansdown 2006). Given the fact that only some plants are able to produce long-pedunculate fruits when they become terrestrial and different chromosome numbers in both groups they are currently recognised as two separate subspecies (i Bonada and i Capdevila 1974) or varieties (Lansdown 2006). Here the latter option was followed.

275 In Stefánsson (1901) referred to as *C. "auctumnalis"*.

276 Some authors treat *H. lanceolata* as a hybrid between *H. tetraphylla* and *H. vulgaris*. Here we follow a view of Elven et al. (2011), who gives good reasons to recognise *H. vulgaris*, *H. lanceolata* and *H. tetraphylla* as three distinct and morphologically non-overlapping taxa.

***Hippuris vulgaris* L.**²⁷⁷

Sp. Pl.: 4 (1753)

Lófótur

***Littorella uniflora* (L.) Asch.**

Fl. Brandenburg 1, 2: 544 (1864)

Tjarnalaukur

– *Plantago uniflora* L., Sp. Pl.: 115 (1753)– *Littorella lacustris* L., Mant. Pl. 2: 295 (1771)○ *Linaria repens* (L.) Mill.

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: no. 6 (1768)

Randagin

– *Antirrhinum repens* L., Sp. Pl.: 614 (1753)○ *Linaria vulgaris* Mill.

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: no. 1 (1768)

Gullgin

○ *Plantago arenaria* Waldst. & Kit.

Descr. Icon. Pl. Hung.: 51 (1801)

Sandtungu

– *Plantago indica* L., Syst. Nat. ed. 10, 2: 896 (1759)▼ ***Plantago coronopus* L.**²⁷⁸

Sp. Pl.: 115 (1753)

Flipatunga

– by König and Müller (1770)

– by Vahl (1840)

– by Babington (1871)

– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

***Plantago lanceolata* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 113 (1753)

Selgresi

■ ***Plantago major* L.**²⁷⁹

Sp. Pl.: 112 (1753)

Græðisúra

277 In Iceland three taxa from *Hippuris* are present. All of them belong to *Hippuris vulgaris* aggregate and are most probably very closely related. Taxa present in Iceland differ in leaf shape and number (*H. lanceolata* – 6 broadly linear or narrowly oblong subacute to subobtuse leaves per whorl; *H. tetraphylla* – 4 oblong to broadly oblong, obtuse to sometimes emarginate leaves per whorl; *H. vulgaris* – 8 linear or very narrowly lanceolate and acute leaves per whorl) in stamens morphology (*H. lanceolata* – stamen is sessile on the perianth with a filament about as long as or shorter than the anther; *H. tetraphylla* – stamen as in *H. lanceolata*; *H. vulgaris* – single stamen is well exerted from the perianth with filament much longer than the anther) and in ecological requirements (*H. lanceolata* – in both brackish water and freshwater; *H. tetraphylla* – restricted to brackish waters; *H. vulgaris* – usually a freshwater species but when found in brackish water it retains morphological characteristics).

278 *P. coronopus* was recorded by König and Müller (1770) and copied by most of the early authors. The species has never been confirmed later based on collections.

279 *P. major* is a doubtfully native species – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

***Plantago maritima* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 114 (1753)

Kattartunga

- *Plantago maritima* var. *glauca* Hornem., Fors. Oecon. Plantel., ed. 3, 1: 167 (1821)
- *Plantago juncooides* var. *glauca* (Hornem.) Fernald, Rhodora 27: 101 (1925)
- *Plantago borealis* Lange, Fl. Dan. 16, 46: 5 (1867)
- *Plantago maritima* subsp. *borealis* (Lange) A. Blytt & O.C. Dahl, Haandb. Norges Fl.: 651 (1906 1905)
- *Plantago maritima* subsp. *juncooides* Hultén, Acta Univ. Lund., n.s., sect. 2, 45, 1: 1431 (1949)
- *Plantago juncooides* auct. non Lam. (1792)
- *Plantago alpina* auct. non L. (1753)

▼ ***Plantago media* L.**²⁸⁰

Sp. Pl.: 113 (1753)

Loðtunga

- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Bennett (1896)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Veronica agrestis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 13 (1753)

Akurdepla

***Veronica alpina* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 11 (1753)

Fjalladepla

Veronica alpina* L. subsp. *alpina***Veronica alpina* subsp. *pumila* (All.) Pennell**

Rhodora 23: 14 (1921)

- *Veronica pumila* All., Fl. Pedem. 1: 75 (1785)
- *Veronica alpina* var. *australis* Wahlenb., Fl. Carpat. Princ.: 5 (1814)
- *Veronica alpina* subsp. *australis* (Wahlenb.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Acta Horti Gothob. 20(4): 148 (1956)

***Veronica anagallis-aquatica* L.**²⁸¹

Sp. Pl.: 12 (1753)

Laugadepla

- *Veronica aquatica* Benquerel, Neuch. Bull. 5: 1859 (1861)

○ *Veronica arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 13 (1753)

Reykjadepla

- ? *Pocilla arvensis* sensu Löve (1983)

280 *P. media* was recorded by some of the early authors. There are no specimens available and the species has never been recorded by some more contemporary studies.

281 *V. anagallis-aquatica* in Stefánsson (1901) is mentioned under the name of *Veronica anagallis*.

▼ *Veronica beccabunga* L.²⁸²

Sp. Pl.: 12 (1753)

Safadepla

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- by Grønlund (1881)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

 ● *Veronica chamaedrys* L.

Sp. Pl.: 13 (1753)

Völudepla

- *Veronicella chamaedrys* (L.) Fourr., Ann. Soc. L. Lyon, N.s. 17: 128 (1869)

Veronica fruticans Jacq.

Enum. Stirp. Vindob.: 200 (1762)

Steindepla

- *Veronica saxatilis* Scop., Fl. Carn. ed. II. 1: 11 (1771)
- *Petrodora "fruticans"* sensu Löve (1983), non *Petrodora fruticulosa* (L.) Fourr.
- ? *Veronica fruticulosa* auct. non L. (1762)

 ○ *Veronica gentianoides* Vahl

Symb. Bot. 1: 1 (1790)

Kósakkadepla

 ○ *Veronica hederifolia* L.

Sp. Pl.: 13 (1753)

Bergfléttudepla

 ○ *Veronica longifolia* L.

Sp. Pl.: 10 (1753)

Langdepla

Veronica officinalis L.

Sp. Pl.: 11 (1753)

Hárdepla

 ▼ *Veronica peregrina* L.²⁸³

Sp. Pl.: 14 (1753)

Ameríkudepla

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Veronica marilandica*
- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

 ● *Veronica persica* Poir.

Encycl. 8: 542 (1808)

Varmadepla

- *Veronica tournefortii* C.C. Gmelin, Fl. Bad. 1: 39 (1805)
- *Pocilla persica* (Poir.) Fourr., Ann. Soc. L. Lyon, N.s. 17: 129 (1869)

282 *V. beccabunga* was recorded by some of the early authors. These records are most probably due to a mistake or misidentification.

283 *V. peregrina* was recorded from Iceland by some of the early botanists. There are no specimens to confirm these records.

***Veronica scutellata* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 12 (1753)

Skriðdepla

◆ *Veronica serpyllifolia* L.²⁸⁴

Sp. Pl.: 12 (1753)

Lækjadepla

- *Veronicastrum serpyllifolium* (L.) Fourr., Ann. Soc. Linn. Lyon, sér. 2, 17: 128 (1869)
- *Veronica serpyllifolia* var. *nummularioides* Lecoq & Lamotte

▼ *Veronica spicata* L.²⁸⁵

Sp. Pl.: 10 (1753)

Axdepla

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

SCROPHULARIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 117 (1789), nom. cons.

Hnúðrótarátt

○ *Digitalis purpurea* L.

Sp. Pl.: 621 (1753)

Fingurbjargarblóm

***Limosella aquatica* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 631 (1753)

Efjugras

LENTIBULARIACEAE Lindl.

Fl. Paris. [Poiteau & Turpin] 1: 23 (ed. fol.), 26 (ed. qto.) (1808), nom. cons.

Blöðrujurtarátt

▼ *Pinguicula alpina* L.²⁸⁶

Sp. Pl.: 17 (1753)

Fjallalyfjagras

- by Mohr (1786)
- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)
- by Baring-Gould (1863)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

***Pinguicula vulgaris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 17 (1753)

Lyfjagras

284 *V. serpyllifolia* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

285 *V. spicata* was recorded from Iceland by some 19th century botanists. There are no specimens available to confirm these records.

286 *P. alpina* was recorded by some of the early authors and several localities are given. There are, however, no specimens available and the species has never been confirmed later.

***Utricularia minor* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 18 (1753)

Blöðrujurt

LAMIACEAE Martinov (= Labiatae Juss. nom. cons.)

Tekhno-Bot. Slovar 355. (1820), nom. cons.

Varablómaætt

***Ajuga pyramidalis* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 561 (1753)

Lyngbúi

○ *Nepeta sibirica* L.

Sp. Pl.: 572 (1753)

Högnanípa

– *Dracocephalum sibiricum* (L.) L., Syst. Nat. ed. 10, 2: 1104 (1759)

○ *Galeopsis bifida* Boenn.

Prodr. Fl. Monast. Westphal.: 178 (1824)

Skoruhjálmgas

○ *Galeopsis ladanum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 579 (1753)

Engjahjálmgas

○ *Galeopsis speciosa* Mill.

Gard. Dict., ed. 8: Galeopsis no. 3 (1768)

Gullhjálmgas

● *Galeopsis tetrahit* L.

Sp. Pl.: 579 (1753)

Garðahjálmgas

Lamium album L.

Sp. Pl.: 579 (1753)

● *Lamium album* L. subsp. *album*

Ljósatvítönn

● *Lamium amplexicaule* L.

Sp. Pl.: 579 (1753)

Varpátvítönn

○ *Lamium confertum* Fr.

Summa Veg. Scand.: 15, 198

Garðatvítönn

– *Lamium intermedium* Fr., Novit. Fl. Svec.: 105 (1823), nom. illeg.

– ? *Lamium moluccellifolium* auct. non Fr. (1819)

Lamium purpureum L.

Sp. Pl.: 579 (1753)

- *Lamium purpureum* L. subsp. *purpureum*

Sp. Pl.: 579 (1753)

Akurtvítönn

- *Lamium purpureum* subsp. *hybridum* (Vill.) Vill.

Hist. Pl. Dauphiné 2: 385 (1787)

Flípatvítönn

- *Lamium hybridum* Vill., Hist. Pl. Dauphiné 1: 251 (1786)

- *Mentha aquatica* L.

Sp. Pl.: 576 (1753)

Vatnamynta

- *Mentha arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 577 (1753)

Akurmynta

- *Mentha* × *gentilis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 577 (1753)

Engjamynta

- *Mentha* × *gracilis* Sole, Menth. Brit. 37, pl. 16 (1798)

- *Mentha longifolia* (L.) Huds.

Fl. Angl.: 221 (1762)

Rósamynta (Grámynta)

- *Mentha spicata* var. *longifoila* L., Sp. Pl.: 576 (1753)

- *Mentha spicata* L.

Sp. Pl.: 576 (1753)

Hrokkinmynta (Garðmynta)

***Prunella vulgaris* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 600 (1753)

- *Prunella officinalis* Crantz, Stirp. Austr. Fasc., ed. 2, 2: 279 (1769)

- *Brunella vulgaris* (L.) Moench

Prunella vulgaris* L. subsp. *vulgaris

Blákolla

- *Stachys macrantha* (K. Koch) Stearn

Gard. Chron. III, 130: 169 (1951)

Álfakollur

- *Betonica macrantha* K. Koch, Linnaea 21: 683 (1849)

Thymus praecox Opiz

Naturalientausch 6: 40 (1824)

Thymus praecox subsp. ***arcticus*** (Durand) Jalas²⁸⁷

Veröff. Geobot. Inst. ETH Stiftung Rübel Zürich 43: 190 (1970)

Blóðberg

- *Thymus serpyllum* var. *arcticus* Durand in Kane, Arct. Explor. 1853–55, App. 18: 459 (1856)
- *Thymus serpyllum* var. *prostratus* Hornem. ex Lange, Consp. Fl. Groenland. 1: 81 (1880)
- *Thymus arcticus* (Durand) Ronniger, Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 20: 331, 237 (1924)
- *Thymus drucei* Ronniger, Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 20: 328 (1924)
- *Thymus britannicus* Ronniger, Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 20: 330 (1924)
- *Thymus praecox* subsp. *britannicus* (Ronniger) Holub, Preslia 45: 359 (1973)
- *Thymus polytrichus* subsp. *britannicus* (Ronniger) Kerguélen, Lejeunia, n.s., 120: 175 (1987)

PHRYMACEAE Schauer

Prodr. [A.P. de Candolle] 11: 520 (1847), nom. cons.

Lotaldinætt

- *Mimulus guttatus* DC.

Cat. Pl. Horti Monsp.: 127 (1813)

Apablóm

OROBANCHACEAE Vent.

Tabl. Regn. Vég. 2: 292 (1799), nom. cons.

Sníkjujurtaætt

Bartsia alpina L.

Sp. Pl.: 602 (1753)

Smjörgras

Euphrasia L.²⁸⁸

Sp. Pl.: 604 (1753)

- * ***Euphrasia arctica*** Lange ex Rostr.²⁸⁹

Bot. Tidsskr. 1, 4: 47 (1870–1871)

287 *T. praecox* subsp. *arcticus* has rather limited distribution covering the British Isles, western part of Norway, Iceland (very common), and the southern part of Greenland (Hulten and Fries 1986, Elven et al. 2011). It is the only member of *Lamiaceae* with a significant part of its range in the Arctic (Elven et al., 2011). Views on its taxonomy are conflicting. Some authors claim that the taxon should be treated as a subspecies and assigned to *T. praecox* Opiz, while some other place it in *T. polytrichus* A. Kerner [see discussion in Elven et al. (2011)]. Here, a provisional solution accepted by Kristinsson (2008) and Elven et al. (2011) is followed.

288 The taxonomy of *Euphrasia* in Iceland is complex and very poorly understood. Therefore, the present treatment should be considered provisional. There are different views on the number of species present in Iceland. Pugsley (1933) accepted numerous, very narrowly circumscribed species, Yeo (1972) accepted six species ($\equiv E. arctica$ subsp. *tenuis* [$\equiv E. stricta$ var. *tenuis* or *E. tenuis*], *E. calida* Yeo - Icelandic endemic confined to geothermal sites, *E. davidssonii* Pugsley - Icelandic endemic, *E. frigida* auct. [$\equiv E. wettsteini$], *E. ostenfeldii* (Pugsley) Yeo and *E. scottica*), while Löve (1970) accepted three (*E. brevipila* [$\equiv E. stricta$], *E. curta* [$\equiv E. parviflora$] var. *davidssonii* (Pugsley) Á. Löve, and *E. frigida* auct. with subsp. *frigida* [$\equiv E. wettsteini$] and subsp. *rotundifolia* (Pugsley) Á. Löve. Here, the species list accepted by Kristinsson (2008) is repeated and supplemented with recent findings by Elven et al. (2011). There is no doubt that modern revision of the genus from Iceland is very needed.

289 *E. arctica* was accepted by Elven et al. (2011) from northern Iceland.

* ***Euphrasia calida*** Yeo²⁹⁰

Bot. Jour. L. Soc. 64: 359 (1971)

Hveraugnfró

* ***Euphrasia stricta*** D. Wolff ex J.F. Lehm.

Prim. Fl. Herbip.: 43 (1809)

Kirtilaugnfró

– *Euphrasia brevipila* Burnat & Grebli ex Wettst., Oesterr. Bot. Z. 44: 92 (1894)

* ***Euphrasia wettsteinii*** G. Gusarova²⁹¹

Bot. Zhurn. 89: 1103–1104 (2005)

Augnfró

– *Euphrasia officinalis* auct. non. L. (1753)

– *Euphrasia arctica* auct. non Lange ex Rostr. (1870–1871)

– *Euphrasia frigida* auct. non Pugsley (1930)

– *Euphrasia latifolia* sensu Stefánsson (1901) non L. (1753)

– ? *Euphrasia curta* sensu Grøntved (1942)

Melampyrum pratense L.²⁹²

Sp. Pl.: 605 (1753)

Engjakambjurt

Melampyrum sylvaticum L.

Sp. Pl.: 605 (1753)

Krossjurt

Pedicularis flammea L.

Sp. Pl.: 609 (1753)

Tröllastakkur

– *Pedicularis versicolor* auct. non Wahlenb.

– *Pedicularis oederi* auct. non Vahl

▼ ***Pedicularis palustris*** L.²⁹³

Sp. Pl. 607 (1753)

Mýrastakkur

– by Baring-Gould (1863)

– by Babington (1871)

– by Grønlund (1881)

– rejected by Grøntved (1942)

290 Species endemic to Iceland accepted by Yeo (1972) and Kristinsson (2008).

291 This common eglandular, small-flowered plant has for long been referred to as *Euphrasia frigida* (e.g. Löve (1983), Kristinsson (2008)). Recently, it became clear that this name, based on the type specimen from Greenland (Elven et al. 2011) has been misapplied to Icelandic plants.

292 *M. pratense* was recently found to be present in Iceland. It seems that the species should be considered native (Wasowicz et al. 2018).

293 *P. palustris* has been recorded by Baring-Gould from Miklibær (N Iceland) most probably due to a mistake. Subsequently, this record was copied by some of the early authors.

▼ *Pedicularis sylvatica* L.²⁹⁴

Sp. Pl.: 607 (1753)

Skógarstakkur

- by König and Müller (1770)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

○ *Rhinanthus angustifolius* C.C. Gmelin

Fl. Bad. 2: 669 (1806)

Meyjarsjóður

***Rhinanthus minor* L.**

Amoen. Acad. 3: 54 (1756)

Lokasjóður

- *Rhinanthus crista-galli* L., Sp. Pl. 603 (1753)
- *Rhinanthus glaber* Lam., Fl. Franc. 2: 352 (1778)
- *Alectorolophus minor* (L.) Wimm. & Grab., Fl. Siles. 2(1): 213 (1829)
- *Rhinanthus major* auct. non. Ehrh. (1791), non L. (1753)

Rhinanthus minor* L. subsp. *minor***Rhinanthus minor* subsp. *groenlandicus*** (Ostenf.) Neuman, Bot. Not. 1905: 257 (1905)

- *Alectorolophus groenlandicus* Ostenf., Phan. Pterid. Faeroes: 51 (1891)
- *Rhinanthus groenlandicus* (Ostenf.) Chabert, Bull. Herb. Boissier 7: 511 (1899)
- *Rhinanthus groenlandicus* var. *drummond-hayi* (Buchanan-White) Ostenf.

CAMPANULACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 163 (1789), nom. cons.

Bláklukkuætt

○ *Campanula fragilis* Cirillo

Pl. Rar. Neapol. 1: 32 (1788)

Skrúðsklukka

● *Campanula glomerata* L.

Sp. Pl.: 166 (1753)

Höfuðklukka

○ *Campanula latifolia* L.

Sp. Pl.: 165 (1753)

Risaklukka

○ *Campanula patula* L.

Sp. Pl.: 163 (1753)

Vallarklukka

²⁹⁴ *P. sylvatica* was mentioned by König and Müller (1770) and then copied by some of the early authors. The species has never been confirmed later and it is rather unlikely that it occurs in Iceland.

***Campanula rotundifolia* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 163 (1753)

***Campanula rotundifolia* L. subsp. *rotundifolia*²⁹⁵**

Bláklukka

- *Campanula rotundifolia* subsp. *groenlandica* sensu Löve (1983), non Á. Löve & D. Löve (1986)

***Campanula uniflora* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 163 (1753)

Fjallabláklukka

MENYANTHACEAE Dumort.

Anal. Fam. Pl. 20, 25 (1829), nom. cons.

Horblöðkuætt

***Menyanthes trifoliata* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 145 (1753)

Horblaðka

▼ *Nymphoides peltata* (S.G. Gmelin) O. Kuntze²⁹⁶

Rev. Gen. Pl. 1: 429 (1891)

Vatnanykurrós

- by Benguerel (1861) as *Villarsia nymphoides*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

ASTERACEAE Bercht. & J. Presl (= Compositae Giseke, nom. cons.)

Prir. Rostlin 254. (1820), nom. cons.

Körfublómaætt

***Achillea millefolium* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 899 (1753)

Vallhumall

Achillea millefolium* L. subsp. *millefolium***Achillea millefolium* subsp. *lanulosa* (Nutt.) Piper**

Fl. Washington: 584 (1906)

- *Achillea lanulosa* Nutt., J. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philadelphia 7: 36 (1834)

◆ *Achillea ptarmica* L.²⁹⁷

Sp. Pl.: 898 (1753)

Silfurhnappur

○ *Ambrosia artemisiifolia* L.

Sp. Pl.: 988 (1753)

Ömbrujurt

295 Icelandic *C. rotundifolia* conforms to European morphotype ("*rotundifolia*"). Löve (1983) assigned all Icelandic plants to "*groenlandica*" type, with very few and large flowers. It seems that this point of view cannot be sustained. However, it cannot be excluded that the "*groenlandica*" morphotype is present in Iceland. Further studies are needed to elucidate this problem.

296 *N. peltata* was recorded by some early authors and never confirmed again (most probably a mistake).

297 *A. ptarmica* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

Antennaria alpina (L.) Gaertn.

Fruct. Sem. Pl. 2, 3: 410 (1791)

- *Gnaphalium alpinum* L., Sp. Pl. 856 (1753)

- *Gnaphalium carpaticum* auct. non Wahl. (1833)

Antennaria alpina subsp. ***canescens*** (Lange) Chmiel.

Rhodora 100: 61 (1998)

Fjallalójur

- *Antennaria alpina* var. *canescens* Lange, Fl. Dan. 16, 47: 9, t. 2786, f. 1 (1869)

- *Antennaria canescens* (Lange) Malte, Rhodora 36: 109 (1934)

- *Antennaria canescens* subsp. *boecheriana* (A.E. Porsild) Á. Löve, Taxon 19: 301 (1970)

▼ *Antennaria dioica* (L.) Gaertn.²⁹⁸

Fruct. Sem. Pl. 2: 410 (1791)

Garðalójur

- by Olafsen and Povelsen (1772) as *Gnaphalium dioicum*

- by Gliemann (1824)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

○ *Anthemis arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 894 (1753)

Akurgæsajurt

▼ *Anthemis cotula* L.²⁹⁹

Sp. Pl.: 894 (1753)

Hnotgæsajurt

- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)

- by Baring-Gould (1863)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

○ *Anthemis tinctoria* L.

Sp. Pl.: 896 (1753)

Gullgæsajurt

○ *Artemisia vulgaris* L.

Sp. Pl.: 848 (1753)

Malurt

○ *Arnica chamissonis* Less.³⁰⁰

Linnaea 6: 238 (1831)

Klettagullblóm

● *Bellis perennis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 886 (1753)

Fagurfífill

298 There are no collections to confirm the presence of *A. dioica* in Iceland.

299 *A. cotula* was recorded by some of the 19th century botanists. There are no specimens to confirm these records and the species has never been found by contemporary botanists.

300 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

▼ *Carduus acanthoides* L.³⁰¹

Sp. Pl. 821 (1753)

Broddþistill

- by Gliemann (1824)
- by Vahl (1840)
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Carduus crispus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 821 (1753)

Hrukkupistill

○ *Centaurea jacea* L.

Sp. Pl.: 914 (1753)

Hnappakornblóm

○ *Centaurea scabiosa* L.

Sp. Pl.: 913 (1753)

Fagurkornblóm

◆ *Cirsium arvense* (L.) Scop.³⁰²

Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 2: 126 (1772)

Þistill

- *Carduus arvensis* Robs., Brit. Fl.: 163 (1777)

● *Cirsium heterophyllum* (L.) Hill

Hort. Kew.: 64 (1768)

Purpurapistill

- *Carduus heterophyllum* L., Sp. Pl.: 824 (1753)
- *Cirsium helenioides* auct. non Hill (1768)

○ *Cirsium palustre* (L.) Scop.

Fl. Carn., ed. 2, 2: 128 (1772)

Mýrapistill

▼ *Cirsium vulgare* (Savi) Ten.³⁰³

Fl. Nap. V: 209 (1835)

Risapistill

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Carduus lanceolatus*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

○ *Crepis capillaris* (L.) Wallr.

Linnaea 14(6): 657–658 (1840)

Fálkaskegg

- *Lapsana capillaris* L., Sp. Pl.: 812 (1753)

301 *Carduus acanthoides* was recorded from Iceland by Gliemann (1824) but this record was classified as doubtful even by the early authors. The species has never been confirmed from Iceland on the basis of collections.

302 *C. arvense* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

303 *C. vulgare* was recorded by almost all of the early authors, but actually never confirmed from Iceland by collections.

Crepis paludosa (L.) Moench

Methodus: 535 (1794)

Hjartafífill

- *Hieracium paludosum* L., Sp. Pl.: 803 (1753)
- *Aracium paludosum* Monnier, Ess. Monogr. Hieracium: 73 (1829)

▼ *Crepis praemorsa* Tausch³⁰⁴

Flora (Regensb.) 11 (Ergänz. 1): 79 (1828)

Haukaskegg

- by König and Müller (1770) as *Hieracium praemorsum*
- by Babington (1871)
- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

○ *Crepis tectorum* L.

Sp. Pl.: 807 (1753)

Valsskegg

○ *Cyanus segetum* (L.) Hill

Veg. Syst. 4: 29, pl. 26, fig. 3 (1762)

Garðakornblóm

- *Centaurea cyanus* L., Sp. Pl.: 911 (1753)

● *Cyanus montanus* (L.) Hill

Hort. Kew.: 64 (1768)

Fjallakornblóm

- *Centaurea montana* L., Sp. Pl.: 911 (1753)

○ *Cyanus triumfettii* (All.) Dostál ex Á. Löve & D. Löve

Bot. Not., Suppl. 114: 44 (1961)

Flauelskornblóm

- *Centaurea triumfettii* All., Auct. Syn. Stirp. Horti Taur. 16 (1773)

○ *Doronicum columnae* Ten.

Fl. Neapol. Prodr. App. 5 1: 49 (1811)

Gimbráfífill

○ *Doronicum orientale* Hoffm.

Commentat. Soc. Phys.-Med. Univ. Lit. Caes. Mosq. 1: 8 (1808)

Hjartarfífill

○ *Doronicum pardalianches* L.

Sp. Pl.: 885 (1753) emend Jacq.

Bolafífill

○ *Echinops exaltatus* Schrad.

Hort. Götting.: 15 (1809)

Broddþyrnikollur

³⁰⁴ *C. praemorsa* was recorded by some early authors but there are no specimens to confirm these findings.

Erigeron borealis (Vierh.) Simmons

Acta Univ. Lund., n.s., sect. 2, 9, 19: 127 (1913)

Jakobsfífill

- *Trimorpha borealis* Vierh., Beih. Bot. Centralbl. 19, 2: 447 (1906)
- *Erigeron alpinus* sensu Stefánsson (1901), non L. (1753)
- *Erigeron neglectus* sensu Stefánsson (1901), non A. Kern. (1871)

Erigeron humilis Graham

Edinburgh New Philos. J. 6: 175 (1828)

Snækobbi

- *Erigeron unalaschkensis* (DC.) Vierh., Beih. Bot. Centralbl. 19(2): 492 (1906)

Erigeron eriocephalus J. Vahl

Fl. Dan. 13, 39: 6 (1840)

Jöklakobbi

- *Erigeron uniflorus* subsp. *eriocephalus* (J. Vahl) Cronquist, Brittonia 6: 236 (1947)
- *Erigeron uniflorus* var. *eriocephalus* (J. Vahl) B. Boivin, Phytologia 23: 49 (1972)

Erigeron uniflorus L.

Sp. Pl.: 864 (1753)

Fjallakobbi

○ *Erigeron speciosus* (Lindl.) DC.

Prodr. 5: 284 (1836)

Garðakobbi

○ *Filago germanica* (L.) Huds.

Fl. Angl.: 328 (1763)

Knappmulla

- *Gnaphalium germanicum* L., Sp. Pl.: 857 (1753), nom. inval.
- *Filago vulgaris* Lam., Flore Française 2: 61 (1778)

○ *Galatella linosyris* (L.) Rchb.f.

Icon. Fl. Germ. Helv. (H.G.L. Reichenbach) 16: 8 (1853)

Gullstjarna

- *Aster linosyris* (L.) Bernh., Syst. Verz. (Bernhardi): 151 (1800)

◆ *Gnaphalium uliginosum* L.³⁰⁵

Sp. Pl.: 856 (1753)

Grámygla

- *Filaginella uliginosa* (L.) Opiz, Abh. Königl. Böhm. Ges. Wiss. 8 (b. Sitz. Sect.): 57 (1854)

○ *Helianthus annuus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 904 (1753)

Sólblóm

305 *G. uliginosum* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

HIERACIUM L.³⁰⁶

Sp. Pl.: 799. (1753)

Hieracium acidotoides agg.

Merkurfífill

> *Hieracium acidotoides* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 34 (1904)

Tannafífill

> *Hieracium aeolocephalum* Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk.Kl. 1938(3): 31 (1939)

Ólafarfífill

> *Hieracium basipinnatum* (Omang) Grøntved

Bot. Iceland 4(1): 379 (1942)

Flipafífill

> *Hieracium chaetophyllum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Ísland. 34: 9 (196)

Dvergblaðafífill

> *Hieracium chlorolepidotum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Ísland. 37: 55. (1966)

Kóngrsfífill

> *Hieracium cretatum* Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 49 (1904)

Möðruvallafífill

> *Hieracium euglaucum* Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk.Kl. 1938(3): 44 (1939)

Bláblaðafífill

> *Hieracium euprosopum* Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk.Kl. 1938(3): 47 (1939)

Giljafífill

> *Hieracium floccellum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Ísland. 37: 59 (1966)

Lórfífill

> *Hieracium floccilimbatum* (Dahlst.) Grøntved

Bot. Iceland 4(1): 379 (1942)

306 Icelandic species from the genus *Hieracium* were studied quite thoroughly during the 20th century. Ingimar Óskarsson, Icelandic botanist, is certainly among the most prolific authors contributing to the knowledge on Icelandic Hieracia. In total he listed 176 species from Iceland (excluding the genus *Pilosella* Hill.) (Óskarsson 1966, 1973, 1976, 1979). Löve (1983) classified Icelandic Hieracia into 9 species complexes (*H. alpinum*, *H. nigrescens*, *H. alatum*, *H. schmidtii*, *H. murorum*, *H. laevigatum*, *H. viosum*, *H. dovrense* and *H. prenanthoides*). More recently, Bergþór Jóhannsson published two works on Icelandic Hieracia and proposed a practical system consisting initially of 19 species (Jóhannsson, 1989). This view was subsequently revised and finally 22 Icelandic species (aggregates) were proposed by Jóhannsson (2004). This system was also accepted by Kristinsson (2008). Here, another view proposed by Greuter (2010) is accepted and a total number of taxa decreased even further to 14 species aggregates.

- > *Hieracium habrodon* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 43 (1957)
Staktannaþífill

- > *Hieracium immodestum* Greuter
Willdenowia 37: 156 (2007)
Öðlingsþífill
– *Hieracium superbum* (Strömf.) Dahlst, Ark. Bot. 3(10): 30 (1904)

- > *Hieracium megalomeres* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 26 (1939)
Stjarnhárafífill

- > *Hieracium nordenstamii* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 37: 82 (1966)
Svíafífill

- > *Hieracium pallidivirens* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 46 (1957)
Fölvafífill

- > *Hieracium paurodontum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 47 (1957)
Fátannaþífill

- > *Hieracium pellaeocephalum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 41 (1939)
Loðkollsþífill

- > *Hieracium perornaticeps* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 24 (1939)
Skrauthöfðafífill

- > *Hieracium poliobrachium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 37: 85 (1966)
Ögurþífill

- > *Hieracium praecordans* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 41 (1939)
Hjartblaðafífill (Gilkitsífill)

- > *Hieracium praefloccellum* Omang
Nyt Mag. Naturvidensk. 67: 310 (1929)

- > *Hieracium praepallens* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 42 1904
Runnaþífill

- > *Hieracium prasinamaurum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 34: 8 (1961)
Dökkreifafífill

- > *Hieracium sarcophylloton* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 35 (1957)
Bleikblaðafífill

> *Hieracium senex* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 39 (1904)

Öldungsfífill

> *Hieracium stenopholidium* (Dahlst.) Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 36 (1939)

Mjóhreistarfífill (Skáneyjarfífill)

> *Hieracium thaectolepium* Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 37 (1904)

Hlíðafífill

> *Hieracium trichotum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 40 (1904)

Svarthöfðafífill

- *Hieracium hemitrichotum* Omang, Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 43 (1939) nom. illeg.

***Hieracium alpinum* agg.**

Fellafífill (Fjallafífill)

> *Hieracium exsiliusculum* (Omang) Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 8 (1939)

Smákollsfífill

> *Hieracium gudbrandii* Ósk.,

Vísindaf. Ísland. 37: 20 (1966)

Guðbrandsfífill

Hieracium kaldalonense Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 10 (1904)

Kaldalónsfífill

> *Hieracium perlaniferum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Ísland. 34: 5 (1961)

Lubbaífill

> *Hieracium semialpinum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 21 (1957)

Fellafífillsbróðir

> *Hieracium sericellum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 19 (1904)

Hnattkollsfífill

> *Hieracium taraxacifrons* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 27 (1957)

Hrafnablöðkuffífill

***Hieracium anglicum* agg.**

Klausturfífill

> *Hieracium anglicum* Fr.,

Nova Acta Regiae Soc. Sci. Upsal. 14: 93 (1848)

Vestmannafífill

> *Hieracium arctocerinthe* Dahlst.

Bot. Tidsskr. 20: 356 (1896)

Tíglufífill

> *Hieracium chasmataeum* Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 29 (1939)

Almannagjárfífill

> *Hieracium clomacotes* Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 28 (1939)

Kálfafellsfífill

> *Hieracium foliolosum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 9 (1957)

Smáblaðafífill

> *Hieracium jonassonii* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 35 (1957)

Helgafífill

> *Hieracium leucodetum* Omang

Fl. Iceland: 163 (1934)

Hærufífill (Bæjargilsfífill)

> *Hieracium mesopolium* Dahlst.

Ark. Bot. 3(10): 27 (1904)

> *Hieracium semianglicum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 33 (1957)

Húsavíkurfífill

> *Hieracium stoedvareense* Omang

Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 55 (1939)

Stöðvarfífill

> *Hieracium vogareense* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 36 (1957)

Vogafífill

***Hieracium aquiliforme* agg.**

Arinfífill

> *Hieracium amphichnoum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 40 (1957)

Lóblaðafífill

> *Hieracium anomodon* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 40 (1957)

Össufífill

> *Hieracium apachyglossum* Ósk.

Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 41 (1957)

Snögghærufífill

- > *Hieracium aquiliforme* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 47 (1904)
Arinffífill
- > *Hieracium arnarfellense* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 37 (1957)
Arnarfellsfífill
- > *Hieracium atricholepium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 34: 10 (1961)
Arinffílsbróðir
- > *Hieracium belonodontum* (Dahlst.) Omang
Fl. Iceland: 157 (1934)
Hátannafífill
- > *Hieracium catoxylepis* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 47 (1939)
Krossastaðafífill
- > *Hieracium erigescens* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 46 (1939)
Húsafellsfífill
- > *Hieracium furfurosum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 48 (1904)
Hreisturfífill
- > *Hieracium integrilaterum* (Dahlst.) Omang
Fl. Iceland: 157 (1934)
Sléttraðafífill
- > *Hieracium leucoclonum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 45 (1957)
Glóstilkafífill
- > *Hieracium levihirtum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 45 (1939)
Mjúkhárafífill
- > *Hieracium longifrons* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 46 (1904)
Gjáfífill
- > *Hieracium macropholidium* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 35 (1904)
Tröllafífill
- > *Hieracium oncadenium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 29 (1957)
Stórkirtlafífill
- > *Hieracium pammelanum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 43 (1939)
Dökkkollsfífill

> *Hieracium scytalocephalum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 49 (1939)
Eldborgarfífill

> *Hieracium semiprolixum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 38 (1904)
Mókollsíffill

***Hieracium demissum* agg.**

Skallafífill

> *Hieracium chaetolepis* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 63 (1957)
Sólheimafífill

> *Hieracium demissum* (Strömf.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 60 (1904)
Skallafífill

> *Hieracium notophilum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 65 (1957)
Rakafífill

> *Hieracium steffensenii* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 75 (1957)
Steffensensíffill

> *Hieracium tynnoglochin* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 77 (1957)
Álftafjarðarfífill

***Hieracium elegantiforme* agg.**

Glæsifífill

> *Hieracium altipetens* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 59 (1939)
Háblaðafífill (Látrafífill)

> *Hieracium aquitectum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 62 (1957)
Oddafífill

> *Hieracium atrichocephalum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 58 (1904)
Kirtlafífill

> *Hieracium axillifrons* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 69 (1957)
Axlablaðafífill

> *Hieracium devians* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 57 (1904)
Útfjarðarfífill

- > *Hieracium elegantiforme* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 60 (1904)
Glæsifífill
- > *Hieracium erythrostickum* Omang
Fl. Iceland: 167 (1934)
Rauðdeplafífill
- > *Hieracium oxyodontophorum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 74 (1957)
Broddtannafífill
- > *Hieracium paurocyma* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 59 (1939)
Trostansfífill
- > *Hieracium perpiliferum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 58 (1939)
Loðnuvífill (Stuðlafífill)
- > *Hieracium retifolium* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 63 (1904)
Netæðafífill
- > *Hieracium rhombotum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 71 (1957)
Ólafsfjarðarfífill
- > *Hieracium tapeinocephalum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 61 (1939)
Lágkollsfífill

***Hieracium froelichianum* agg.**

- > *Hieracium arrostoccephalum* Omang
Fl. Iceland: 165 (1934)
Ingimarsfífill
- > *Hieracium phyllochnoum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 57 (1939)
Fornhagafífill

***Hieracium holopleurum* agg.**

Runnafífill

- > *Hieracium cephalochnoum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 34: 10 (1961)
Ljóshöfðafífill
- > *Hieracium chamaecephalum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 42 (1957)
Smáhöfðafífill

- > *Hieracium congenitum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 51 (1904)
Smáfífill (Dvergafífill)

- > *Hieracium groentvedii* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 53 (1957)
Gröntveðsfífill

- > *Hieracium hoidalicum* (Omang) Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.- Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 51 (1939)

- > *Hieracium holopleuroides* (Dahlst.) Omang
Fl. Iceland: 159 (1934)
Glókollsfífill

- > *Hieracium holopleurophyllum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 44 (1957)
Öræfafífill

- > *Hieracium holopleurum* Dahlst.
Bot. Tidsskr. 20: 355 (1896)
Grákollsfífill

- > *Hieracium longipilipes* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 55 (1957)
Langhærufífill

- > *Hieracium lopholepidioides* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 50 (1939)
Kambfífill (Hofsárfífill)

- > *Hieracium megalocaulon* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 56 (1957)
Skessufífill

- > *Hieracium nigrescenticeps* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 53 (1939)
Svartkollsfífill

- > *Hieracium ovatifolians* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 51 (1939)
Kolkufífill

- > *Hieracium pauradenium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 49 (1957)
Klængshólsfífill

- > *Hieracium scolopoglossum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 51 (1957)
Þéttannafífill

- > *Hieracium senectum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 50 (1904)
Flekkufífill (Eiðafífill)

> *Hieracium sococratodium* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 52 (1939)
Vandarfífill (Mýrdalsfífill)

> *Hieracium subcongenitum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 58. (1957)
Smáfífilbróðir

> *Hieracium thingvellirensse* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 68. (1957)
Oddblaðafífill

***Hieracium lygistodon* agg.**

Vargsfífill

> *Hieracium acroscepes* (Omang) Omang
Islenzkar Jurtir: 273. (1945)
Hafnarfjarðarfífill

> *Hieracium angusticranum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 37: 14 (1966)
Fáreifaífill

> *Hieracium aphylocaule* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 6 (1957)
Arnarstapafífill

> *Hieracium apicicomum* Omang,
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 16 (1939)
Loðfífill

> *Hieracium austurgilense* (Omang) Omang
Islenzkar Jurtir: 273 (1945)
Austurgilsfífill

> *Hieracium cataponum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 22 (1939)
Hörgsfífill, Hörgárfífill

> *Hieracium chordum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 7 (1957)
Þráðblaðafífill

> *Hieracium chrysocladium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 8 (1957)
Gullhærufífill

> *Hieracium cremnaeiforme* (Omang) Omang
Islenzkar Jurtir: 273 (1945)
Öxnadalsfífill

> *Hieracium davidsonii* Omang
Fl. Iceland: 149 (1934)
Ólafsfífill

- > *Hieracium diacritum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 15 (1939)
Silkifífill
- > *Hieracium edentulum* Ósk.
Acta Bot. Islandica 2: 64 (1973)
- > *Hieracium einarssonii* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 37: 18 (1966)
Fögrubrekkuvífill
- > *Hieracium extracticaule* (Omang) Omang
Islenzkar Jurtir: 272 (1945)
Geirþjófsvífill
- > *Hieracium fusciviride* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 9 (1957)
Brúnifífill
- > *Hieracium gigantecephalum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 10 (1957)
Risavífill
- > *Hieracium hafstroendense* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 10 (1957)
Hafstrandarvífill
- > *Hieracium haploun* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 11 (1939)
Árskógsvífill
- > *Hieracium holostenophyllum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 17 (1939)
Strikblaðavífill
- > *Hieracium integrifrons* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 13 (1957)
Sporblaðavífill
- > *Hieracium leucomalloides* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 14 (1957)
Selárvífill
- > *Hieracium leucomallum* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 13 (1904)
Ljósreifavífill
- > *Hieracium lygistodon* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 18 (1904)
Vargsvífill
- > *Hieracium macrolasium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 34: 6 (1961)
Kársstaðavífill

- > *Hieracium monanthum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 9 (1939)
Einkollsfífill (Hraundalsfífill)
- > *Hieracium nanidens* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 15 (1957)
Dvalinsfífill
- > *Hieracium neorepandum* P. D. Sell & C. West
Bot. J. Linn. Soc. 71: 265 (1976)
Bugtannafífill
– *Hieracium repandum* Dahlst., Bot. Tidsskr. 22: 202 (1899)
- > *Hieracium nepium* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 12 (1939)
Þingvallafífill
- > *Hieracium obtusangulum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 19 (1904)
Skaftárfífill
- > *Hieracium percome* Omang
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 19 (1904)
Vinafífill
- > *Hieracium percomiforme* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 17 (1957)
Vinafífillsbróðir
- > *Hieracium petiolosum* Dahlst.
Arkiv Bot. Stockh. 3: No. 10, 11 (1904)
- > *Hieracium piciniforme* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 21 (1904)
Mjóblaðafífill
- > *Hieracium praegrandiceps* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 17 (1957)
Tröllhöfðafífill
- > *Hieracium pumilare* (Omang) Omang
Íslenzkar Jurtir: 273 (1945)
Hestahraunsfífill
- > *Hieracium pyrolifolium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 18 (1957)
- > *Hieracium repandilaterum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 19 (1957)
Sljótannafífill
- > *Hieracium rubrimaculatum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Ísland. 31: 20 (1957)
Skrautblaðafífill

- > *Hieracium semipercome* Ósk.,
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 22 (1957)
Norðfjarðarfífill
- > *Hieracium skarddalicum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 22 (1957)
Skarðdalsfífill
- > *Hieracium steindorii* (Omang) Omang
Islenzkar Jurtir: 275 (1945)
Steindórsfífill
- > *Hieracium stellatifolium* (Omang) Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 23 (1957)
Stjörnuvífill (Hofsfallsfífill)
- > *Hieracium stroemfeltii* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 17 (1904)
Strömfeltsfífill
- > *Hieracium subapicicomum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 24 (1957)
Valhallarfífill
- > *Hieracium subfusciviride* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 25 (1957)
Mósufífill
- > *Hieracium subrotundiforme* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 26 (1957)
Tungufífill
- > *Hieracium subrotundum* (Dahlst.) Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 15 (1939)
Kringlufífill

***Hieracium magnidens* agg.**

Kvíslfífill

- > *Hieracium anochnoum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 28 (1957)
Hýfífill
- > *Hieracium bipediforme* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 22 (1904)
Kvíslfífill (Vörtufífill, Snælandsfífill)
– *Hieracium subobtusum* Dahlst., Ark. Bot. 3(10): 26 (1904), nom. confus.
- > *Hieracium dissotocoides* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 20 (1939)
Fljótafífill
- > *Hieracium hraunense* Omang
Fl. Iceland: 152 (1934)
Hraunafífill

- > *Hieracium hyocomium* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 12 (1957)
Kjarrfífill
- > *Hieracium magnidens* Dahlst.
Bot. Tidsskr. 22: 203 (1899)
Stórtannafífill
- > *Hieracium nordlandicum* Dahlst.
Acta Horti Berg. 2(4): 98 (1894)
Norrænifífill
- > *Hieracium phrixomalliforme* (Omang) Omang
Islenzkar Jurtir: 274 (1945)
Skúfáfífill (Grímsnessfífill)
- > *Hieracium semibipes* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.,
Bot. Ark. 3(10): 23 (1904)
Greinafífill
- > *Hieracium skutudalicum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 30 (1957)
Skútudalsfífill
- > *Hieracium stefanssonii* Omang
Fl. Iceland: 151 (1934)
Stefánsfífill
- > *Hieracium tanyclonum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 31 (1957)
Mjóstilkafífill

***Hieracium microdon* agg.**

Holtafífill

- > *Hieracium crinosum* Omang
Fl. Iceland: 153 (1934)
Lokkafífill (Reykholtshóltsfífill)
- > *Hieracium gilense* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 38 (1957)
Gilsfífill
- > *Hieracium ingolfii* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 34: 11 (1961)
Ingólfsfífill
- > *Hieracium microdon* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Fl. Íslands, ed. 2: 240 (1924)
Smátannafífill
- > *Hieracium semisuperbum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 34: 8 (1961)
Keisarafífill

***Hieracium prenanthoides* agg.**

> *Hieracium furvescens* (Dahlst.) Omang
Nyt Mag. Naturvidensk. 48: 246. (1910)

> *Hieracium thulense* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 63 (1904)
Skrautfífill

***Hieracium pullicalicium* agg.**

Skeggfífill

> *Hieracium agastophyes* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 61 (1957)
Guðafífill

> *Hieracium cladiopogon* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 76 (1957)
Skeggfífill

> *Hieracium lamprochlorum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 35 (1939)
Svínafellsfífill

> *Hieracium megaphyes* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 37: 104 (1966)
Gljáfífill

> *Hieracium olafii* Ósk.
Acta Bot. Islandica 5: 71 (1979)

> *Hieracium pullicalicium* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 54 (1939)
Brúnkollsfífill

***Hieracium sparsifolium* agg.**

> *Hieracium acidophorum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 63 (1939)
Hvasstannafífill (Þjórsárfífill)

> *Hieracium acidophyllum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 52 (1957)
Hvassblaðafífill

> *Hieracium anelctum* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 34 (1939)
Langtannafífill (Borgarnesfífill)

- > *Hieracium chamaeodon* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 64 (1957)
Dvergtannafífill
- > *Hieracium floccilepium* Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.-Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 62 (1939)
Lóreifafífill (Þingfífill)
- > *Hieracium halfdanii* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 70 (1957)
Hálfðánarfífill
- > *Hieracium hypoleptolepis* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 77 (1957)
Fjöltreifafífill
- > *Hieracium macrocomum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 66 (1904)
Brekkuvífill
- > *Hieracium megalophyton* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 57 (1957)
Jötunvífill
- > *Hieracium myrdalense* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 73 (1957)
Álfafífill
- > *Hieracium oxypleurum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 65 (1957)
Sagarvífill
- > *Hieracium pernervosum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 66 (1957)
Taugafífill
- > *Hieracium phrioxclonum* (Omang) Omang
Skr. Norske Vidensk.-Akad. Oslo, Mat.- Naturvidensk. Kl. 1938(3): 60 (1939)
Kögurvífill (Þrastarhólsfífill)
- > *Hieracium purpuriguttatum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 50 (1957)
Purpurafífill
- > *Hieracium stictophylloides* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 67 (1957)
Nettblaðafífill
- > *Hieracium stictophyllum* Dahlst.
Herb. Hierac. Scand. 4: [in schedis] No. 81 (1893)
Blettafífill
- > *Hieracium thermophilum* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 59 (1957)
Varmafífill

> *Hieracium tynnotrichum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 3(10): 56 (1904)
Búðafífill

> *Hieracium vikense* Ósk.
Vísindaf. Íslend. 31: 78 (1957)
Víkurfífill

○ *Jacobaea vulgaris* Gaertn.³⁰⁷

Fruct. 2: 445 (1791)

Bikarþulur

● *Lactuca alpina* (L.) A. Gray

Syn. Fl. N. Amer. 1(2): 444 (1884)

Fjallablámi

– *Sonchus alpinus* L., Sp. Pl.: 794 (1753)

– *Cicerbita alpina* (L.) Wallr., Sched. Crit.: 434 (1822)

– *Mulgedium alpinum* (L.) Less., Syn. Gen. Compos.: 142 (1832)

○ *Lactuca macrophylla* (Willd.) A. Gray

Syn. Fl. N. Amer. 1(2): 444 (1884)

Risablámi

– *Sonchus macrophyllus* Willd., Sp. Pl. 3: 1519 (1803)

– *Cicerbita macrophylla* (Willd.) Wallr., Sched. Crit.: 434 (1822)

○ *Lactuca muralis* (L.) Gaertn.

Fruct. Sem. Pl.: t. 158 (1791)

Skógarsalat

– *Prenanthes muralis* L., Sp. Pl.: 797 (1753)

– *Mycelis muralis* (L.) Dumort., Florula Belg.: 60 (1827)

○ *Lactuca serriola* L.

Cent. Pl. 2: 29 (1756)

Þyrnisalat

○ *Lapsana communis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 811 (1753)

Hérafífill

● *Lepidotheca suaveolens* (Pursh) Nutt.³⁰⁸

Trans. Amer. Philos. Soc., n.s., 7: 454 (1841)

Hlaðkolla

– *Santolina suaveolens* Pursh, Fl. Amer. Sept. 2: 520 (1813)

– *Chamomilla suaveolens* (Pursh) Rydb., N. Amer. Fl. 34, 3: 232 (1916)

– *Matricaria discoidea* DC., Prodr. 6: 50 (1838)

– *Matricaria suaveolens* (Pursh) Buchenau, Fl. Nordwestdeut. Tiefebene: 496 (1894), nom. illeg. hom.

– *Matricaria matricarioides* auct. non Porter (1894)

307 Old records of the species by Baring-Gould (1863) and Babington (1871) cannot be confirmed due to the lack of available specimens. First confirmed and recent record is from Hafnarfjörður (Wasowicz 2019).

308 The name *Matricaria matricarioides* has been misapplied to this species in several earlier works on Icelandic flora.

- *Leucanthemum vulgare* Lam.
Fl. Franç. 2: 137 (1779)
Freyjubrá
 - *Chrysanthemum leucanthemum* L., Sp. Pl.: 888 (1753)
 - *Leucanthemum ircutianum* DC., Prodr. 6: 47 (1838)

- *Matricaria chamomilla* L.
Sp. Pl.: 891 (1753)
Kryddbaldursbrá
 - *Matricaria recutita* L., Sp. Pl.: 891 (1753)

- ***Omalotheca norvegica*** (Gunnerus) Sch.Bip. & F.W. Schultz
Arch. Fl. 2: 311 (1861)
Fjandafæla
 - *Gnaphalium norvegicum* Gunnerus, Fl. Norveg. 2: 105 (1776)

- ***Omalotheca supina*** (L.) DC.
Prodr. 6: 245 (1838)
Grámulla
 - *Gnaphalium supinum* L., Syst. Nat., ed. 12, 3: 234 (1768)
 - *Gnaphalium fuscum* Scop., Fl. Carniol. (ed. 2) 2: 152 (1772)
 - *Gnaphalium rectum* C.A. Mey., Verz. Pfl. Caucasus 77. n. 641 (1831)

- ***Omalotheca sylvatica*** (L.) Sch.Bip. & F.W. Schultz
Arch. Fl. 2: 311 (1861)
Grájurt
 - *Gnaphalium sylvaticum* L., Sp. Pl.: 856 (1753)

- *Petasites hybridus* (L.) G. Gaertn., B. Mey. & Scherb.
Oekon. Fl. Wetterau 3(2): 184 (1802)
Hrossaffíll
 - *Tussilago hybrida* L., Sp. Pl.: 866 (1753)

- *Pilosella aurantiaca* (L.) F.W. Schultz & Sch.Bip.
Flora 45: 426 (1862)
Roðafíll
 - *Hieracium aurantiacum* L., Sp. Pl.: 801 (1753)

- ***Pilosella islandica*** (Lange) Á. Löve
Taxon 19: 301 (1970)
Íslandsfíll
 - *Hieracium floribundum* var. *islandicum* Lange in Grønlund, Isl. Fl.: 77 (1881)
 - *Hieracium islandicum* (Lange) Dahlst., Acta Horti Berg. 2, 4: 15 (1894)

- *Pilosella officinarum* Vaill.
Königl. Akad. Wiss. Paris Phys. Abh. 5: 70 (1754)
Tágaffíll
 - *Hieracium pilosella* L., Sp. Pl.: 800 (1753)

- *Rudbeckia laciniata* L.
Sp. Pl.: 906 (1753)
Flipahattur

***Scorzoneroides autumnalis* (L.) Moench**

Methodus: 549 (1794)

Skariffill

- *Leontodon autumnalis* L., Sp. Pl.: 798 (1753)
- *Hedypnois taraxaci* Huds., Fl. Angl. (Hudson) (ed. 2) 2: 341 (1778)
- *Apargia autumnalis* (L.) Hoffmann, Deutschl. Fl. ed. II. 2: 113 (1813)

○ *Senecio duriaei* J. Gay

Ann. Sci. Nat., Bot. 6: 346 (1836)

Meistarakrossgras

- *Senecio nebrodensis* L., Sp. Pl., ed. 2: 1217 (1763)

Senecio leucanthemifolius Poir.

Voy. Barbarie 2: 238 (1789)

- *Senecio leucanthemifolius* subsp. *vernalis* (Waldst. & Kit.) Greuter
Willdenowia 33: 247 (2003)

Vorþulur

- *Senecio vernalis* Waldst. & Kit., Descr. Icon. Pl. Hung. 1: 23 t. 24 (1800)

● *Senecio pseudo-arnica* Less.

Linnaea 6: 240 (1831)

Stormþulur

- *Arnica maritima* L., Sp. Pl.: 884 (1753)

○ *Senecio sylvaticus* L.

Sp. Pl.: 868 (1753)

Trönuþulur

○ *Senecio viscosus* L.³⁰⁹

Sp. Pl.: 868 (1753)

Kvoðuþulur

◆ *Senecio vulgaris* L.³¹⁰

Sp. Pl.: 867 (1753)

Krossfífill

○ *Solidago gigantea* Ait.³¹¹

Hort. Kew. 3: 21 (1789)

Tröllagullhrís

○ *Solidago virgaurea* L.³¹²

Sp. Pl. 880(1753)

Gullhrís

○ *Sonchus arvensis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 793 (1753)

Grísafífill

309 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

310 *S. vulgaris* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

311 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

312 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

- *Sonchus asper* (L.) Hill
Herb. Brit. 1: 47 (1769)
Galtarfífill
– *Sonchus oleraceus* var. *asper* L., Sp. Pl.: 794 (1753)
- *Sonchus oleraceus* L.
Sp. Pl.: 794 (1753)
Gyltufífill
- *Tanacetum vulgare* L.
Sp. Pl.: 844 (1753)
Regnfang
– *Chrysanthemum vulgare* (L.) Bernh., Syst. Verz.: 144 (1800) nom. illeg. hom.

Taraxacum F.H. Wiggers³¹³
Prim. Fl. Holsat. 56. 1780, nom. cons.
Fífill

Sect. *Borea* A. J. Richards
Taxon 34: 639 (1985)

- > *Taraxacum myvatnense* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 338 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum ostenfeldii* Raunk.
Bot. Tidsskr. 25(2): 139 (1903)
- > *Taraxacum septentrionale* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 12(2): 115 (1912)
Mývatnsfífill
- > *Taraxacum stictophoreum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 262 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum triangulare* H. Lindb.
Meddeland. Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 35: 19 (1909)

Sect. *Crocea* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 255 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum acidotum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 279 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum acutatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 270 (1942)

313 The genus *Taraxacum* in Iceland was studied by Christiansen (1942), who listed a total of 116 microspecies. More recently, Richards and Sell (1976) treated Icelandic species in European context, but much work has been done since. In his Flora of Iceland, Löve (1983) acknowledged the work of Christiansen (1942), but stated that most of the taxa listed from Iceland are "evidently disputable" and included most of them in a collective species named *Taraxacum spectabile*, while placing other taxa in two comprehensive groups: *Taraxacum erythrospermum* and *Taraxacum officinale*. Here, a treatment proposed by Kirschner et al. (2007) is adopted as it follows recent changes in infra-generic nomenclature. Main sections present in Iceland as well as species belonging to them are listed. There is no doubt that the genus *Taraxacum* in Iceland needs urgently a modern taxonomic revision.

- > *Taraxacum akranesense* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 268 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum appositum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 260 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum armatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 285 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum azureum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 267 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum ceratolobum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 12(2): 12 (1912)
- > *Taraxacum clitolobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 263 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum croceum* Dahlst.
Bih. Kongl. Svenska Vetensk.-Akad. Handl. 26(3, 1): 12(1900)
Engjafífill
- > *Taraxacum curvidens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 262 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum davidssonii* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 289 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum declive* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 269 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum devexum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 270 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum divarium* Sahlin
Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 18: 445 (1983)
- > *Taraxacum dolichocentrum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 281 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum egilsstadirensense* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 267 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum espinulosum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 259 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum gladiatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 269 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum hamidens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 290 (1942)
- > *Taraxacum hostile* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 286 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum hastiliforme* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 281 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum isolobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 290 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum lonchophyllum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 265 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum longihastatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 280 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum longisagittatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 261 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum loratum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 264 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum luteodens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 277 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum macromerum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 277 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum obovatifrons* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 276 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum ostrinum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 302 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum perdevexum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 272 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum pergracile* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 282 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum planifrons* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 278 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum pravum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 287 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum pycnostictum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 287 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum repletum* (Dahlst.) Brenner
Meddeland. Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 33: 109(1908)

- > *Taraxacum rufescens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 291 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum sagittifrons* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 291 (1942)

> *Taraxacum scotolepidiforme* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 274 (1942)

> *Taraxacum sigmoideum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 273 (1942)

> *Taraxacum spiculiforme* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 273 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subcrispum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 273 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subnefrens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 273 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subrepletum* G.E. Haglund
Bot. Iceland 3: 273 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subscolopendricum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 273 (1942)

> *Taraxacum xiphoideum* G.E. Haglund
Nytt Mag. Naturvidensk. 82: 94 (1941)

Sect. *Erythrosperma* (H. Lindb.) Dahlst.
Dahlst., Acta Fl. Sueciae 1: 36 (1921)

> *Taraxacum arrigens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 252 (1942)

> *Taraxacum diversiflorum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 252 (1942)

> *Taraxacum erythrospermum* Besser
Enum. Pl.: 75 (1821)

> *Taraxacum falcatum* Brenner
Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 4: 354 (1907)

> *Taraxacum limbatum* Dahlst.
Bot. Not. (1909): 173 (1909)

> *Taraxacum proximum* (Dahlst.) Raunk.
Dansk Exkurs.-Fl., ed. 2: 258 (1906)

Sect. *Macrodonia* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 318 (1942)

> *Taraxacum acromaurum* Dahlst.
Fl. Iceland: 146 (1934)
Túnfífill

> *Taraxacum concavum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 324 (1942)

> *Taraxacum cymbifolium* Dahlst.
Kongl. Svenska Vetensk. Acad. Handl., ser. 3 9(2):10, 73 (1930)

> *Taraxacum dentex* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 323 (1942)

> *Taraxacum gibberosum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 326 (1942)
Kryppufífill

> *Taraxacum hoplites* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 327 (1942)

> *Taraxacum hypochoeris* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 12(2): 40 (1912)
Gríseyrnaífill

> *Taraxacum islandicum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 328 (1942)
Frónsfiill

> *Taraxacum latispinulosum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 322 (1942)

> *Taraxacum leucocephalum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 324 (1942)

> *Taraxacum rhomboideum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 321 (1942)

> *Taraxacum selenodon* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 283 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subhoplites* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 335 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subreduncum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 264 (1942)

> *Taraxacum tenebricans* (Dahlst.) H. Lindb.
Meddeland. Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 35:148 (1909)
Dökkfiill

Sect. *Naevosa* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 303 (1942)

> *Taraxacum atroglaucum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 307 (1942)

> *Taraxacum brachylobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 332 (1942)

> *Taraxacum brevihastatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 305 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum brevilobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 309 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum chloodeum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 334 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum ciconium* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 325 (1942)
Móaffill

- > *Taraxacum cycloctrum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 312 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum dilutisquameum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 312 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum galeiferum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 336 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum galeipotens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 307 (1942)
Hagaffill

- > *Taraxacum latidens* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 329 (1942)
Hrímbiðuffill

- > *Taraxacum latifrons* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 320 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum latihastatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 321 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum longispinulosum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 333 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum luxurians* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 335 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum melanocephalum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 333 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum mucroniferum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 311 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum naevosum* Dahlst.
Bot. Faeröes: 840 (1907)
Deplaffill

- > *Taraxacum pardinum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 305 (1942)

- > *Taraxacum parile* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 315 (1942)

> *Taraxacum reclinatum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 293 (1942)

> *Taraxacum rubellum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 313 (1942)

> *Taraxacum scabrum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 317 (1942)

> *Taraxacum selenolobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 320 (1942)

> *Taraxacum stictophyllum* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 12(2): 38 (1912)

> *Taraxacum subpardinum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 306 (1942)

> *Taraxacum triste* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 316 (1942)
Myrkifjall

Sect. *Spectabilia* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Acta Fl. Sueciae 1: 37 (1921)

> *Taraxacum calanthum* Dahlst.
Kongl. Svenska Vetensk. Acad. Handl., ser. 3 9(2): 6, 13 (1930)

> *Taraxacum cordatifrons* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 299 (1942)

> *Taraxacum crispifrons* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 299 (1942)

> *Taraxacum devians* Dahlst.
Fl. Iceland: 145 (1934)

> *Taraxacum faeroense* (Dahlst.) Dahlst.
Bergens Mus. Årbok 1923–1924 (6): 12 (1925)
Færeyjafjall

> *Taraxacum furvum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 297 (1942)

> *Taraxacum laticonicum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 266 (1942)

> *Taraxacum ovillum* H. Øllg.
Nordic J. Bot. 33: 31 (2015)

> *Taraxacum pravicentrum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 279 (1942)

> *Taraxacum scalenum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 301 (1942)

> *Taraxacum spectabile* Dahlst.
Bot. Not. 1905: 151, 159 (1905)
Múlakotsfífill

> *Taraxacum subeximium* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 294 (1942)

> *Taraxacum subspectabile* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 300 (1942)

> *Taraxacum vestmannicum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 295 (1942)

Sect. *Taraxacum* F.H. Wigg.
Prim. Fl. Holsat.: 56 (1780)

> *Taraxacum angustisquameum* H. Lindb.
Acta Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn. 29(9): 10, 23 (1908)
Mjóreifaíffill

> *Taraxacum haematicum* H. Øllg. & Wittzell
Ann. Bot. Fenn. 32: 229 (1995)

> *Taraxacum pilosella* Lundev. & H. Øllg.
Willdenowia 36: 683 (2006)

> *Taraxacum stenoglossum* Brenner
Repert. Spec. Nov. Regni Veg. 4: 356 (1907)

> *Taraxacum sublaeticolor* Dahlst.
Ark. Bot. 19(18): 17 (1925)
Ljósfífill

Taxa unassigned to sections

> *Taraxacum nematolobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 254 (1942)

> *Taraxacum oxyphorum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 287 (1942)

> *Taraxacum ulophyllum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 285 (1942)

> *Taraxacum uncatilobum* M.P. Christ.
Bot. Iceland 3: 323 (1942)

○ *Tragopogon pratensis* L.
Sp. Pl.: 789 (1753)
Hafursskeggfífill

○ *Tripleurospermum inodorum* (L.) Sch.Bip.
Tanacetum: 32 (1844)
Völvubrá

Tripleurospermum maritimum (L.) W.D.J. Koch

Syn. Fl. Germ. Helv., ed. 2: 1026 (1845)

Baldursbrá

- *Matricaria maritima* L., Sp. Pl.: 891 (1753)
- *Pyrethrum maritimum* auct. non Sm. (1800)
- *Matricaria ambigua* auct. non Krylov (1904)

Tripleurospermum maritimum subsp. ***phaeocephalum*** (Rupr.) Hämet-Ahti³¹⁴

Acta Bot. Fenn. 75: 9 (1967)

- *Matricaria inodora* var. *phaeocephala* Rupr., Fl. Samojed. Cisural.: 42 (1845)
- *Tripleurospermum phaeocephalum* (Rupr.) Pobed., Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk SSSR 21: 347 (1961)
- *Matricaria maritima* subsp. *phaeocephala* (Rupr.) Rauschert, Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 9: 257 (1974)

Tripleurospermum maritimum subsp. ***subpolare*** (Pobed.) Hämet-Ahti³¹⁵

Acta Bot. Fenn. 75: 5 (1967)

- *Tripleurospermum subpolare* Pobed., Bot. Mater. Gerb. Bot. Inst. Komarova Akad. Nauk SSSR 21: 347 (1961)
- *Matricaria maritima* subsp. *subpolaris* (Pobed.) Rauschert, Folia Geobot. Phytotax. 9: 257 (1974)
- *Tripleurospermum inodorum* var. *boreale* Hartm., Handb. Skand. Fl., ed. 5: 2 (1849)
- *Tripleurospermum maritimum* subsp. *boreale* (Hartm.) A. Pedersen, Meddel. Grønland 178(7): 25 (1972)
- *Matricaria maritima* subsp. *borealis* (Hartm.) Á. Löve & D. Löve, Bot. Not. 128: 521 (1976)

 ● *Tussilago farfara* L.

Sp. Pl.: 865 (1753)

Hóffífill

CAPRIFOLIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 210 (1789), nom. cons.

Geitblaðsætt

 ▼ *Cephalaria alpina* (L.) Schrad.³¹⁶

Cat. Sem. Hort. Götting. (1814); ex Roem. & Schult. Syst. 3: 43 (1814)

Fjallakollur

- by Gliemann (1824) as *Scabiosa alpina*
- by Preyer and Zirkel (1862)
- rejected by Gröntved (1942)

 ► *Knautia arvensis* (L.) Coult.³¹⁷

Mém. Dipsac.: 41 (1823)

Rauðkollur

- *Scabiosa arvensis* L., Sp. Pl.: 99 (1753)

314 *T. maritimum* subsp. *phaeocephalum* has been found just in few places in SW Iceland and on Grímsey island (N Iceland).

315 *T. maritimum* subsp. *subpolare* is a main taxon in Iceland.

316 *C. alpina* was recorded, most probably by a mistake, by some of the 19th century authors. The species has never been confirmed from Iceland by contemporary authors.

317 *K. arvensis* is a non-native species of unknown age – see Wasowicz (2018) for more details.

○ *Lonicera caerulea* L.

Sp. Pl.: 174 (1753)

Blátoppur

○ *Lonicera periclymenum* L.³¹⁸

Sp. Pl.: 173 (1753)

Skógartoppur

Sambucus racemosa L.

Sp. Pl.: 270. 1753

○ *Sambucus racemosa* subsp. *pubens* (Michx.) Hultén

Fl. Aleutian Isl. 308

Dúnyllir

– *Sambucus pubens* Michx., Fl. Bor. Amer. 1: 181 (1803)

Succisa pratensis Moench

Methodus: 489 (1794)

Stúfa

– *Scabiosa succisa* L., Sp. Pl.: 98 (1753)

● *Valeriana officinalis* L.

Sp. Pl.: 31 (1753)

Garðabrúða

Valeriana sambucifolia J.C. Mikan ex Pohl³¹⁹

Tent. Fl. Bohem. 1: 41 (1809)

Hagabrúða

– *Valeriana excelsa* Poir., Encyc. 8: 301 (1808)

ARALIACEAE Juss.

Gen. Pl. [Jussieu]: 217 (1789), nom. cons.

Bergfléttuætt

▼ ◇ *Hedera helix* L.³²⁰

Sp. Pl.: 202 (1753)

Bergflétta

- by Gliemann (1824)

- by Baring-Gould (1863)

- by Babington (1871)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

Hydrocotyle vulgaris L.

Sp. Pl.: 234 (1753)

Vatnsnafli

318 For more information on this newly registered species check Wasowicz (2019).

319 The question of the identity of the taxon (taxa) present in Iceland has still not been solved. Löve (1970, 1983) accepted two subspecies (subsp. *sambucifolia* and subsp. *procurrens* (Wallr.) Á. Löve), while Kristinsson (2008) accepted only one taxon: subsp. *procurrens*. Recently, Elven et al. (2011) argued that subsp. *procurrens* is not present in Iceland and opted for provisional name *Valeriana sambucifolia* "Icelandic race". They also claimed that Icelandic material is uniform and should not be subdivided into two distinct taxa. Both Löve (1970) and Elven et al. (2011) suggest that *V. sambucifolia* might be an adventive species naturalized long time ago.

320 *H. helix* has been mentioned by some early authors but never found growing in Iceland more recently. Grøntved (1942) suggests that specimens mentioned by early authors might have been collected from cultivation.

APIACEAE Lindl. (= Umbelliferae Juss., nom. cons.)

Intr. Nat. Syst. Bot., ed. 2: 21 (1836), nom. cons.

Sveipjurtaætt

● *Aegopodium podagraria* L.

Sp. Pl.: 265 (1753)

Geitakál

○ *Aethusa cynapium* L.

Sp. Pl.: 256 (1753)

Villisteinselja

Angelica archangelica L.

Sp. Pl.: 250 (1753)

Angelica archangelica L. subsp. ***archangelica***³²¹

Ætihvönn

– *Archangelica officinalis* Hoffm., Pl. Umb. Gen. 1: 168 (1814)***Angelica sylvestris*** L.

Sp. Pl.: 251 (1753)

Geithvönn

Anthriscus sylvestris (L.) Hoffm.³²²

Gen. Pl. Umbell.: 40 (1814)

– *Chaerophyllum sylvestre* L., Sp. Pl.: 258 (1753)● *Anthriscus sylvestris* (L.) Hoffm. subsp. *sylvestris*

Skógarkerfill

◆ *Carum carvi* L.³²³

Sp. Pl.: 263 (1753)

Kúmen

* ○ *Caucalis platycarpos* L.³²⁴

Sp. Pl.: 241 (1753)

Önguljurt

– *Caucalis daucoides*, Sp. Pl.: 241 (1753)*Daucus carota* L.

Sp. Pl.: 242 (1753)

○ *Daucus carota* subsp. *sativus* (Hoffm.) Schübl. & Martens

Fl. Würtemb.: 179 (1834)

Gulrót

– *Daucus carota* var. *sativus* Hoffm., Deutschl. Fl.: 94 (1791)– *Daucus carota* (Hoffm.) Arcangeli, Comp. Fl. Ital.: 299 (1882)

321 Löve (1970, 1983) classified all Icelandic plants as *A. archangelica* subsp. *littoralis*, while Hulten and Fries (1986) assigned coastal plants to subsp. *littoralis*, and inland plants to subsp. *archangelica*. Recent revision of plant material from Iceland showed that only subsp. *archangelica* is present in the country (Fröberg 2010a). *A. archangelica* subsp. *littoralis* (Wahlenb.) Thell. is native to the southern coasts of Fennoscandia and occur neither in Iceland nor the Faroe Islands (Fröberg 2010a).

322 *A. sylvestris* is considered to be invasive in Iceland. First records of the species are from N Iceland (Akureyri – 1932) and its spread was evident as early as in 1940, when the species was seen to be spreading widely around army camps and gardens in Reykjavík and surroundings (Davíðsson 1959).

323 *C. carvi* is an archaeophyte – see Wasowicz (2018) for details.

324 *C. platycarpos* has been recorded as a casual in Seyðisfjörður by Gröntved (1942), only literature record available.

- *Heracleum mantegazzianum* Sommier & Levier

Nuovo Giorn. Bot. Ital., n.s., 2: 79 (1895)

Bjarnarkló (Tröllahvönn)

- *Heracleum persicum* Desf. ex Fisch.

Index Sem. Hort. Petrop. 7: 50 (1841)

Tröllakló

Heracleum sphondylium L.

Sp. Pl.: 249 (1753)

- *Heracleum sphondylium* L. subsp. *sphondylium*³²⁵

Húnakló

- ▼ *Imperatoria ostruthium* L.³²⁶

Sp. Pl.: 259 (1753)

Undrarót

- *Peucedanum ostruthium* (L.) Koch, Nova Acta Acad. Leop.-Carol. 12(1): 95 (1824)

- by König and Müller (1770)

- by Lauder Lindsay (1861)

- by Babington (1871)

- by Grønlund (1881)

- by Bennett (1886)

- rejected by Grøntved (1942)

- *Levisticum officinale* W.D.J. Koch

Nov. Actorum Acad. Caes. Leop.-Carol. Nat. Cur. 12(1): 101, f. 41 (1824)

Skessujurt

***Ligusticum scoticum* L.**

Sp. Pl.: 250 (1753)

Sæhvönn

- *Haloscias scoticum* (L.) Fries, Summ. Veg. Scand. 180 (1846)

- *Meum athamanticum* Jacq.

Fl. Austriac. 4: 2 (1776)

Bjarnarrót

- *Myrrhis odorata* (L.) Scop.

Fl. Carniol., ed. 2, 1: 207 (1771)

Spánarkerfill

- *Scandix odorata* L., Sp. Pl.: 256 (1753)

- *Torilis japonica* (Houtt.) DC.

Prodr. 4: 219 (1830)

Runnakerfill

- *Caucalis japonica* Houtt., Nat. Hist. 2(8): 42, t. 45, f. 1. (1777)

³²⁵ There is no doubt, that nominal subspecies is present in Iceland. There are also some reports about the presence of *H. sphondylium* subsp. *sibiricum* (Frøberg 2010b), but no vouchers are available to confirm these rather doubtful observations.

³²⁶ *I. ostruthium* was recorded by many of the early authors, but its presence in Iceland is really doubtful. These records are most probably misidentification of *A. archangelica* or *L. scoticum*.

ÚTDRÁTTUR Á ÍSLENSKU

Í þessu riti er birtur listi yfir allar æðplöntur sem þekktar eru á Íslandi og byggist hann fyrst og fremst á umfangsmiklum plöntusöfnum Náttúrufræðistofnunar Íslands sem varðveitt eru á Akureyri (AMNH) og í Garðabæ (ICEL). Fyrsti nútímalegi tékklistinn yfir íslenskar æðplöntur var gefinn út fyrir ríflega áratug (Hörður Kristinsson 2008) og var hann mikilvægur grunnur að frekari rannsóknum á fjölbreytileika og flokkun íslenskra æðplantna. Skráin sem hér birtist tekur eldri útgáfunni fram að því leyti að bætt er við umtalsverðum upplýsingum, þar á meðal um fjölda tegunda og annarra flokkunareininga eftir sem við á, og samheitum þeirra. Alls inniheldur nýja útgáfan nær 2500 plöntuheiði, þar af ríflega 1000 viðurkennd heiti og yfir 1400 samheiti. Listi yfir innlendar tegundir hefur verið uppfærður, auk þess sem birtur er tæmandi og endurskoðaður listi yfir slæðinga, bæði ílenda og tilfallandi, með nýjustu viðbótum. Einnig eru skráðar nokkrar mikilvægar ræktaðar tegundir (einkum þær sem mikið eru notaðar í skógrækt) vegna möguleikans á að þær ílendist í náinni framtíð.

Aðfluttar tegundir

Einnig vafi leikur á að nokkur fjöldi tegunda sem hafa verið taldar innlendar (Hörður Kristinsson 2008) eru í raun aldagamlar og aðfluttar tegundir sem bærust til Íslands með mönnum og ílentust fyrir löngu, einkum á landnámstímanum, miðöldum eða síðar. Uppruni þeirra í flóru landsins er enn óljós og eru þær flokkaðar sem fornaðfluttar tegundir (e. archaeophyte) og þar með ályktað að þær hafi borist til landsins fyrir 1770 (Wasowicz 2018). Stundum leikur þó vafi á hvort tegund sé raunverulega fornaðflutt og því hefur verið bætt við tveimur flokkum sem eiga að endurspegla það: (1) óviss innlend tegund og (2) aðflutt tegund með óþekkta landnámssögu. Nánari útlistun má finna í grein Pawels Wasowicz (2018). Staða nýrra aðfluttra plantna á Íslandi er yfirleitt nokkuð ljós en þegar um er að ræða tvær deilitegundir þar sem önnur er innlend en hin aðflutt eða ekki er ljóst hvernig tvær deilitegundir dreifa sér í náttúrunni, er þess getið með viðeigandi táknum (sjá bls. 8).

Óvissa í skráningum

Á liðnum öldum hefur safnast upp mikið magn heimilda um flóru Íslands í fjölda útgefna og óútgefna skýrsla og skráa. Eitt meginmarkmið nýrrar og endurskoðaðrar útgáfu íslenska æðplöntulistans var að yfirfara gögnin og meta á gagnrýninn hátt. Hefur sú grandskoðun leitt í ljós

vafasamar skráningar í gömlum flóruлистum frá 18. og 19. öld en einnig í nýrri flóru frá 20. öld. Til að varpa ljósi á þetta er í útgáfunni bætt við hópi tegunda (alls 150 tegundir) sem afskráðar eru úr íslensku flórunni og ástæður afskráningarinnar stuttlega skýrðar í neðanmálgreinum.

Flokkunarfræði og latnesk fræðiheiti

Til að varpa ljósi á fjölbreytileika íslensku flórunnar og til að skrá hámarksfjölda tegunda var notast við þröngar flokkunarfræðilegar skilgreiningar. Þegar upp kom misræmi í hvaða flokkunarfræðilega röð ætti að raða tegundum eða undirtegundum var í flestum tilvikum ákveðið að velja hærri flokkunarfræðilega röðun. Þegar um var að ræða bráðabirgðaskráningar og búsvæði tegunda óstaðfest var lægri flokkunarfræðileg röðun valin. Í þessari útgáfu æðplöntulistans eru blendingar ekki skráðir nema í undantekningartilvikum þegar um er að ræða vel þekktar og nokkuð algenga blendinga innlendra og ræktaðra tegunda.

Ættir eru settar fram samkvæmt kerfisbundinni röð en innan þeirra eru tegundir skráðar í stafrófsröð. Latneskar nafngiftir burkna og jafna fylgja að mestu Christenhusz o.fl. (2011b), nafngiftir berfrævinga Christenhusz o.fl. (2011a) og nafngiftir dulfrævinga APG IV (2016). Eingöngu voru notuð nöfn sem uppfylla skilmála Alþjóðlegu reglnanna um grasafraeðiheiti.

Samheiti eru almennt ekki skráð í tengslum við afskráðar tegundir. Á því eru þó nokkrar undantekningar þar sem samheiti eru listuð til að auka skýrleika. Í staðin er birtur listi yfir fyrirliggjandi heimildir sem sýna heiti sem höfundarnir notuðu til að vísa til viðkomandi tegundar en þar er oft ekki um samheiti, í þröngum skilningi þess orðs, að ræða.

Hjá mörgum tegundum er nauðsynlegt að tilgreina undirtegundir og eru þær þá skráðar fyrir neðan hverja tegund fyrir sig. Þeim getur fylgt listi yfir samheiti og almenn tegundaheiti eru birt þar sem það á við.

Listinn sem hér er birtur er hvorki endalegur né fullkominn. Hjá mörgum plöntuhópum er langt síðan endurskoðun plöntusýna fór fram og á það meðal annars við um ættkvíslir túnfífla (*Taraxacum*), undafífla (*Hieracium*) og augnfróar (*Euphrasia*). Því ber að skoða skráningu þeirra með gagnrýnum augum og til bráðabirgða. Ljóst er að frekari rannsókn er þörf til að öðlast betri skilning á líffræðilegum breytileika innan ættkvíslanna héraendis.

Tölfræði

Til íslensku æðplöntuflórunnar teljast 426 innlendar tegundir. Til viðbótar eru 10 tegundir skráðir sem óvissar innlendar tegundir, 10 tegundir eru aðfluttar tegundir með óþekkta landnámssögu og 19 tegundir eru fornaðfluttar (sbr. Wasowicz 2018). Auk þess eru 65 tegundir æðplantna sem hafa numið land á Íslandi og teljast nú ílendar. Á Íslandi eru því samanlagt 530 tegundir (innlendar og aðfluttar) sem geta myndað stofna og viðhaldið sjálfum sér (1. mynd). Ein tegund flokkast sem útdauð hér á landi (Wasowicz and Heiðmarsson 2019). Að auki eru 282 erlendar tegundir sem hafa verið skráðar að minnsta kosti einu sinni í íslenskri náttúru, utan ræktaðra svæða, en hafa ekki náð fótfestu.

Fjórar ættir plantna eru tegundaríkastar og til þeirra teljast 35% af heildarfjölda innlendra tegunda. Þetta eru stararætt (Cyperaceae), grasætt (Poaceae), körfublómaætt (Asteraceae) og hjartagrasætt (Caryophyllaceae). Tegundir sem eftir standa, 65%, tilheyra 84 ættum og er hlutur hvernar ættar minni en 5% (2. mynd).

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